

D3.3 Feasibility studies and selection of final uses cases

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¹ PU = Public

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Summary

Begonia project

Europe is embarking on a transformative endeavour to modernise digital information usage, with a focus on enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and connectivity of our energy and transportation sectors. At the core of this initiative lies the development of advanced ODPs that transcend national boundaries, leveraging state-of-the-art technologies such as data sharing, cloud computing, and network connectivity.

The BEGONIA Project is an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action that aims to expedite this digital transformation in the energy and transport sectors, analysing the most promising solutions and providing information to the European Commission to set up and fund future works project(s).

BEGONIA has the goal of identifying, studying and preparing the development of ODPs across different EU countries, starting from the identification of 10 cross-border and possibly cross-sector (energy and transport) use cases, meticulously shortlisting three based on predefined criteria, and evaluating their impacts through proof-of-concept implementation of their ODPs.

Summary of the Deliverable

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	Description
AESA	Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
ANAC	Agência Nacional de Aviação Civil
API	Application Programming Interface
BCR	Benefit Cost Ration
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
CBP	Custom and Border Protection
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CF	Carbon Footprint
CL	Controllable Load
CP	Charging Point
CPP	Charging Point Providers
DC	Data Centre
DEA	Danish Energy Agency
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSS	Decision Support System
EAG	European Air Group
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
EEDI	Energy Efficiency Design Index
EEXI	Energy Efficiency Existing Index
EFTI	Electronic Freight Transport Information
EEU	Energy End User
eIDAS	electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services
EMS	Energy Management Systems
EMSP	E-Mobility Service Providers

ES	Electricity Supplier
ET	Electric Truck
EU	European Union
EU ETS	European Union Emissions Trading System
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Standards Organisation
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LPWAN	Low Power Wide Area Network
LUC	Light UAS Operator Certificate
ML	Machine Learning
MPO	Metering Point Operator
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MS	Milestone
NPV	Net Present Value
ODP	Operational Digital Platform
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PC	Project Coordinator
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RES	Renewable Energy Source

SOC	State Of Charge
SORA	Specific Operations Risk Assessment
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft Systems
UC	Use Case
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

1.1. BEGONIA Project

The aim of the BEGONIA Project is to expedite the European digital transformation by analyzing promising solutions and providing recommendations to the European Commission (EC). Specifically, the project focuses on identifying, studying, and preparing the development of ODPs in the energy and transport sectors across various European Union (EU) countries, with the goal of facilitating the setup and funding of future projects.

1.2. Work Package 3

Work Package (WP) 3 is exploiting the six shortlisted Use Cases that were produced by WP2 Deliverable D2.2 (<https://www.begonia-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Begonia-D2.2.pdf>), towards fulfilling the following objectives:

- Develop technical criteria for filtering the Use Cases,
- Conduct a feasibility study for each shortlisted Use Case,
- Finalize the selection of Use Cases based on technical feasibility, regulatory compliance, and cost-benefit analysis,
- Design the solution architecture and governance for each selected Use Case,
- Develop the necessary regulatory and technical frameworks for each Use Case and ensure that the selected Use Cases meet the technical requirements and interoperability standards of the digital infrastructure platform.

This way, WP 3 will deliver the three final Use Cases to WP4 for designing specific piloting activities. The structure of WP3 is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Structure of BEGONIA WP3

1.3. Deliverable description

In particular, Deliverable D3.3 “Feasibility studies and selection of final Use Cases”, which is issued in April 2025, is serving the need for Task 3.3 “Conduct feasibility studies for each

shortlisted Use Cases and selection of final cases”, by providing a detailed cost-benefit analysis of the six Uses Cases previously selected and conducting feasibility studies on the economic, technical, regulatory and governance aspects of the six Use Cases to select the three best Use Cases for piloting. Since technical solution architecture, regulatory and governance framework have been covered in detail in Deliverable D3.1 and D3.2, respectively, Deliverable D3.3 used the analysis in D3.1 and D3.2 to provide the feasibility studies of the six Use Cases, in addition to the detailed cost-benefit analysis of these Use Cases.

1.4. Relation to other deliverables

Deliverable D3.3 is based on the technical requirements analysis that came out of Deliverable D3.1 (<https://www.begonia-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/BEGONIA-D3.1.pdf>), which was issued in December 2024, on the six shortlisted UCs and the relevant potential technologies for each one of them. This deliverable also uses the inputs from Deliverable D3.2 which was issued in March 2025 and focused on the solution architecture and governance framework. Meanwhile, Deliverable D3.3 will feed information to Deliverable D3.4 - Evaluation framework and governance scheme for the final cases, due in May 2025, which will describe the selection process for the three final Use Cases and the detailed implementation and governance plan for each one of them.

2. Description of the six Use Cases (UCs)

2.1. UCI: Electricity customer-centric ODP

The electricity customers centric ODP is designed to place consumers at the centre of the energy ecosystem by enabling smarter energy management, market participation, and seamless integration with renewable energy sources (RES). The platform provides real-time insights into energy consumption, allowing users to optimize their electricity usage, receive personalized recommendations, and actively participate in demand response programs. By leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as IoT, AI, and secure data sharing frameworks, this ODP facilitates automated energy supplier switching, supports engagement in virtual energy communities (VEC), and enables customers to contribute to grid stability by offering demand flexibility services. By integrating RES, controllable devices, electric vehicles (EVs), and electric trucks (ETs), the platforms enable customers to contribute to grid stability savings, reduce energy billing and operational costs, and actively participate in green transition programs by reducing CO₂ emissions and air pollutants such as SO_x, NO_x, and PM₁₀. Electricity customers centric ODPs support forecasting, decision-making, and personalized recommendations, ensuring varying regulations across EU member states while fostering sustainable energy practices.

Objective: The Electricity customer centric ODP aims to introduce cross-border services for electricity consumers, such as automated supplier switching with smart metering, virtual energy communities, and demand-side flexibility. These services benefit all involved stakeholders, including end-users, electricity suppliers, demand aggregators, transmission system operators (TSOs), and distribution system operators (DSOs) while supporting RES integration into the power systems.

Scale and dimension: The platforms will be implemented in Germany, Sweden, and Denmark with tenth (1/10) of the households considered every year by the ODP while all the existing capacity of RES, EVs, and ETs allowed to participate in the platform.

Engineering features: The platform integrates smart meters, IoT sensors, AI algorithms, edge computing frameworks and cloud infrastructure.

Stakeholders: The primary stakeholders are electricity consumers, RES providers (solar and wind farms), EV and ET users (owners), aggregators, TSOs, and electricity retailers. There are also secondary stakeholders for the ODP such as Policymakers, regulatory bodies, technology providers, data management entities and environmental NGOs.

Socio-economic impact: The platform will reduce electricity costs through optimized energy use and market competition, enhance system reliability, lowering operational costs for stakeholders. In addition, the ODP will empower consumers with transparent energy options and increase energy equity across borders.

2.2. UCII: AI-driven ODP for integration of EVs, ETs, RES and Grid

AI-driven ODP for integrating EVs, ETs, RES, and the grid focuses on integrating RES with dynamic weather adaptation and grid management to enhance energy sustainability and efficiency. With the increasing adoption of EVs ETs, and RES, it is crucial to ensure efficient access to charging infrastructure, optimal route planning, and effective grid integration. The platform leverages AI-driven analytics, real-time traffic insights, and dynamic pricing models to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of charge point (CP) booking, charging coordination, and grid flexibility services. By integrating historical usage patterns, RES forecasts, and traffic congestion detection, the ODP facilitates data-driven decision-making that benefits commuters, logistics operators, and grid managers. The dynamic pricing mechanism ensures that EVs and ETs are incentivized to charge during periods of high renewables production, optimizing grid stability while promoting sustainable transport solutions.

Objective: The AI-driven ODP for integrating EV, ET, RES and grid aims to leverage real time weather data, forecasting, and demand response to enhance grid flexibility, reduce energy costs and emissions, and ensure seamless interoperability for a sustainable, low-carbon energy systems.

Scale and dimension: The proposed ODP will be deployed at scale in Austria, Hungary, and Slovenia.

Engineering features: The platform will integrate AI-based predictive models for grid balancing and demand response, IoT-enabled smart meters for real-time energy monitoring, 5G connectivity for high-speed data transmission, and Middleware integration to connect grid management systems, RES providers, and charging infrastructure.

Stakeholders: The primary stakeholders include EV users, fleet operators, charging point operators, grid operators and RES providers are the main stakeholders.

Socio-economic impact: The proposed ODP is expected to lower electricity costs (efficiency), optimize logistics operations (time, productivity), and reduce grid maintenance costs. They will enhance renewable energy integration, lower greenhouse gas emissions, reduce fossil fuel consumption and increase EV and ET adoption, equitable access to sustainable energy solutions, and reduced energy poverty.

2.3. UCIII: Digitalisation of data centres

The Digitalization of data centres for energy efficiency and waste heat reuse UC aims to enhance the sustainability and operational efficiency of data centers (DCs) by leveraging advanced digital technologies. As DCs are among the largest energy consumers, optimizing their electricity usage and integrating waste heat recovery solutions is critical

for cost reduction and environmental impact. This UC proposes an ODP that enables DCs to function as cross-sector prosumers, participating in the EU energy market while also providing grid flexibility services. Through real-time monitoring, AI-driven analytics, and demand-side flexibility mechanisms, DCs can optimize energy flows, improve cooling efficiency, and support RES integration.

The platform offers two sets of services: DC-related services for monitoring, operation, and planning, and grid-related services for flexibility capacity estimation, computational load transfer, and ancillary service participation. By integrating forecasting models and automated control systems, the ODP ensures that DCs minimize energy waste, strategically shift computational loads across EU member states, and contribute to grid stability. Additionally, the platform aligns with EU sustainability directives by facilitating transparent energy reporting, and regulatory compliance monitoring.

Objective: The digitalization of data centers ODP aims to enhance sustainability and efficiency by integrating advanced energy storage, AI-driven optimization, and real-time monitoring. Through predictive analytics and waste heat reuse, the ODP reduces operational costs, improves energy utilization, and contributes to grid flexibility services. By leveraging RES and ensuring compliance with regulatory standards, they transform data centers into active participants in the energy transition, optimizing their environmental impact.

Scale and dimension: The proposed DCs ODP will be implemented in *Germany, Sweden, and Denmark*, enabling DCs to operate as cross-sector prosumers at the EU scale. The platform supports transmission networks by providing ancillary services, dynamically shifting data loads across borders, and optimizing real-time energy analytics for innovative equipment integration. As AI and HPC workloads continue to rise, the DCs ODP will focus on meeting growing AI demands while ensuring sustainability through RES, controllable loads (CL), energy reuse/conversion technologies, digital interfaces, and IoT. The ODP facilitates integration with EU electricity markets, and mobilities to encourage DCs aggregators across Member States to address increasing grid-adaptive intelligence loads. The ODP framework leverages *digital twins* and advanced energy management techniques to optimize resource allocation, grid participation, and operational efficiency across multiple DCs in different European regions. The UC targets small- to large-scale data centers across Europe, which are increasingly consuming electricity and generating excess heat due to rising AI and HPC workloads.

Engineering features: It includes smart sensors and IoT connectivity, digital twin technology, AI-driven predictive analytics, grid and heating services integration, cloud-based data processing and orchestration & workload management.

Stakeholders: The primary stakeholders include data center operators and energy managers, RES providers, TSOs & regulators, AI and cloud technology providers, environmental agencies, policymakers and research institutions studying energy efficiency

Socio-economic impact: The ODP are expected to reduce operational energy costs and improve grid efficiency through demand-side flexibility, enhance energy security and critical system uptime through AI-based energy forecasting, lower CO₂ emissions, and promote sustainable energy practices via heat reuse and renewable integration.

2.4. UCIV: Digital permits for drone-based inspections

The digital permits for drone-based inspections in linear infrastructures aims to streamline and digitize the authorization processes for drone operations, particularly in cross-border scenarios involving Spain, Portugal, and France. Traditional permit approvals are slow, highly manual, and involve multiple regulatory bodies, leading to significant delays, especially in cross-border operations. Leveraging blockchain technology, this ODP facilitates efficient and secure interactions among infrastructure managers, air traffic control providers, regulatory authorities, and drone operators. By digitizing flight permits and standardizing validation processes, the UC significantly reduces administrative delays, minimizes human errors, and enhances regulatory compliance.

Objective: The digital permit for drone-based inspections in linear infrastructures aims to reduce the time required to obtain flight permits for drone-based inspections, minimize human errors and foster better coordination among air safety agencies, infrastructure managers, and public authorities.

Scale and dimensions: The ODPs will be implemented in Spain, France and Portugal.

Engineering features: The platform will integrate blockchain-based platform for secure and transparent permit management, real-time tracking of permit validation processes, automated workflow for cross-border permit approval and middleware integration with existing infrastructure management and airspace monitoring systems.

Stakeholders: Infrastructure managers, air traffic control providers, regulatory and public authorities and drone operators are the main stakeholders.

Socio-economic impact: The platform will reduce administrative costs, improve productivity in maintenance operations, and decrease disruption costs associated with traditional inspection methods. The environmental impact is that it reduces road traffic disruptions and improves management of environmental protection areas. Finally, the social impact is to enhance safety for maintenance staff and road users, and better public acceptance of drone operations through transparency and regulatory compliance.

The ODP complies with European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) regulations, IEEE 3205-2023, IEEE 3801-2022 and National regulations of Spain, Portugal, and France. Additionally, the interoperability of the platform across jurisdictions supports seamless cross-border drone operations, helping to improve infrastructure maintenance, road safety, and environmental protection while reducing operational costs and disruptions.

2.5. UCV: Smart port operations

The smart port operations UC aims to enhance efficiency, safety, and sustainability in port management through the integration of AI-driven cameras, drone systems, and digital platforms. By leveraging real-time monitoring and volumetric measurement technologies, this UC enables precise tracking of docks, cranes, ships, and stockpiles, ensuring optimal resource allocation and regulatory compliance. The FIWARE digital platform, as adopted by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), serves as the central hub for data integration, providing advanced analytics, visualisation, and decision-making tools to improve port operations.

Objective: smart ports operations ODP aims to develop and implement advanced, AI-driven monitoring and digital twin technologies (integrated with FIWARE platforms) for real-time optimization of port operations, enabling efficient resource allocation, streamlined logistics, and the creation of scalable, replicable models for global port digital transformation.

Scale and dimensions: This Use Case will be piloted in the Port of Sevilla, the only inland Port of Spain with a direct connection to the Atlantic Ocean.

Engineering features: The platform will involve the deployment of IoT sensors for continuous monitoring of air and water quality, AI-driven cameras for real-time video analytics to enhance port operations, and drone fleets integrated with cloud-based analytics to provide aerial intelligence and volumetric data for improved situational awareness and decision-making.

Stakeholders: Port authority, port staff, ship operators, customers authorities and logistic companies are the main stakeholders of this ODP.

Socio-economic impact: The platform drives a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions by enabling optimized and cleaner logistics operations, directly contributing to EU decarbonization goals. It lowers operational costs for logistics companies through improved fuel efficiency and resource allocation, enhancing their competitiveness in sustainable trade markets. Additionally, it improves worker safety and security through AI-powered surveillance and increased transparency across port workflows.

2.6. UCVI: Carbon footprint of port supply chain

The carbon footprint (CF) of port supply chain UC focuses on establishing a standardized, transparent, and verifiable methodology for tracking and managing carbon emissions in logistics, particularly within port operations. Given the critical role of ports as transport and energy hubs, this UC proposes an ODP that integrates real-time and historical data from diverse sources such as shipping emissions, fuel consumption, cargo tracking, and multimodal transportation data. The platform aims to bridge the gap in emissions tracking by automating data collection from ships, trucks, and port equipment, ensuring a comprehensive and reliable CF calculation.

Objective: The CF of ports supply chain aims to develop a blockchain-enabled ODP that enables accurate tracking, calculation, and reporting of the CF of goods across logistics chains, while reducing greenhouse gas emissions through route optimization, cleaner transport modes, and improved operational efficiency; enhancing transparency and regulatory compliance with EU frameworks such as Fit for 55, CBAM, and ETS; and enabling real-time CF monitoring and reporting through the integration of IoT, AI, and cloud-based technologies to support sustainable, data-driven logistics management.

Scale and dimensions: This UC will be piloted at the Port of Vigo and the port of Leixões, a major logistics hub in Spain and Portugal.

Engineering features: The ODP will handle real-time data from IoT sensors, blockchain records, and cloud-based analytics, ensuring accurate CF tracking across the supply chain using blockchain.

Stakeholders: The primary stakeholders include port operators and authorities, logistics and transport companies, manufacturers and exporters, freight forwarders and shipping companies are the main stakeholders for this ODP.

Socio-economic impact: The proposed ODP will reduce CO₂ emissions through optimized transport routes and cleaner logistics operations, directly supporting EU decarbonization targets, lower operational costs for logistics companies by improving fuel efficiency and resource allocation, enhancing competitiveness in sustainable trade markets and increase consumer and industry awareness through transparent CF tracking, promoting sustainable supply chain decisions and long-term environmental responsibility.

This ODP aligns with key EU policies and industry standards, ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks and supporting the transition toward sustainable logistics: Fit for 55 & FuelEU Maritime Initiative, Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), EU ETS and Operational Program for Transport (OP 2025).

3. Cost-benefit analysis of the six UCs

3.1. Cost-benefit analysis methodology

For the cost-benefit analysis of these six selected UCs, we follow the cost-benefit methodology proposed by [1] and [2]. These methodologies focus on the cost-benefit analysis of smart grids and renewable energy projects in developing countries, and smart grid initiatives in the Isernia region of Italy, respectively. Both scientific policy reports outline seven steps for cost-benefit analysis, with one key difference where [2] includes *Establish the baseline* as step 4 but omits the *Sensitivity analysis* described as step 7 in [1]. While recognizing the value of both reports, we adopt the CBA methodology outlined in [1] and proposed our new approach, which is in line with most EU cost-benefits analysis frameworks. We also refine Step 7 as *Sensitivity analysis and risk assessment* to adopt mitigation strategies as well. Since each UC is independent, we conduct the cost-benefit analysis separately, ensuring the possibility of implementing each UC in its specific geographic scope. The framework we propose for the cost-benefit analysis and its seven steps are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Seven-step framework for CBA

Cost-benefit analysis framework	
Steps	Procedure
Step 1	Define the Use Case
Step 2	Map technologies to functions
Step 3	Map functions to benefits
Step 4	Monetize benefits
Step 5	Quantify costs
Step 6	Compare costs and benefits
Step 7	Sensitivity analysis and risk assessment

3.2. Cost benefit analysis: Electricity customers centric ODP

Step 1. Define the Use Case

Please refer to Section 2.1.

Step 2. Map technologies to functions

Step 2 in the cost-benefit analysis determines which functionalities of the electricity customers centric ODPs are activated by the technologies. The technologies involved provide different functionalities that enable the ODP's benefits.

Table 2: Mapping of technologies onto functions for UCI

Functions						
		A. Data and information collection	B. Interoperability and system integration	C. Smart load forecasting and grid balancing	D. Automating switching and secure transactions	E. Decision support system
Technologies (Assets)	Smart meters		•	•	•	•
	IoT sensors	•	•	•	•	•
	AI algorithms	•		•	•	•
	Communication protocol	•	•	•	•	•
	Edge computing frameworks		•			•
	Cloud Infrastructure		•			•
	Data integration					
	Data lake & databases	•	•	•	•	•
	Edge network 5G	•	•			•
	Message queues	•	•			

The technologies outlined in Table 2 are strategically mapped to their respective functionalities to ensure seamless integration, optimization, and interoperability within electricity customers centric ODPs. Each technology plays a distinct yet interconnected role in supporting the overall energy systems.

Step 3. Map functions to benefits

The technologies and functionalities outlined are mapped to benefits. Table 3 summarizes the mapping of the ODP's benefits to functionalities. The benefits are categorized as economic, system reliability and environmental sustainability.

Table 3: Mapping functionalities to benefits for UCI

Benefits		Functions				
		A. Data and information Collection	B. Improved interoperability and system integration	C. Smart load forecasting and grid balancing	D. Automating switching and secure transactions	E. Decision support system
Economic benefits	Reduction in billing	•			•	

	Reduction in transaction costs	•		•	•	•
	Cost saving through demand response			•	•	
	Cost savings from peak load reduction	•	•	•	•	•
	Revenue generation from energy trading (virtual markets)			•	•	•
Reliability benefits	Grid stability savings		•	•		
	Avoided energy curtailment	•		•		•
Environmental benefits	Reduced CO2 emissions		•		•	•
	Reduced Sox, Nox and PM10	•			•	•

Economic benefits arise from reduction billing and operational cost efficiency improvements, and revenue generation, enabled by real-time data collection, system interoperability, AI-driven forecasting, automated transactions, and decision support systems. Reduction in billing costs is facilitated through data and information collection and decision support systems, which enable predictive maintenance and automated fault detection, minimizing system downtime. This reduction is measured by the decrease in system downtime per year, monetized by the number of operational hours saved multiplied by the average cost per outage. *Reduction in transaction costs* is achieved through improved interoperability, automated transactions, and decision support tools that streamline administrative processes, energy trading, and billing systems. These efficiencies lower manual processing expenses, measured by the reduction in administrative and transaction costs per unit of energy traded or billed. AI-driven demand response mechanisms optimize energy consumption by shifting loads to off-peak hours, leading to cost savings from reduced electricity prices and lower peak demand charges. *Cost savings from peak load reduction* are realized through real-time grid balancing, demand-side management, and adaptive energy distribution, which reduce reliance on expensive backup power plants. Enabled by data collection, system interoperability,

forecasting, automated transactions, and decision support, this function lowers the cost per MW of peak demand avoided. *Time savings for consumers* translate into economic benefits, particularly for EV users and energy prosumers. *Revenue generation from energy trading in virtual energy markets* is enhanced by interoperability, forecasting, and automation, allowing optimized bidding strategies and improved market participation. *Reductions in energy waste and operational costs* are achieved through data-driven monitoring, smart metering, automated billing, and decision support tools, ensuring more efficient energy usage and lower transaction overhead.

The ODPs also contribute to grid stability by improving interoperability and forecasting, which enhance coordination between energy sources and demand centers. AI-powered forecasting and automated control mechanisms help prevent energy curtailment. This ensures excess RES is effectively utilized rather than wasted. Enhanced energy security is also a key outcome, supported by system integration and smart load balancing, which improves resilience against supply fluctuations and grid disruptions. Finally, *environmental benefits* arise from reductions in CO₂ and air pollutant emissions, facilitated by smart load forecasting, automated transactions, and decision support systems that optimize renewable energy utilization. Lower reliance on fossil fuel-based power plants, combined with reduced energy curtailment, leads to measurable decreases in CO₂ emissions (kg per MWh avoided) and SO_x, NO_x, and PM₁₀ emissions.

Step 4: Monetize benefits

The next step is calculating benefits and applying monetary metrics. Table 4 presents detailed formulas, calculations and necessary parameters.

Table 4: Metrics and formulas for calculations of benefits for UCI

Benefits	Metrics and formula of calculations
<p>Reduction in billing costs</p>	<p>Billing cost savings result from reduced energy consumption due to ODP-enabled efficiency improvements, including smart meters enabling real-time demand optimization, increased self-consumption of RES, optimized EV and ET charging schedules, virtual energy community (VEC) participation lowering overall demand.</p> $\Delta B = \%EE_{ODP} \times EE_{TOT} \times t_e$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\%EE_{ODP}$ total net yearly electricity energy (EE) reduction per customer due to ODP • EE_{TOT} = total yearly energy consumption [kWh] • t_e = average electricity energy tariff (€/kWh) <p>The energy reduction percentage $\%EE_{ODP}$ due to ODP is calculated as:</p> $\%EE_{ODP} = \left(\frac{\sum_{m=1}^M E_{m,ODP}}{\sum_{m=1}^M E_{m,TOT}} \right) \times 100\%$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $E_{m,ODP}$ = total monthly energy consumption per customer with ODP

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $E_{m,TOT}$ = total monthly energy consumption per customer without ODPs (historical reference) • M = total months analyzed <p>In this analysis, an average reduction of about 3% has been considered for calculation, mostly accounting for residential customers¹.</p>
<p>Reduction in transaction costs</p>	<p>Transaction cost savings from automated billing, smart meters, and virtual energy trading.</p> $\Delta TC = H_{int} \times \left(\frac{VEC_{new} + RES_{int} + EV_{int} + ET_{int}}{H_{tot}} \right) \times (TC_{ODP} \times (1 - \%TC_{reduction}))$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H_{int} = number of households integrated into ODP • H_{tot} = total number of households in the country • VEC_{new} = new virtual energy communities created • RES_{int} = households with integrated renewable energy sources² • EV_{int} = households with integrated EV charging • ET_{int} = businesses/industries with integrated ETs • $\%TC_{reduction}$ = %age of transaction cost reduction per household with ODP
<p>Cost saving through demand response</p>	$\Delta C_{DR} = H_{int} \times \left(\frac{EV_{shift} + ET_{shift} + RES_{self} + VEC_{engaged}}{H_{tot}} \right) \times \left((P_{t,peak} - P_{t,off}) \times \Delta E_t \right)_{ODP(\%)}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EV_{shift}, ET_{shift} = proportion of EV and ET demand shifted to off – peak hours • RES_{self} = share of RES self – consumed within the household • $VEC_{engaged}$ = share of households actively participating in virtual energy trading • $P_{t,peak}, P_{t,off}$ = electricity prices during peak and off – peak hours (€ per kWh) • ΔE_t = total shifted energy demand (MWh) $\Delta E_t = H_{int} \times (EV_{shift} + ET_{shift} + RES_{self} + VEC_{engaged})$
<p>Cost savings from peak load reduction</p>	<p>Peak load is reduced through smart scheduling of EV charging, ET energy optimization, and increased RES storage.</p> $\Delta C_{PLR} = H_{int} \times C_{MW} \times \left(\frac{EV_{smart} + ET_{smart} + RES_{storage} + VEC_{flex}}{EV_{tot} + ET_{tot} + RES_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times \Delta P$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VEC_{flex} = households using dynamic pricing and flexibility services in virtual energy • $RES_{storage}$ = proportion of RES stored & used instead of curtailed • EV_{smart}, ET_{smart} = %age of EVs/ETs participated in flexibility trading • C_{MW} = cost per MW of peak demand avoided (€/MW)

¹ Cost-benefit analysis of Smart Grid projects: Isernia (<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC111852>) used the 3% reduction to calculate the observed reduction due to smart info kit, which we predict the operational digital platforms expected to achieve.

² $X_{year} = X_{current\ year} \times (1 + growth\ rate)$, where X_{year} is the projected value for year 2026-2035, $X_{current\ year}$ is the current (fixed) year, $growth\ rate$ is the annual %age for RES, EVs, and ETs.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ΔP = reduced peak demand (MW)
Revenue generation from energy trading (virtual markets)	<p>Revenue from energy trading in virtual markets increases when households and businesses actively participate in decentralized trading, using electricity customers centered ODP.</p> $\Delta R_{ET} = H_{int} \times \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{VEC_{engaged} + RES_{smart} + EV_{bid} + ET_{bid}}{RES_{tot} + EV_{tot} + ET_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times P_{t,ODP(\%)} \times \Delta Q_t$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $VEC_{engaged}$ = households actively participating in virtual energy trading³ • RES_{smart} = proportion of renewable energy sold into virtual markets • EV_{bid}, ET_{bid} = share of EVs/ETs participating in demand response bidding • $P_{t,ODP(\%)}$ = %age of energy prices due to ODP – enabled market integration (€/MWh) • ΔQ_t = additional energy traded due to ODP (MWh)
Grid stability savings	<p>Smart EV charging, ET scheduling, and household RES balancing improve grid stability.</p> $\Delta C_{GS} = H_{int} \times N_o \times C_o \times \left(\frac{RES_{balanced} + EV_{grid} + ET_{grid} + VEC_{stability}}{RES_{tot} + EV_{tot} + ET_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times (1 - \%LR)$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $RES_{balanced}$ = %age of RES for grid balancing services • EV_{grid}, ET_{grid} = %age of EVs and ETs connected the grid and providing grid stability services • $VEC_{stability}$ = households providing grid – balancing services • N_o = number of outages prevented • C_o = cost of outages prevented (€/event) • $\%LR$ = Load reduction % in peak load stress time due to ODP (15% in our calculation)
Avoided energy curtailment	<p>Curtailment is reduced through RES storage, demand-side flexibility, and virtual energy transactions.</p> $\Delta E_{EC} = H_{int} \times \left(\frac{RES_{storage} + VEC_{active}}{RES_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times \Delta E_{curt} \times P_E \times (1 - \%CR)$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VEC_{active} = proportion of households actively trading excess RES • ΔE_{curt} = reduction in curtailed energy (MWh) • P_E = value of curtailed energy (€ per MWh) • $\%CR$ = curtailment reduction cost % (5% improvement considered)
	$\Delta CO_2 = pCO_2 \times (\Delta EE_{RES,ODP} + \Delta EE_{EV,ODP} + \Delta EE_{ET,ODP} + \Delta EE_{awareness,ODP} + VEC_{CO_2,ODP})$ <p>where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pCO_2 = carbon emission price [€/tonne] • $\Delta EE_{RES,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from ODP-enabled RES [tonne CO₂/year]

<p>Reduced CO2 emissions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $+\Delta EE_{EV,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from ODP-enabled EV smart charging [tonne CO₂/year] • $\Delta EE_{ET,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from ETs due to ODP-enabled smart charging [tonnes CO₂/year] • $\Delta EE_{awareness,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from ODP-enabled demand-side energy savings [tonnes CO₂/year] • $VEC_{CO_2,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from ODP-enabled VEC participation [tonnes CO₂/year] • CO₂ emission saving from RES $\Delta EE_{RES,ODP} = ERS_{ccapacity,ODP} \times h_{eq} \times RES_{factor}$ • $ERS_{ccapacity,ODP}$ = Additional RES capacity integrated into the ODP [MW] • h_{eq} = Equivalent full-load hours of RES production [hours/year] • ERS_{factor} = CO₂ emissions displaced per MWh of RES generation [tonnes CO₂/MWh] • CO₂ emission saving from electric mobility $\Delta EE_{EV,ODP} = km_{year} \times N_{EV,ODP} \times CS_{ODP} (ERS_{factor,ff} - ERS_{factor,EV})$ $\Delta EE_{ET,ODP} = km_{year} \times N_{ET,ODP} \times CS_{ODP} (ERS_{factor,ff} - ERS_{factor,ET})$ • km_{year} = Annual km driven per EV [km/year] • CS_{ODP} = ODP-enabled charging stations [count] • $N_{EV,ODP}$ = EVs using ODP-enabled smart charging [count] • $ERS_{factor,ff}$ = CO₂ emissions per km for fossil fuel vehicles [tonnes CO₂/km] • $ERS_{factor,EV}$ = CO₂ emissions per km for EVs [tonnes CO₂/km] • $N_{ET,ODP}$ = ETs using ODP-enabled route & charge optimization [count] • $ERS_{factor,ET}$ = CO₂ emissions per km for electric trucks [tonnes CO₂/km] • CO₂ emission saving from customer awareness Reduced electricity consumption can be translated into carbon emission savings according to the national energy production mix. Hence environmental benefits can be calculated as: $\Delta EE_{awareness,ODP} = EE_{TOT} \times \%EE_{ODP} \times ERS_{factor}$ • EE_{TOT} = Total electricity consumption [MWh/year] • $\%EE_{ODP}$ = Energy efficiency improvement due to ODP [%]
<p>Reduced SOx, NOx and PM10</p>	<p>Air pollutant emission saving can be monetized as follows: $\Delta AP = P_{AP} \times (\Delta AP_{RES,ODP} + \Delta AP_{EV,ODP} + \Delta AP_{ET,ODP} + \Delta AP_{awareness,ODP})$ where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P_{AP} = Air pollutant cost [€/tonne] (societal cost of pollutants like NO_x, SO_x, PM10) • $\Delta AP_{RES,ODP}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled RES integration [tonnes/year]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\Delta AP_{EV,ODP}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled EV smart charging & routing [tonnes/year] • $\Delta AP_{ET,ODP}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled ET smart charging & routing [tonnes/year] • $\Delta AP_{awareness,ODP}$ = Air pollutant saving from ODP-enabled customer awareness [tonne] <p>Air pollutant emission savings from RES</p> $\Delta AP_{RES} = \text{tonne}_{AP/MWh} \times \Delta EE_{RES,year}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\text{tonne}_{AP/MWh}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled demand-side energy savings [tonnes/year] <p>Air pollutant emission saving from electric mobility</p> $\Delta AP_{EV,ODP} = \text{km}_{year} \times N_{EV,ODP} \times CS_{EV,ODP} (\text{tonne}_{AP/km,ff} - \text{tonne}_{AP/km,EV})$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • km_{year} = Annual distance driven per EV [km/year] • CS_{ODP} = ODP-enabled charging stations [count] • $N_{EV,ODP}$ = EVs using ODP-enabled smart charging & routing [count] • $\text{tonne}_{AP/km,EV}$ = Air pollutant emissions per km for EVs [tonnes AP/km] • $\text{tonne}_{AP/km,ff}$ = Air pollutant emissions per km for fossil fuel vehicles [tonnes AP/km] <p>The same formula is used for ET emission reduction</p> <p>Air pollutant reduction from demand-side energy savings (consumer awareness & efficiency)</p> $\Delta AP_{awareness,ODP} = EE_{TOT} \times \%EE_{ODP} \times \text{tonne}_{AP/MWh}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE_{TOT} = Total electricity consumption [MWh/year] • $\%EE_{ODP}$ = ODP-enabled energy efficiency improvement [%]

To effectively evaluate the benefits of the ODPs and implement them in Germany, Sweden, and Denmark from 2026 to 2035, we apply the detailed formulas in Table 4. We also establish comprehensive assumptions during the costs and benefits calculations. The assumptions serve as the foundation for calculating each benefit by providing necessary data inputs. For all assumptions, data sources, and parameter values, we refer to the reader Appendix (Tables 57, 58, and 59).

Table 5: Economic, reliability and environmental benefits for UCI

Year	Economic benefits (€)					Reliability benefits (€)		Environmental benefits (€)	
	RBC	RTC	CSDR	CSPLR	RGET	GSS	AEC	CO ₂	SO _x
2026	4,397,632	276,706	325,847	698,693	5,195,020	3,038,444	10,672,830	46,994,129	2,011,632
2027	8,795,265	776,351	1,303,386	1,298,884	10,906,630	6,404,678	18,424,073	50,153,716	2,129,766

2028	13,192,897	1,501,090	2,932,620	1,813,327	17,173,407	10,027,239	24,663,002	53,534,777	2,255,546
2029	17,590,529	2,453,278	5,213,546	2,252,837	24,036,494	13,846,745	30,032,149	57,153,915	2,389,498
2030	21,988,162	3,635,493	8,146,166	2,626,653	31,539,758	17,813,675	34,869,564	61,029,015	2,532,186
2031	26,385,794	5,050,552	11,730,479	2,942,719	39,729,960	21,886,638	39,372,006	65,179,334	2,684,217
2032	30,783,426	6,701,537	15,966,485	3,207,905	48,656,930	26,030,991	43,663,053	69,625,617	2,846,240
2033	35,181,059	8,591,814	20,854,185	3,428,185	58,373,766	30,217,738	47,825,144	74,390,212	3,018,952
2034	39,578,691	10,725,066	26,393,578	3,608,780	68,937,029	34,422,635	51,916,069	79,497,195	3,203,100
2035	43,976,324	13,105,315	32,584,664	3,754,272	80,406,957	38,625,467	55,978,077	84,972,509	3,399,487
Total	241,869,778	52,817,202	125,450,955	25,632,254	384,955,951	202,314,250	357,415,969	642,530,418	26,470,623

Note: RBC is reduced in billing costs, RTC is reduction in transaction costs, CSDR is cost saving using demand response, CSPLR is cost saving from peak load reduction, RGET is revenue generation from energy trading, GSS is Grid stability savings, AEC is avoided energy curtailment, CO₂ is CO₂ emission reduction and SO_x is air pollutant reduction (SO_x, NO_x, PM₁₀).

Figure 2: Total benefits of UCI over the lifetime

Table 5 presents the discounted economic, reliability and environmental benefits per year. On the other hand, Table 6 presents the summary of projected economic, reliability, and environmental benefits from the implementation of the ODP across Germany, Sweden, and Denmark over the period 2026–2035. The cost-benefit analysis indicates that environmental benefits will be crucial with CO₂ emission reduction of €642.53 million. Revenue generation from energy trading emerges as the highest contributor of *economic benefits* with €384.96 million. Reduction in billing costs (€241.87 million) and cost savings using demand response (€125.45 million) further highlight the effectiveness of smart energy management in lowering household and system-wide energy expenditures. Other economic benefits include reductions in transaction costs (€52.82

million) and cost savings from peak load reduction (€25.63 million), which reflect the efficiency gains from automated billing, smart metering, and dynamic pricing strategies.

Reliability benefits, particularly avoided energy curtailment (€357.42 million) and grid stability savings (€202.31 million), demonstrate the critical role of ODPs in enhancing the resilience of power systems by reducing energy wastage and improving system flexibility. These gains stem from better load balancing, optimized dispatching, and smart EV charging strategies, which prevent renewable energy curtailment and increase system efficiency. Air pollutant emission reductions with a 1% ODP augmented system (€93.88 million) illustrate the significance of the ODP integrating existing systems in reducing emissions from non-renewable sources and industrial activities contribute to air pollution. Figure 2 demonstrates the distribution of these benefits over different categories of benefits over the ten-year time horizon of the platforms. The results confirm that the implementation of ODPs leads to financial and operational efficiency with sustainable and resilient energy future.

Table 6: Summary of benefits over ten years for UCI

Category	Benefits	(€)
Economic benefits	Reduced billing costs	241,869,779
	Reduction in transaction costs	52,817,202
	Cost savings through demand-response	125,450,955
	Cost savings from peak load reduction	25,632,254
	Revenue generation from energy trading	384,955,951
Reliability benefits	Grid Stability savings	202,314,250
	Avoidance of energy curtailment	357,415,969
Environmental benefits	CO ₂ emission reduction	642,530,418
	SO _x , NO _x , PM10 reduction	26,470,623
Total benefits		2,059,457,401

Step 5: Quantify costs

Capital expenditure (CAPEX)

Costs are categorized into capital expenditure (CAPEX), recurring operational & maintenance costs (OPEX). Table 60 in the appendix A1 shows the CAPEX for the electricity customers centric ODP deployment in Germany, Sweden and Denmark. The total upfront cost is €39,450,000. Table 61 in the appendix A1 presents smart meters and different sensors discounted costs of €572,348,517 across the three countries over the platform's lifetime.

Recurring operational & maintenance (OPEX)

Table 64 in Appendix A1 presents the details of OPEX costs in each country per category. One of the OPEX required to implement the ODP in the three countries is labor costs. The total labor force required across all three countries is projected at 127 jobs, with Germany employing 59 workers, Sweden 39, and Denmark 29. The average salary per job category varies between €48,000 and €60,000, with AI models grid optimization and cybersecurity roles commanding the highest wages due to their specialization. The total labor cost for 2026 is estimated to be €6,731,000. The estimated discounted total labor costs for the deployment of ODP over the ten-year period is €56,778,217 million. Jobs expected for different positions are presented in Table 63 in Appendix A1.

Figure 3: Total OPEX (including labor costs) in the first year for UCI

Figure 3 presents the OPEX distribution for the first year (2026) of the electricity customers centric ODPs implementation across key cost categories. The largest expense categories include cloud computing and data processing (€7.8 million) and grid expansion and new EV/ET integrations (€7.7 million), reflecting the critical investments required for data infrastructure and integrating expanding RES and EVs. Other significant expenditures include network maintenance (€6.9 million), grid and sensor maintenance (€6.3 million), and TSO/DSO & energy market integration (€6.3 million), highlighting the importance of ensuring secure and efficient energy trading and grid reliability. Labor costs amount to €6.73 million, while additional costs for cybersecurity, customer support, virtual energy community (VEC) integration, and miscellaneous expenses further contribute to the total OPEX. These recurring expenses are essential for maintaining the system functionality of the ODP. The total discounted OPEX cost for the 10 years is projected to be €516,503,789.

Step 6: Compare costs and benefits

Financial metrics such as NPV (net present value) and BCR (benefit-cost ratio) are calculated to evaluate cost-benefit comparisons. Costs and benefits are compared based on these metrics to show the feasibility of the UCs over the ODP horizon and beyond. This is a critical step where investment decisions are made regarding the electricity customers centric ODPs.

Table 7: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCI

Category	Value (€)
Total benefits	2,059,457,401
CAPEX	611,798,517
OPEX	516,503,789
Net benefit (NPV)	931,155,095
BCR	1.83

Table 7 provides a comparative analysis of the costs and benefits associated with the deployment of electricity customers centric ODP over a ten-year period. The total benefits amount to €2.06 billion, while the CAPEX and OPEX sum up to €611.79 million and €516.5 million, respectively. This results in a net benefit of €931.15 million, demonstrating the ODP implementation's economic viability and long-term financial gains. The BCR of 1.83 indicates that for every €1 invested, the system generates €1.83 in benefits, underscoring the cost-effectiveness and positive return on investment of integrating the electricity customers centric ODPs.

Figure 4 provides a comparison of the costs and benefits associated with the ODPs over their ten-year lifetime. The figure clearly differentiates costs (CAPEX and OPEX) in red and benefits (economic, reliability, and environmental) in blue and the net benefit in green. The net benefit of €931 million highlights the overall financial and societal gains, proving the economic viability of the electric customers centric ODPs.

Figure 4: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCI

Step 7: Sensitivity analysis and risk assessment

The cost-benefit analysis has been prepared based on the best knowledge available. However, uncertainty always attaches to estimates of returns on major energy and transportation projects. We therefore conduct some sensitivity analyses highlighting the sensitivity of the result to various assumptions and calculations. The goal of the sensitivity analysis is to investigate how the results of cost-benefit analysis may change with some critical parameters, because different economic, and geographic factors play an important role in determining the magnitude of benefits for different Member States/regions and the cost-benefit analysis is essentially based on forecasts and estimates of variables, which have many uncertainties surrounding.

Table 8: Results under different benefit and cost scenarios for UCI

Scenario	Benefit change	Cost change	New NPV (€)	New BCR
Base Case	0%	0%	931,155,095	1.83
Increased benefits (+10%)	10%	0%	1,137,100,835	2.01
Decreased benefits (-10%)	-10%	0%	725,209,355	1.64
Increased costs (+10%)	0%	10%	818,324,864	1.66
Decreased costs (-10%)	0%	-10%	1,043,985,325	2.03

Table 8 outlines multiple scenarios demonstrating how changes in benefits and costs influence the BCR and NPV. Under the Base Case, with no adjustments to costs or

benefits, the analysis results in a BCR of 1.83 and an NPV of €931.15 million, serving as a benchmark for comparison. If benefits increase by 10%, the BCR improves to 2.01, and the NPV reaches €1.1 billion, illustrating that wider adoption and higher utilization significantly enhances economic feasibility. On the other hand, if benefits decrease by 10%, the BCR drops to 1.64, while the NPV declines to €725.2 million, highlighting the financial decrease associated with lower adoption rates. If the total cost increases by 10%, the NPV and BCR reduce to €818.3 million and 1.66, respectively. Meanwhile, if the total cost decreases by 10%, the NPV and BCR increase to €1.04 billion and 2.03, respectively.

Figure 5: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCI using various discount rates

Figure 5 illustrates the sensitivity analysis of discount rates using NPV and BCR. The left plot shows how NPV decreases with higher discount rates, indicating that future benefits are valued less when a higher discount rate is applied. The right plot demonstrates the positive correlation between BCR and discount rates, showing that a higher discount rate decreases the ODP's cost-effectiveness. Both plots emphasize that choosing an appropriate discount rate is crucial for accurately assessing the financial feasibility of ODP implementation.

We run a Monte Carlo simulation to assess financial uncertainty in the cost-benefit analysis. Monte Carlo simulations allow us to generate thousands of possible financial outcomes based on probability distributions for key input variables, providing a probabilistic view of financial risks and helping us evaluate the likelihood of different financial outcomes. For this analysis, we run 10,000 iterations of potential financial results for NPV and BCR, considering key uncertain variables⁴ such as EV adoption growth, electricity price fluctuations, CAPEX variations, and OPEX uncertainties. Each simulation run generates a unique combination of these variables, computing NPV and BCR for each

⁴ EV adoption growth was modeled with a normal distribution (mean = 1.05, std dev. = 0.02), electricity price fluctuations followed a triangular distribution (ranging from 0.98 to 1.08, with a mode at 1.04), CAPEX uncertainty was represented by a uniform distribution (±15%), and OPEX uncertainty was modeled with a normal distribution (mean = 1.04, std dev. = 0.01).

iteration.

Figure 6: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCI using Monte Carlos simulation

The results presented in Figure 6 are probability distributions, which provide insights into the range and likelihood of different financial outcomes. The left plot in Figure 6 shows the NPV distribution, centered around €1 billion, with 95% of the time the NPV values fall above €900 million, indicating a high probability of positive financial returns. The right plot displays the BCR distribution, which is approximately normal and centered around 1.9, suggesting that in most cases, the benefits outweigh the costs. The results confirm that under a wide range of scenarios, the ODP remains financially viable.

3.3. Cost benefit analysis: AI-driven ODP for integration of EVs, ETs, RES, and Grid

Step 1. Define the Use Case

Please refer to Section 2.2.

Step 2: Map technologies to functions

Each technology is analyzed for its contributions to the operational functions of the AI-driven ODP for EVs, ETs, RES, and grid integration. Below is a detailed mapping of the technologies and their functions.

Table 9: Mapping of technologies onto functions for UCII

		Functions			
		A. Data and information collection	B. Improve interoperability and system integration	C. Smart load forecasting and grid balancing	D. Decision support system
Technologies (Assets)	IoT Sensors (EV, ET, RES, weather and environmental sensors)	•	•	•	•
	Edge gateway	•	•		

	Edge network 5G		•		
	Message queues		•		
	Communication protocols	•		•	•
	Microservice			•	•
	Data Integration	•		•	
	Data lake & databases	•	•	•	•
	AI models and ML algorithms	•		•	•
	APIs & external systems	•		•	•
	User interface		•		•

The technologies in Table 9 are mapped to their respective functions to ensure seamless integration, optimization, and interoperability of the AI-driven ODP for EVs, ETs, RES, and grid systems. Each component supports the broader system through a distinct but interconnected role. For example, IoT sensors, such as EV and RES sensors, collect real-time data on state-of-charge, driving behavior, battery health, and renewable energy output, enabling accurate energy demand forecasting and grid integration. Adaptive environmental and weather sensors further enhance system intelligence by predicting energy production and load patterns based on real-time conditions. AI models (e.g., Azure ML, TensorFlow, OR-Tools) predict grid loads, optimize demand response, and manage routes for EVs and ETs. Weather forecasting further refines renewable generation predictions. Functionality mapping ensures each technology plays a defined role while complementing others, forming a robust, intelligent system for energy and mobility optimization.

Step 3: Map functions to benefits

We now map the functions of the ODP to the expected benefits and the results are summarized in Table 10.

Table 10: Mapping functionalities to benefits for UCII

Benefits		Functions			
Economic benefits		A. Data and information	B. Improved interoperability and system integration	C. Smart load forecasting and grid balancing	D. Decision support system

		Collection			
	Reduction in operational downtime cost	•			•
	Revenue from optimized energy trading	•		•	•
	Cost saving through demand response			•	•
	Cost savings from peak load reduction	•	•	•	•
	Revenue from time saving for drivers			•	•
	Avoided energy curtailment		•	•	•
Reliability benefits	Grid stability savings		•	•	
	Fleet energy savings		•	•	
Environmental benefits	Reduced carbon emissions				•
	Reduced Sox, Nox and PM10	•			•

As can be seen from Table 10, the benefits are categorized as economic efficiency, system reliability and environmental sustainability, ensuring an optimized integration of EVs, ETs, RES, and the grid.

Economic benefits arise from cost reductions, efficiency improvements, and revenue generation facilitated by real-time data collection, AI-based forecasting, and demand response mechanisms. The reduction in operational downtime costs is achieved through predictive analytics and automated fault detection, which reduce the duration and frequency of outages. Revenue from optimized energy trading is generated by leveraging AI-driven ODP forecasting models to enhance market participation and maximize profits from trading electricity. Cost savings through demand response results from the optimization of electricity consumption patterns. AI-driven ODP demand response programs shift consumption to off-peak hours, leading to lower energy costs. Cost

savings from peak load reduction are realized by balancing grid loads that dynamically reduces reliance on expensive backup power plants. Revenue from time savings for drivers is achieved through optimized charging schedules and route planning, minimizing delays and increasing fleet productivity. Finally, avoided energy curtailment is a major benefit stemming from AI-driven ODP forecasting and real-time grid management, ensuring that excess renewable energy is utilized efficiently instead of being wasted.

Reliability benefits improve grid stability, fleet efficiency, and optimized EV and ET charging costs, ensuring a resilient and cost-effective energy system. Grid stability savings are achieved through enhanced forecasting and real-time monitoring, preventing fluctuations and improving grid balance. Fleet energy savings are facilitated by AI-driven ODP routing and smart charging optimization, which reduce energy wastage in EV and ET operations. EV and ET charging cost savings result from smart charging algorithms that shift charging to periods of lower electricity demand, reducing costs for operators and consumers.

Environmental benefits are driven by optimized energy resource utilization, reduced emissions, and lower fossil fuel dependency. Reduced carbon emissions are achieved by integrating more renewables into the grid and reducing reliance on fossil fuels. Reduced SO_x, NO_x, and PM₁₀ emissions are linked to the displacement of fossil fuel-based energy generation by cleaner renewables due to ODPs implementation.

Step 4: Monetize benefits

Calculating the economic, reliability, and environmental benefits of AI-driven ODP for the integration of EVs, ETs, RES, and the grid is somewhat tricky, as the benefits are intertwined with those of existing system benefits. On the other hand, since there is no actual/accurate data regarding the ODP technologies, we need to assume a small percentage (for robustness) improvement of the ODP from the existing systems so that we can quantify the benefits of the AI-driven ODP for integrating EV, ET, RES and the grid. All the assumptions, and the data sources used to calculate each benefit are presented in Tables 66, 67, and 68 in the Appendix A2.

Table 11: Metrics and formulas for calculations of benefits for UCII

Benefits	Metrics and formula of calculations
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<p>Reduction in operational downtime cost</p>	<p>$BLDC \times (1 + GR)^{(year - start\ year)} \times (1 + EV/ET\ Adoption\ Rate)^{(year - start\ year)} \times efficiency\ improvement\ factor.^5$</p> <p>Baseline downtime costs (BLDT): We assume €100 million annually for Austria and €42 million for Hungary and Slovenia, a 10% reduction with ODP equates to €14.2 million in annual downtime cost in all countries⁶.</p> <p>We assume 12%/year grid capacity growth rate (GR), 12.97% EV/ET adoption rate and 10% efficiency improvement factor due to ODP.</p>
<p>Revenue from optimized energy trading</p>	<p>$MFI \times [(RES \times RES\ factor) + (EV \times EVCP \times EVCE \times CFF) + (ET \times ETCP \times ETCE \times CFF)] \times V,$</p> <p>where MFI is market price forecasting accuracy improvement due to ODP, RES is total RES capacity [MW], EV is total EV fleet, ET is total ET fleet, V is market price volatility (€ per MWh), CFF is charging flexibility factor, EVCP/ETCP is EV/ET charging power (kW), and EVCE/ETCE is EV/ET charging efficiency.</p> <p>We consider the minimum RES capacity factor, which is 1200MWh per/MW/year.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market price volatility (25€ per MWh) • 2.3KW for EV and ET standard charging power in Europe (source) and • 0.8 charging efficiency (source).
<p>Cost savings through demand-response</p>	<p>$(1 + Market\ participation\ increase\ due\ to\ ODP(\%)) \times [RES \times Curtailable\ RES\ \% + (EV \times EVCP \times EV\ demand\ flexibility\ factor \times 1/1000) + (ET \times ETCP \times ET\ demand\ flexibility\ factor \times 1/1000)] \times demand\ response\ payment\ per\ MW\ (\text{€})$</p>

⁵ The grid size factor can be approximated by examining the installed electricity generation capacities of each country. Austria: The high-voltage electricity grid comprises approximately 18,200 km of lines, with 3,051 km at 380 kV and 3,714 km at 220 kV. Hungary: The total installed electricity generation capacity is about 7,697 MW. Studies have indicated that such AI-driven interventions can reduce operational downtime costs by an additional 10-15% compared to traditional systems. In addition, $8,760 \times 0.01 \times 1200$ converts the RES capacity power to MWh. Then we consider 1% of it as an impact due to ODP.

Imbalance Reduction with ODP \times (Total RES Capacity (MW) + EV/ET Charging Capacity (MW)) \times Market Penalty Rate (€ per MWh)

⁶ Practically, downtime cost is very high. The average cost of downtime is around €5300/minute according to [ATLASSIAN](#). The average Western European country average outage duration is 25 minutes per year. Austria has 75,000,000MWh annual electricity consumption. Based on SAIDI data the estimated annual electricity not supplied in Austria is 250,000MWh. Using the conversion rate, $250,000MWh \times \text{€}8000 = \text{€}2,000,0000$ for Austria. Then assume only 5% of this downtime cost could be saved using the integration of ODP, gives the €100 million annually for downtime cost for our calculation. The same can be calculated for Hungary.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RES curtailment is usually 5-15% of total RES capacity. EV demand flexibility factor represents %age shift of EVs (20-50%). Demand response payment typically ranges from €5,000 to €50,000 per MW per year, depending on the market. We take the lowers of all these ranges.
Cost savings from peak load reduction	$(1 + \text{Peak load reduction Due to ODP (10\%)}) \times$ $[(\text{Total peak Load (M} - (\text{RES} \times \text{RES peak utilization factor})) - ((\text{EV} \times \text{EVCP} \times \text{EV demand Flexibility Factor}) + (\text{ET} \times \text{ETCP} \times \text{ET demand flexibility factor}))) \times \text{Peak load hours per year} \times \text{Price (€/MWh)}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Though the average peak load hour could reach up to 1500 hours, we only consider 10% of it that is 150 peak load hours per year. Electricity price during peak hours is assumed to be €10/MWh.
Avoided energy curtailment	$\text{Curtailment reduction due to ODP (1\%)} \times \text{RES} \times \text{P (€/MWh)} \times \text{Annual operating hours} \times \text{RES curtailment factor}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RES curtailment factor= 5% (0.05). Average operation hour per year for RES is 1200.
Grid stability savings	$\text{ODP} - \text{enabled imbalance reduction(10\%)} \times ((\text{RES} + (\text{EV} \times \text{EVCP}) + (\text{ET} \times \text{ETCP})) \times [\text{fuel saving per year}]$
Fleet energy savings	$\text{ODP} - \text{enable distance reduction (0.1\%)} \times \text{Total fleet distance (km)} \times \text{Price (€/kWh)} \times \text{Average energy consumption per km (kWh/km)}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average annual distance per vehicle 20,000km/EV and 40,000km/ET. Electricity cost per kWh €0.20, EVs: 0.20 kWh/km, ETs: 2.0 kWh/km.
CO₂ emissions reduction	$[(\text{RES} \times \text{RES capacity factor}) + (\text{EV} \times \text{Annual distance per EV} \times \text{EV energy consumption per km} \times \text{Grid decarbonization factor}) + (\text{ET} \times \text{Annual distance per ET} \times \text{ET energy consumption per km} \times \text{Grid decarbonization factor})] \times \text{Emission factor (tCO}_2\text{/MWh)} \times \text{Emission price (€/tCO}_2\text{)}$
Reduction in SO_x, NO_x, PM10 emissions	<p>Air pollutant emission saving can be monetized as follows:</p> $\Delta AP = P_{AP} \times (\Delta AP_{\text{RES,ODP}} + \Delta AP_{\text{EV,ODP}} + \Delta AP_{\text{ET,ODP}} + \Delta AP_{\text{awareness,ODP}})$ <p>where:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P_{AP} = Air pollutant cost [€/tonne] (societal cost of pollutants are NOx, SOx, PM10) • $\Delta AP_{RES,ODP}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled RES integration [tonnes/year] • $\Delta AP_{EV,ODP}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled EV smart charging & routing [tonnes/year] • $\Delta AP_{ET,ODP}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled ET smart charging & routing [tonnes/year] • $\Delta AP_{awareness,ODP}$ = air pollutant saving from customer awareness [tonne] <p>Air pollutant emission savings from RES</p> $\Delta AP_{RES} = \text{tonne}_{AP/MWh} \times \Delta EE_{RES,year}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\text{tonne}_{AP/MWh}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled demand-side energy savings [tonnes/year] <p>Air pollutant emission saving from electric mobility</p> $\Delta AP_{EV,ODP} = \text{km}_{year} \times N_{EV,ODP} \times CS_{EV,ODP} (\text{tonne}_{AP/km,ff} - \text{tonne}_{AP/km,EV})$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • km_{year} = Annual distance driven per EV [km/year] • CS_{ODP} = Charging stations enabled by ODPs [count] • $N_{EV,ODP}$ = EVs using ODP-enabled smart charging & routing [count] • $\text{tonne}_{AP/km,EV}$ = Air pollutant emissions per km for EVs [tonnes AP/km] • $\text{tonne}_{AP/km,ff}$ = Air pollutant emissions per km for fossil fuel vehicles [tonnes AP/km] <p>The same formula is used for ET emission reduction</p> <p>Air pollutant reduction from demand-side energy savings (consumer awareness & efficiency)</p> $\Delta AP_{awareness,ODP} = EE_{TOT} \times \%EE_{ODP} \times \text{tonne}_{AP/MWh}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE_{TOT} = Total electricity consumption [MWh/year] • $\%EE_{ODP}$ = ODP-enabled energy efficiency improvement [%]
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Table 11 presents the detailed formulas and sources of the benefit calculations based of each category. Most of our formulas are consistent with reference [2].

Table 12: Economic, reliability and environmental benefits for UCII

Year	Economic benefits (€)						Reliability benefit (€)		Environmental benefits (€)	
	ROD	ROET	CSDR	PLR	AEC	FES	GSS	GSF	CO ₂	SO _x
2026	3,478,750	11,615,599	5,277,856	4,351,045	23,044,220	4,153,290	13,938,761	9,344,882	6,977,935	2,196,148
2027	4,000,562	12,228,577	5,910,187	4,884,026	24,246,431	4,682,598	14,674,293	10,536,176	7,346,836	2,457,498
2028	4,600,646	12,875,081	6,621,323	5,484,075	25,512,564	5,279,605	15,450,937	11,879,887	7,735,965	2,751,306
2029	5,290,743	13,556,993	7,421,267	6,159,740	26,846,075	5,952,996	16,268,932	13,395,579	8,146,496	3,081,868
2030	6,084,355	14,276,359	8,321,304	6,920,667	28,250,216	6,712,572	17,131,631	15,105,329	8,579,764	3,453,681
2031	6,997,008	15,035,351	9,334,164	7,777,737	29,730,822	7,569,398	18,042,422	17,034,057	9,036,826	3,872,058
2032	8,046,560	15,836,281	10,474,114	8,743,232	31,288,364	8,535,960	19,003,537	19,209,859	9,519,364	4,342,244
2033	9,235,444	16,681,066	11,757,651	9,831,012	32,929,921	9,626,354	20,017,927	21,664,493	10,028,791	4,873,004
2034	10,641,575	17,573,494	13,202,770	11,056,716	34,659,299	10,856,488	21,088,873	24,433,994	10,566,790	5,469,981
2035	12,237,812	18,516,048	14,830,202	12,437,944	36,480,997	12,244,323	22,219,300	27,558,559	11,134,828	6,114,493
Total	70,631,599	148,195,839	93,150,939	77,646,249	292,988,420	75,613,588	177,835,009	170,162,955	89,073,282	38,640,329

Note: ROD is reduction in operational downtime cost, ROET is revenue from optimized energy trading, CSDR is cost savings through demand-response, PLR is cost savings from peak load reduction, AEC avoid energy curtailment, FES is fleet energy savings, CO₂ is CO₂ emission reduction with ODP and SO_x is air pollutant reduction (SO_x, NO_x, PM10).

Grid stability form forecasting, FES is Fleet energy savings, CO₂ emission Reduction, SO_x Reduction.

Figure 7: Total benefits of UCII over the lifetime

Table 13: Summary of benefits over ten years for UCII

Category	Benefits	(€)
	Reduction in operational downtime cost	70,631,599

Economic benefits	Revenue from optimized energy trading	148,195,839
	Cost savings through demand-response	93,150,939
	Cost savings from peak load reduction	77,646,249
	Fleet energy savings	170,162,955
	Avoid energy curtailment	170,162,955
Reliability benefits	Grid Stability from forecasting	119,894,682
	Grid stability saving	106,812,233
Environmental benefits	CO ₂ Emission reduction	85,209,272
	Sox, NOx, PM10 Reduction	51,373,761
Total benefits		1,233,938,319

Table 12 shows the discounted benefits for each year. Then, Table 13 provides a summary of the projected benefits of the AI-driven ODPs for integrating EVs, ETs, RES, and the grid over a ten-year period. The analysis, applying a 4% discount rate, estimates a total benefit of €1.234 billion across three key categories: economic, reliability, and environmental benefits. Economic benefits, totaling over €852.77 million. Environmental benefits, amounting to €127.7 million. Figure 7 illustrates how these benefits position the ODP as a high-impact investment in cost efficiency, grid stability, and environmental sustainability. The largest savings come from enhanced battery longevity, optimized peak load management, and improved renewable energy utilization.

Step 5: Quantify costs

Capital expenditure (CAPEX)

The total CAPEX throughout the ODPs lifetime is €561,251,541, including discounted sensor costs for the incoming EVs, ETs and RESs in every year, starting from 2027. Tables 69 and 70 in the Appendix A2 present the details of the CAPEX, including yearly investments for technological increments.

Recurring operational & maintenance costs (OPEX)

These costs recur annually due to system maintenance, updates, data processing, and the integration of new EVs, ETs, RES, and grid expansions.

Table 72 in Appendix A2 present the labor costs related to ODP integration of EVs, ETs, RES, and the grid in Austria, Hungary, and Slovenia and the annual recurring OPEX for ODP deployment, respectively.

Figure 8 represents the OPEX distribution across various cost (€ million) categories for the first year (2026). The highest cost categories are cloud computing & data processing and cybersecurity & threat monitoring, at €4.8 million, and €4.4 million, respectively. Other expenses include grid & sensor maintenance (€3.4M), TSO/DSO & energy market integration (€3.5M), and total labor costs (€3.9M). The total discounted OPEX cost for the 10 years is €315,891,002.

Figure 8: Total OPEX (including labor costs) in the first year for UCII

Step 6: Compare costs and benefits

Table 14 provides a comparative analysis of the costs and benefits associated with the deployment of AI-driven ODP over a ten-year period. The total benefits amount to €1.23 billion, while the CAPEX and OPEX sum up to €561.2 million and €315.8 million, respectively. This results in a net benefit of €356.76 million, demonstrating the ODP implementation's economic viability and long-term financial gains. The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of 1.40 indicates that for every €1 invested, the system generates €1.41 in benefits, underscoring the cost-effectiveness and positive return on investment of AI-driven ODP for integrating EVs, ETs, RES, and the grid. Figure 9 also shows the comparison of cost and benefits for completeness.

Table 14: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCII

Category	Value (€)
Total benefits	1,233,938,319
CAPEX	561,251,541
OPEX	315,891,002

Net benefit	356,775,776
BCR	1.41

Figure 9: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCII

The cost benefit analysis results confirms that the ODP delivers a strong return on investment, with benefits significantly outweighing costs, making it a feasible solution for sustainable energy and mobility integration.

Step 7: Sensitivity analysis and risk assessment

We also perform sensitivity analyses highlighting the sensitivity of the result to various assumptions and calculations. Table 15 outlines scenarios demonstrating how changes in benefits and costs influence the BCR and NPV. Under the Base Case, with no adjustments to costs or benefits, the analysis results in a BCR of 1.41 and an NPV of €356.7 million, serving as a benchmark for comparison. If benefits increase by 10%, the BCR improves to 1.55, and the NPV reaches €480.2 million, illustrating that wider adoption and higher utilization significantly enhance economic feasibility. On the other hand, if benefits decrease by 10%, the BCR drops to 1.23, slightly above break even, while the NPV declines to €233.4 million, highlighting the positive financial gains even with lower adoption rates and lower BCR. If the total cost increases by 10%, the NPV and BCR

reduce to €269.1 million and 1.28, respectively. Meanwhile, if the total cost decreases by 10%, the NPV and BCR increase to €444.5 million and 1.56, respectively.

Table 15: Results under different benefit and cost scenarios for UCII

Scenario	Benefit change	Cost change	New NPV (€)	New BCR
Base Case	0%	0%	356,795,776	1.41
Increased benefits (+10%)	10%	0%	480,189,608	1.55
Decreased benefits (-10%)	-10%	0%	233,401,944	1.27
Increased costs (+10%)	0%	10%	269,081,522	1.28
Decreased costs (-10%)	0%	-10%	444,510,030	1.56

Figure 10: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCII using various discount rates

Figure 10 shows the results of NPV and BCR under various discount rates and it can be seen that higher discount rates lead to a lower NPV and lower BCR.

Figure 11: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCI using Monte Carlo simulation

We also conduct a Monte Carlo simulation to assess financial uncertainty in the cost-benefit analysis. For this analysis, we run 10,000 iterations of NPV and BCR, considering key uncertain variables⁷ such as EV adoption growth, electricity price fluctuations, CAPEX variations, and OPEX uncertainties. Each simulation draws from defined probability distributions for these inputs, producing a unique scenario. The results are visualized as probability distributions, providing a robust understanding of the range and likelihood of different outcomes.

The left plot in Figure 11 shows the NPV distribution, which is centered around €500 million, with most values falling between €400 million and €550 million. The right plot shows the BCR distribution, which is approximately normally distributed and centered around 1.6. These results reinforce the financial robustness of the ODP investment.

3.4. Cost benefit analysis: Digitalization of data centers

Step 1. Define the Use Case

Please refer to Section 2.3.

Step 2. Map technologies to functions

Table 16 illustrates how key technologies are aligned with the main functionalities within the DCs ODP. Smart meters and IoT sensors enable data and energy management by collecting real-time data on temperature, power usage, and compute loads. Interoperability and system integration are facilitated through API management tools, data integration middleware, and cloud infrastructure, ensuring seamless interaction between energy and computing systems.

Table 16: Mapping of technologies onto functions for UCIII

		Functions				
Technologies (Assets)		A. Data and energy management	B. Interoperability & system integration	C. Predictive management	D. Dynamic load & grid flexibility	E. Decision support and optimization
	Smart meters	•	•	•	•	•
	IoT sensors	•	•	•	•	•
	AI algorithms & ML models	•	•	•	•	•

⁷ EV adoption growth was modeled with a normal distribution (mean = 1.05, std dev = 0.02), electricity price fluctuations followed a triangular distribution (ranging from 0.98 to 1.08, with a mode at 1.03), CAPEX uncertainty was represented by a uniform distribution (±10%), and OPEX uncertainty was modeled with a normal distribution (mean = 1.04, std dev = 0.01).

Digital Twin	•		•	•	•
Communication protocol	•	•	•	•	•
Edge computing		•			•
Flexibility forecasting tools		•			•
Data integration	•	•	•	•	•
Data lakes & analytics	•	•	•	•	•
5G connectivity		•			
Visualization tools	•	•			•
Workload orchestration	•			•	•

For predictive energy management, technologies such as AI algorithms, machine learning models, and digital twins play a key role in forecasting renewable energy production, grid demand, and compute load shifts. Dynamic load and grid flexibility are optimized through workload orchestration tools, battery storage systems, and RES integration, allowing data centers to balance power usage and supply efficiently. Decision support and optimization functionality relies on machine learning models, visualization tools like Power BI and Grafana, and data lakes, ensuring that data center operators have actionable insights for energy optimization, operational adjustments, and sustainability compliance. This structured mapping ensures that technologies are effectively aligned with key data center operations, supporting real-time monitoring, cross-border integration, intelligent forecasting, grid balancing, and decision support mechanisms.

Step 3. Map functions to benefits

The DCs ODP provides multiple advantages by integrating cutting-edge technologies with key functionalities. Smart meters, IoT sensors, AI algorithms, digital twins, communication protocols, and workload orchestration tools enable real-time energy management, predictive analytics, and grid flexibility, leading to cost efficiency, operational resilience, and sustainability improvements.

Table 17: Mapping functionalities to benefits for UCIII

Benefits		Functions				
Economic benefits		A. Data and energy	B. Interoperability & system integration	C. Predictive management	D. Dynamic load & grid flexibility	E. Decision support and optimization

		manage ment				
	Reduction in operational expense	•		•	•	•
	Reduction in administrative costs	•	•		•	•
	Financial savings from demand-side flexibility			•	•	
	Cost savings from peak load reduction	•	•	•	•	•
	Revenue generation from grid services			•	•	•
Operational resilience	Improved grid reliability		•	•	•	
	Prevention of energy curtailment	•		•	•	
Environmental benefits	Reduced CO2 emissions				•	•
	Reduced SOx, NOx and PM10	•			•	•

The technologies and functionalities outlined in Table 17 contribute significantly to economic efficiency, operational resilience and environmental sustainability.

Economic benefits in DCs ODP are driven by real-time energy monitoring, AI-powered predictive management, and grid flexibility services. Operational expense reduction is achieved by optimizing electricity consumption, shifting compute loads dynamically, and leveraging data-driven insights. Administrative cost reductions arise from automated billing, seamless energy transactions, and workload management.

Financial savings from demand-side flexibility are realized through predictive energy balancing and AI-driven workload orchestration, allowing cost-effective load adjustments in response to real-time energy market conditions. Peak load reduction savings occur when data centers utilize AI-based forecasting and smart load management, reducing the need for emergency power generation. Additionally, participation in grid services enables

new revenue streams through demand-side response programs and virtual power plant integration. For operational resilience, enhanced interoperability, predictive analytics, and dynamic load balancing strengthen grid reliability by preventing supply-demand imbalances and ensuring continuous energy availability. AI-driven forecasting and real-time integration with grid operators prevent energy curtailment, ensuring renewable energy is efficiently utilized rather than wasted.

From an *environmental sustainability* perspective, the DCs ODP facilitates lower carbon footprints and air pollutant emission reductions by optimizing renewable energy usage and minimizing reliance on fossil fuel-based power sources. AI-driven workload scheduling helps prioritize green energy consumption, leading to measurable reductions in CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, air pollutant reductions (SO_x, NO_x, PM10) are achieved by improving energy efficiency and reducing unnecessary peak energy generation.

Step 4: Monetize benefits

Table 18 provides the key metrics and formulas to calculate the benefits associated with the implementation of the DCs ODP. Each benefit is associated with specific performance drivers and country-specific variables, ensuring that the calculations are adaptable and robust for cross-country comparisons. The formulas provide a transparent and replicable framework for evaluating the value and impact of ODP deployment in the DC sector. To effectively evaluate the benefits of implementing by DCs ODP in Germany, Sweden, and Denmark from 2026 to 2035, various assumptions are considered. Assumptions and data sources are presented in Appended A3.

Table 18: Metrics and formulas for calculations of benefits for UCIII

Benefits	Metrics and formula of calculations
Reduction in operational expenses	$\Delta B = \%EE_{ODP} \times EE_{TOT} \times t_e$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\%EE_{ODP}$ = Net yearly energy reduction per DC due to ODP • EE_{TOT} = Total yearly energy consumption of DC (MWh) • t_e = Average electricity tariff (€/MWh) <p>In this analysis, an average reduction of about 3% has been considered for calculation⁸.</p>
Reduction in transaction costs	<p>Transaction cost savings from automated billing, smart meters, and virtual energy trading.</p> $\Delta TC = N_{DCs} \times \left(\frac{VEC_{new} + RES_{int} + AI_{int}}{N_{tot}} \right) \times (TC_{ODP} \times (1 - \%TC_{reduction}))$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{DCs} = Number of ODP-enabled data centers • TC_{ODP} = Cost per transaction with ODP integration (€/transaction)⁹

⁸ Cost-benefit analysis of Smart Grid projects: Isernia (<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC111852>) used the 3% reduction to calculate the observed reduction due to smart info kit, which we predict the operational digital platform expected to achieve.

⁹ €100 is assumed for cost per transaction with ODP integration (€/transaction) for each DC.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VEC_{new} = new virtual energy communities created • RES_{int} = DCs with integrated renewable energy sources • N_{TOT} = Total yearly energy consumption of DCs (MWh) • $\%TC_{reduction}$ = Percentage reduction in transaction costs
Financial savings from demand-side flexibility	$\Delta C_{DSF} = N_{DC} \times \left(\frac{HPC_{shift} + AI_{shift} + RES_{self} + VEC_{engaged}}{N_{TOT}} \right) \times \left((P_{peak} - P_{off}) \times \Delta E_t \right)_{ODP(10\%)}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HPC_{shift}, AI_{shift} = Proportion of HPC and AI workloads shifted to off-peak hours¹⁰ • RES_{self} = share of RES self-consumed • $VEC_{engaged}$ = Share of data centers actively participating in energy trading • P_{peak}, P_{off} = electricity prices during peak and off-peak hours (€/kWh) • ΔE_t = total shifted energy demand (MWh) $\Delta E_t = N_{TOT} \times (HPC_{shift} + AI_{shif} + RES_{self} + VEC_{engaged})$
Cost savings from peak load reduction	$\Delta C_{PLR} = N_{DC} \times C_{MW} \times \left(\frac{HPC_{smart} + AI_{optimized} + RES_{storage} + VEC_{flex}}{EHPC_{tot} + AI_{tot} + RES_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times \Delta P$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VEC_{flex} = Data centers using dynamic pricing and flexibility services in virtual energy trading • C_{MW} = cost/MW of peak demand avoided (€/MW) • ΔP = reduced peak demand (MW)
Revenue from grid flexibility services	$\Delta R_{GF} = N_{DC} \times \left(\frac{VEC_{engaged} + RES_{smart} + HPC_{bid} + AI_{bid}}{RES_{tot} + HPC_{tot} + AI_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times P_{ODP(\%)} \times \Delta Q_t$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $VEC_{engaged}$ = data centers actively participating in virtual energy trading • RES_{market} = proportion of renewable energy sold into virtual markets • HPC_{bid}, AI_{bid} = Share of workloads participating in demand response bidding • $P_{ODP(\%)}$ = %age of energy prices with ODP – enabled market integration (€/MWh) • ΔQ_t = additional energy traded due to ODP (MWh)
Grid reliability improvements	$\Delta C_{GR} = N_{DC} \times N_o \times C_o \times \left(\frac{RES_{balanced} + HPC_{grid} + AI_{grid} + VEC_{stability}}{RES_{tot} + HPC_{tot} + AI_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times (1 - \%LR)$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $VEC_{stability}$ = data centers providing grid – balancing services • N_o = Number of grid outages prevented

¹⁰ The number of HPC systems or workloads per DC depends on the type and purpose of the data center. HPC used for scientific simulations (climate, pharma, genomics), AI/ML model training, financial risk modeling, rendering and design. It typically requires specialized clusters or nodes, advanced cooling systems, and high energy and compute density (<https://www.iea.org/energy-system/buildings/data-centres-and-data-transmission-networks>). 15-20% of DCs are with HPC in Germany, 20-25% in Sweden and 10-15% in Denmark. Average HPC cluster per HPC-DC are 3-5, 4-6 and 2-4 in Germany, Sweden and Denmark, respectively. Based on this, we can calculate the average HPC clusters in each country.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C_o = cost of outages prevented (€/event) • %LR = ODP-enabled load reduction in peak load stress time (15%)
<p>Avoided energy curtailment</p>	$\Delta E_{EC} = N_{DC} \times \left(\frac{RES_{storage} + VEC_{active}}{RES_{tot} + VEC_{tot}} \right) \times \Delta E_{curt} \times P_E \times (1 - \%CR)$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $RES_{storage}$ = proportion of RES stored & used instead of curtailed • VEC_{active} = proportion of households actively trading excess RES • ΔE_{curt} = reduction in curtailed energy (MWh) • P_E = value of curtailed energy (€ 20 /MWh) • %CR = curtailment reduction cost % (5% improvement in our calculation)
<p>Reduced CO₂ emissions</p>	$\Delta CO_2 = pCO_2 \times (\Delta EE_{RES,ODP} + \Delta EE_{HPC,ODP} + \Delta EE_{AI,ODP} + \Delta EE_{awareness,ODP} + VEC_{CO_2,ODP})$ <p>where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pCO_2 =carbon price [€ /tonne CO₂] • $\Delta EE_{RES,ODP}$ =CO₂ reduction from ODP-enabled RES [tonne CO₂/year] • $\Delta EE_{HPC,ODP}, \Delta EE_{AI,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from workload optimization and AI-driven efficiency [tonne CO₂/year] • $\Delta EE_{awareness,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from demand-side energy savings due to ODP-enabled optimizations [tonnes CO₂/year] • $VEC_{CO_2,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from ODP-enabled VEC participation [tonnes CO₂/year] • CO₂ emission saving from DCs $\Delta EE_{DCs,ODP} = DC_{int,ODP} \times h_{eq} \times ERS_{factor}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $DC_{int,ODP}$ = ODP-enabled additional DCs [MW] • h_{eq} = Equivalent full-load hours of RES production [hours/year] • ERS_{factor} = CO₂ emissions displaced per MWh of DC [tonnes CO₂/MWh] • CO₂ emission saving from workload optimization (HPC & AI) $\Delta EE_{HPC,ODP} = N_{HPC,ODP} (ERS_{factor,ff} - ERS_{factor,HPC})$ $\Delta EE_{AI,ODP} = N_{AI,ODP} (ERS_{factor,ff} - ERS_{factor,AI})$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{HPC,ODP}$ =HPC workload instances using ODP-enabled optimization [count] • $N_{AI,ODP}, N_{HPC,ODP}$ = workload instances using ODP-enabled optimization [count] • $ERS_{factor,ff}$ = CO₂ emissions per equivalent workload unit for traditional fossil-fuel-based compute operations [tonnes CO₂/unit] • $ERS_{factor,HPC}, ERS_{factor,AI}$ = CO₂ emissions per HPC and AI workloads using ODP-enabled efficiency measures [tonnes CO₂/unit] • CO₂ emission saving from customer awareness $\Delta EE_{awareness,ODP} = EE_{TOT} \times \%EE_{ODP} \times ERS_{factor}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE_{TOT} = Total electricity consumption [MWh/year] • %EE_{ODP} =ODP-enabled energy efficiency improvement [%]

Reduced SOx, NOx and PM10	Air pollutant emission saving can be monetized as: $\Delta AP = P_{AP} \times (\Delta AP_{DCs,ODP} + \Delta AP_{HPC,ODP} + \Delta AP_{AI,ODP} + \Delta AP_{awareness,ODP})$ where:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P_{AP} = Air pollutant cost [€/tonne] (NOx, SOx, PM10) • $\Delta AP_{RES,ODP}$ = Air pollutant reduction from ODP-enabled DCs integration [tonnes/year] • $\Delta AP_{HPC,ODP}, \Delta AP_{AI,ODP}$ = Air pollutant savings from consumer awareness and demand-side reductions [tonnes/year] • $\Delta AP_{awareness,ODP}$ = air pollutant saving from customer awareness [tonne]
	Air pollutant emission savings from DCs $\Delta AP_{DCs} = \text{tonne}_{AP/MWh} \times \Delta EE_{DCs,year}$
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\text{tonne}_{AP/MWh}$ = Air pollutant emissions reduction per DC [tonnes AP/MWh]
	Air pollutant emission saving from HPC & AI workload optimization $\Delta AP_{HPC,ODP} = N_{HPC,ODP}(\text{tonne}_{AP/ff} - \text{tonne}_{AP/HPC})$ $\Delta AP_{AI,ODP} = N_{AI,ODP}(\text{tonne}_{AP/ff} - \text{tonne}_{AP/AI})$
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{HPC,ODP}, N_{AI,ODP}$ = Number of ODP-enabled HPC and AI workloads optimizations • $\text{tonne}_{AP/HPC}, \text{tonne}_{AP/AI}$ = ODP-enabled air pollutant emissions reduction per workload optimization [tonnes AP] • $\text{tonne}_{AP/ff}$ = Air pollutant emissions per traditional fossil-fuel compute workload [tonnes AP]
	Air pollutant reduction from demand-side energy savings (consumer awareness & efficiency) $\Delta AP_{awareness,ODP} = EE_{TOT} \times \%EE_{ODP} \times \text{tonne}_{AP/MWh}$
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EE_{TOT} = Total electricity energy consumption [MWh/year] • $\%EE_{ODP}$ = Percentage of ODP-enabled efficiency improvement

Table 19: Economic, reliability and environmental benefits for UCIII

Year	Economic benefits (€)					Reliability benefits (€)		Environmental benefits (€)	
	ROE	RTC	FSDR	CSPLR	RFS	GRI	AEC	CO ₂	SOx
2026	15,971,487	4,761,189	7,886,296	1,973,570	12,635,520	3,400,780	8,524,965	6,770,734	4,898,197
2027	16,131,202	4,808,801	8,125,259	1,993,306	13,385,857	3,434,788	8,610,215	6,977,662	4,995,612
2028	16,292,514	4,856,889	8,371,462	2,013,239	14,180,906	3,469,136	8,696,317	7,187,829	5,094,974
2029	16,455,439	4,905,458	8,625,126	2,033,371	15,023,338	3,503,827	8,783,280	7,401,292	5,196,323
2030	16,619,994	4,954,513	8,886,476	2,053,705	15,915,987	3,538,866	8,871,113	7,618,107	5,299,698
2031	16,786,194	5,004,058	9,155,745	2,074,242	16,861,854	3,574,254	8,959,824	7,838,333	5,405,141
2032	16,954,056	5,054,099	9,433,173	2,094,984	17,864,123	3,609,997	9,049,422	8,062,028	5,512,692

2033	17,123,596	5,104,640	9,719,007	2,115,934	18,926,166	3,646,097	9,139,916	8,289,252	5,622,393
2034	17,294,832	5,155,686	10,013,503	2,137,094	20,051,559	3,682,558	9,231,316	8,520,068	5,734,290
2035	17,467,781	5,207,434	10,316,922	2,158,465	21,244,901	3,719,383	9,323,629	8,754,537	5,848,424
Total	167,097,096	49,812,576	90,532,968	20,647,910	166,089,399	35,579,685	89,189,996	77,419,8	53,607,747

Note: ROE is reduction in operational expenses, RTC is reduction in transaction costs, FSDR is financial saving using demand response, CSPLR is cost saving from peak load reduction, RFS is revenue from grid flexibility services, GRI is grid reliability improvements, AEC is avoided energy curtailment, CO₂ is CO₂ emission reduction and SO_x is air pollutant emission reduction (SO_x, NO_x, PM₁₀).

Figure 12: Total benefits of UCIII over the lifetime

Table 19 presents a summary of the projected economic, reliability, and environmental benefits from the implementation of digitalization of data centers ODP across Germany, Sweden, and Denmark over the period 2026–2035. On the other hand, Table 20 presents the total benefit per category. Economic benefits are significant with a reduction in operational expenses of €167.1 million. Reduction in transaction costs (€49.81 million) and financial savings using demand response (€90.53 million) further highlight the effectiveness of smart energy management in lowering data centers energy usage. Reliability benefits include grid reliability improvement (€35.58 million) and avoided energy curtailment (€89.19 million), which reflect the efficiency gains from automated data center workloads using automated HPC, AI models, smart metering, and participating in virtual energy communities with dynamic pricing strategies.

Environmental benefits such as CO₂ emission reduction (77.42 million) and air pollutant emission reductions (€53.62 million) illustrate the DCs ODP in reducing emissions from non-renewable sources and industrial activities contribute to air pollution. Figure 12 demonstrates the distribution of benefits, where economic and reliability gains are substantial. The dominant advantage of ODP lies in its environmental impact. As can be seen, the implementation of ODP will not only lead to financial and operational efficiency

but also represents a transformative step toward a more sustainable and resilient energy future.

Table 20: Summary of benefits over ten years for UCIII

Category	Benefits	(€)
Economic benefits	Reduction in operational expenses	167,097,096
	Reduction in transaction costs	49,812,576
	Financial savings through demand-response	90,532,968
	Cost savings from peak load reduction	20,647,910
	Revenue from grid flexibility services	166,089,399
Reliability benefits	Grid reliability improvements	35,579,685
	Avoidance energy curtailment	89,189,996
Environmental benefits	CO ₂ emission reduction	77,419,841
	SO _x , NO _x , PM ₁₀ reduction	53,607,747
	Total benefits	749,977,218

Step 5: Quantify costs

Table 77 in Appendix A3 presents the miscellaneous deployment CAPEX for UCIII.

Figure 13 presents the total OPEX distribution for the first year (2026) of the digitalization of data centers ODPs implementation across key cost categories. The largest expense categories include total labor cost (€6.64 million). Other significant expenditures include cloud computing & data processing (€3.2 million), software maintenance & updates (€3.1 million), and network maintenance (€3.4 million). VEC integration and miscellaneous expenses further contribute to the total OPEX. These recurring expenses are essential for maintaining the system functionality of the DCs ODP.

The total OPEX over the project horizon is estimated at approximately €269,888,435 for the deployment of digitalized data center ODP in the three countries.

Figure 13: Total OPEX in the first year for UCIII

Step 6: Compare costs and benefits

Table 21 provides a comparative analysis of the costs and benefits associated with the deployment digitalizing data centers ODP over a ten-year period. The total benefits amount to €749.97 million, while the CAPEX and OPEX sum up to €40.7 million and €269.88 million, respectively. This results in a net benefit of €439.35 million, demonstrating the ODP implementation's economic viability and long-term financial gains. BCR of 2.41 indicates that for every €1 invested, the system generates €2.41 in benefits, underscoring the cost-effectiveness of digitalizing data centers ODP.

Table 21: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCIII

Category	Value (€)
Total benefits	749,977,218
CAPEX	40,730,592
OPEX	269,888,435
Net benefit (NPV)	439,358,191
BCR	2.41

Figure 14 provides a comparison of the costs and benefits associated with the DC ODP over their ten-year lifetime. The figure differentiates costs in red and benefits in blue and green. The initial and annual CAPEX of €41.0 million and the OPEX of €270 million represent the total investment required for system deployment, maintenance, and scaling. Economic benefits (€494 million) form the largest share, reliability benefits (€125

million) stem from grid reliability improvement and avoided energy curtailment, and environmental benefits (€131million) reflect reductions in CO₂ emissions and reduction in air pollutant such as SO_x, NO_x and PM10 emissions. The net benefit of €439 million highlights the overall financial and societal gains, proving the economic viability of the data centers ODP.

Figure 14: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCIII

Step 7: Sensitivity analysis and risk assessment

Table 22 demonstrates the impact of increased or decreased benefits by 10% and that of increased or decreased costs by 10%.

Table 22: Results under different benefit and cost scenarios for UCIII

Scenario	Benefit change	Cost change	New NPV (€)	New BCR
Base Case	0%	0%	439,358,191	2.41
Increased benefits (+10%)	10%	0%	514,355,913	2.66
Decreased benefits (-10%)	-10%	0%	364,360,469	2.17
Increased costs (+10%)	0%	10%	408,296,288	2.19
Decreased costs (-10%)	0%	-10%	470,420,094	2.68

With no adjustments to costs or benefits, the analysis results in a BCR of 2.41 and an NPV of €439.35 million, serving as a benchmark for comparison. If benefits increase by 10%,

the BCR improves to 2.66, and the NPV reaches €514.4 million, illustrating that wider adoption and higher utilization significantly enhance economic feasibility. On the other hand, if benefits decrease by 10%, the BCR drops to 2.17, while the NPV declines to €364.4 million, highlighting the financial decrease associated with lower ODP adoption rates. If the total cost increases by 10%, the NPV and BCR will reduce to 408.3 million and 2.19, respectively. Meanwhile, if the total cost decreases by 10%, the NPV and BCR increase to €470.4 million and 2.68, respectively.

This sensitivity analysis highlights that digitalization of data centers remains financially viable under most scenarios, but ensuring high adoption rates and cost efficiency is critical to maximizing economic and environmental benefits.

Figure 15: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCIII using various discount rates

Figure 15 illustrates the sensitivity analysis of discount rates using NPV and BCR. Both plots emphasize that choosing an appropriate discount rate is crucial for accurately assessing the financial feasibility of ODP implementation.

Figure 16: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCIII using Monte Carlos simulation

We conduct a Monte Carlo simulation to assess financial uncertainty in the cost-benefit analysis of data center ODP in Germany, Sweden, and Denmark.

For this analysis, we run 10,000 iterations of potential financial results for NPV and BCR, considering key uncertain variables¹¹ such as ODP adoption growth, electricity price fluctuations, CAPEX variations, and OPEX uncertainties. The results are presented as probability distributions, showing the expected range of outcomes and highlighting the 5th and 95th percentile values for both NPV and BCR. The left plot in Figure 16 shows the NPV distribution, centered around €480 million, with 95% of the time the NPV values fall above €450 million, indicating a high probability of positive financial returns. The right plot displays the BCR distribution, which is approximately normal and centered around 2.5, suggesting that in most cases, the benefits outweigh the costs. The results confirm that under a wide range of scenarios, data centers ODP remain financially feasible.

3.5. Cost benefit analysis: Digital permits for drone-based inspections

Step 1. Define the Use Case

Please refer to Section 2.4.

Step 2: Map technologies to functions

Each technology is analyzed for its contributions to the operational functions of the digital permits for drone-based inspections. Table 23 a detailed mapping of the technologies and their functions.

Table 23: Mapping of technologies onto functions for UCIV

		Functions			
		A. Data and information collection	B. Improve interoperability and system integration	C. Permit management and compliance validation	D. Decision support system
Technologies (assets)	Drones	•			•
	Environmental sensors	•			
	Edge network 5G	•	•	•	•
	Communication protocols		•		
	Message queues		•		

¹¹ ODP adoption growth was modeled with a normal distribution (mean = 1.04, std dev = 0.01), electricity price fluctuations followed a triangular distribution (ranging from 0.98 to 1.08, with a mode at 1.03), CAPEX uncertainty was represented by a uniform distribution (±10%), and OPEX uncertainty was modeled with a normal distribution (mean = 1.03, std dev = 0.015).

Data lake & databases	•	•	•	•
Blockchain technologies		•	•	
Flight management integration		•	•	
Digital Permit Management			•	•
GIS solutions			•	•
AI algorithms	•		•	•

As outlined in Table 23, different technologies are strategically mapped to their respective functions to ensure seamless integration, optimization, and interoperability within digital permits for drone-based infrastructure inspections ODP.

Step 3: Map functions to benefit

Table 24 details economic efficiency, reliability, safety, and environmental sustainability benefits and their corresponding functionalities in drone-based inspection processes for linear infrastructures.

Table 24: Mapping functionalities to benefits for UCIV

Benefits		Functions			
		A. Data and information collection	B. Improve interoperability and system integration	C. Permit management and compliance validation	D. Decision support
Economic benefits	Cost savings from faster permit processing		•	•	•
	Revenue from optimized maintenance operations	•		•	•
	Savings from reduced manual administrative efforts	•		•	•
	Improved cost-efficiency in infrastructure inspections		•	•	•
	Fuel savings		•		•
	Reliability and safety	Improved infrastructure safety and reliability		•	•
Reduced risk of human errors in permit validation				•	

	Savings in Insurance Costs from Reduced Worker Risks	•		•	•
Environmental benefits	CO2 reduced emissions	•			•

Economic benefits are achieved through substantial cost reductions and enhanced operational efficiencies enabled by digitalization, interoperability, automated permit management, and advanced decision support systems. Cost savings from faster permit processing arise from dramatically reducing the lengthy manual administrative procedures, significantly cutting down permit processing times from approximately one year to two months. Additionally, the platform generates revenue from optimized maintenance operations due to more frequent and precise inspection scheduling, enabling proactive maintenance and early detection of defects, which minimizes costly emergency repairs. The digital permits platform provides savings from reduced manual administrative efforts by automating permit validations and reducing manual labor efforts. Lastly, the platform improves cost-efficiency in infrastructure inspections, significantly reducing inspection-related costs by minimizing redundant, aborted, or improperly scheduled inspections. The digital permits platform substantially improves *infrastructure safety and reliability* by enabling regular, precise inspections, significantly reducing the likelihood of critical infrastructure failures and safety incidents. Significant savings are realized through a reduction in human errors during permit validation, directly attributable to blockchain-based automation. Moreover, the platform offers significant savings in worker risk insurance costs, as drone inspections drastically reduce the exposure and risk for human inspectors. *Environmental benefits* include reduced emissions and minimizing environmental impacts associated with traditional inspection methods. The digital platform supports reduction in environmental impacts due to minimized physical inspections, lowering fuel consumption and related CO₂ emissions from inspection vehicles.

Step 4: Monetize benefits

Table 25 presents the formulas, and the calculation of each benefit identified in Step 3.

Table 25: Metrics and formulas for calculations of benefits for UCIV

Benefits	Metrics and formula of calculations
Cost savings from faster permit processing	$\Delta FPP = N_{\text{Dos}} \times t_{\text{permit}} \times \%M \times \text{op}_{\text{cost}}$ Given parameters:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{Dos} = Total number of drone operators (Dos) • t_{permit} = current average permit time [months] • $\%M$ = expected time reduction [%] • op_{cost} = economic costs per operator per month [€/month] <p>We assume only 1% of the Dos are focused on infrastructure surveillance (energy, transport, etc.).</p>
<p>Revenue for optimized maintenance operations</p>	$\Delta\text{OPO} = N_{\text{infrastructures}} \times I_{\text{cost}} \times \%R_{\text{OPO}}$ <p>Given parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{infrastructures}}$ = Total number of infrastructures • I_{cost} = average annual cost per infrastructure [€] • $\%R_{\text{OPO}}$ = percentage cost reduction [%]
<p>Savings from reduced manual administrative efforts</p>	$\Delta\text{MAE} = N_{\text{permits}} \times t_{\text{admin}} \times c_{\text{labor}}$ <p>Given parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{permits} = Annual number of permits per country • t_{admin} = average administrative time saved per permit [h] • c_{labor} = labour cost/hour [€/h]
<p>Fuel savings</p>	$\Delta F_{\text{savings}} = \Delta F_{\text{savings}_{\text{physical}}} \times \Delta F_{\text{savings}_{\text{traffic}}}$ <p>Given parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\Delta F_{\text{savings}_{\text{physical}}}$ = fuel saved due to minimized physical inspections [€] • $\Delta F_{\text{savings}_{\text{traffic}}}$ = fuel saved due to decreased traffic disruptions [€] <p>Fuel cost savings due minimized physical inspection is calculated as:</p> $\Delta F_{\text{savings}_{\text{physical}}} = N_{\text{inspections}} \times \%D_R \times km_{\text{inspection}} \times F_{\text{consumption}/100km} \times p_{\text{Fuel}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{inspections}}$ = number of annual inspections • $\%D_R$ = percentage replaced by drones [%] • $km_{\text{inspection}}$ = kilometres per inspection [km] • $F_{\text{consumption}/100km}$ = fuel consumption [l/100 km] • p_{Fuel} = fuel prince [€/l] <p>Fuel savings from reduced traffic disruptions:</p> $\Delta F_{\text{savings}_{\text{traffic}}} = N_{\text{inspections}} \times \%I_R \times t_{\text{disruption}} \times N_v \times F_{\text{consumption}/h} \times p_{\text{Fuel}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{inspections}}$ = number of annual inspections • $\%I_R$ = percentage inspections replaced [%] • $t_{\text{disruption}}$ = disruption duration [h] • N_v = number of vehicles/hours • $F_{\text{consumption}/h}$ = fuel consumption [l/h] • p_{Fuel} = fuel prince [€/l]

<p>Improved infrastructure safety and reliability</p>	$\Delta S\&R = N_{\text{infrastructures}} \times \%f \times \%R_{\text{failure}} \times C_{\text{failure}}$ <p>Given parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{infrastructures}}$ = Total number of infrastructures • $\%f$ = probability of failure/year [%] • C_{failure} = average cost/failure [€] • $\%R_{\text{failure}}$ = reduction in failure probability [%]
<p>Reduced risk of human errors in permit validation</p>	$\Delta HE = N_{\text{infrastructures}} \times \%E_r \times \%R_{\text{error}} \times C_{\text{error}}$ <p>Given parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{permits} = Annual number of permits per country • $\%E_r$ = error rate (without ODP) [%] • C_{error} = cost per error [€] • $\%R_{\text{error}}$ = reduction in errors [%]
<p>Savings in insurance costs from reduced worker risks</p>	$\Delta WR = BL_{\text{insurance}} \times \%R_{\text{inspection}} \times \%R_{\text{insurance}}$ <p>Given parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $BL_{\text{insurance}}$ = baseline insurance cost [€] • $\%R_{\text{inspection}}$ = percentage inspections replaced [%] • $\%R_{\text{insurance}}$ = percentage insurance cost reduction [%] <p>Baseline annual insurance cost is calculated as:</p> $BL_{\text{insurance}} = N_{\text{inspections}} \times W_i \times C_{\text{insurance}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{inspections}}$ = number of inspections • W_i = workers per inspections • $C_{\text{insurance}}$ = insurance cost per worker [€]
<p>CO2 reduced emissions</p>	$\Delta CO_2 = \Delta CO_{2\text{physical}} \times \Delta CO_{2\text{traffic}}$ <p>Given parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\Delta CO_{2\text{physical}}$ = CO₂ avoidance due to minimized physical inspections [€] • $\Delta CO_{2\text{traffic}}$ = CO₂ avoidance due to decreased traffic disruptions [€] <p>Emissions avoid due minimized physical inspection is calculated as:</p> $\Delta CO_{2\text{physical}} = N_{\text{inspections}} \times \%D_R \times km_{\text{inspection}} \times F_{\text{consumption}/100km} \times CO_{2\text{savings}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{inspections}}$ = number of annual inspections • $\%D_R$ = percentage replaced by drones [%] • $km_{\text{inspection}}$ = kilometres per inspection [km] • $F_{\text{consumption}/100km}$ = fuel consumption [l/100 km] • $CO_{2\text{savings}}$ = CO₂ savings per litre [€/l] <p>Emissions avoid from reduced traffic disruptions:</p> $\Delta CO_{2\text{traffic}} = N_{\text{inspections}} \times \%I_R \times t_{\text{disruption}} \times N_v \times F_{\text{consumption}/h} \times CO_{2\text{savings}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{inspections}}$ = number of annual inspections

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\%I_R$ = percentage inspections replaced [%] • $t_{\text{disruption}}$ = disruption duration [h] • N_v = number of vehicles/hours • $F_{\text{consumption/h}}$ = fuel consumption [l/h] • $\text{CO}_{2\text{savings}}$ = CO_2 savings per litre [€/l]
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Table 26 presents a summary of the projected economic, reliability and environmental benefits from the implementation of digital permits for drone-based inspection ODP. Economic benefits are led by cost savings from faster permit processing (FPP) with a total impact of over €60.11 million. Revenue for optimized maintenance operations (OMO) results in savings of more than €52 million, while revenue from maintenance automation (RMAE) and fuel savings (FS) contributed 11 million and €47.6 million, respectively. These reflect the platform’s capacity to streamline operations, reduce fuel usage, and enhance resource allocation for infrastructure managers. Reliability benefits include improved infrastructure inspection safety and reliability (IISR) totaling €22.8 million, and significant gains in reduced human error (RRHE) and lower insurance costs from reduced worker risk (ICRWR) with cumulative savings of approximately €3.99 million and €18.1 million, respectively. These figures underscore the platform’s potential to support safer, error-free, and more predictable inspection workflows. Environmental benefits from the reduction of CO₂ emissions over the 10-year period amount to €6.6 million, driven by the shift from traditional road-based inspections to low-emission drone flights. These reductions contribute to the EU’s climate goals by minimizing traffic disruptions and pollution during infrastructure monitoring activities. Figure 17 demonstrates the distribution of these benefits.

Table 26: Economic, reliability and environmental benefits for UCIV

Year	Economic benefits (€)				Reliability benefits (€)			Environmental benefits (€)
	FPP	OMO	RMAE	FS	IISR	RRHE	ICRWR	CO ₂
2026	4,610,400	4,610,400	850,500	5,642,784	2,700,000	306,480	2,250,000	783,720
2027	4,876,385	4,739,664	899,567	5,425,754	2,596,153	324,162	2,163,461	753,577
2028	5,157,715	4,872,551	951,465	5,217,071	2,496,301	342,863	2,080,251	724,593
2029	5,455,275	5,009,165	1,006,358	5,016,414	2,400,290	362,644	2,000,241	696,724
2030	5,770,003	5,149,609	1,064,417	4,823,475	2,307,971	383,565	1,923,309	669,927
2031	6,102,887	5,293,990	1,125,826	4,637,957	2,219,203	405,694	1,849,335	644,161
2032	6,454,977	5,442,420	1,190,777	4,459,574	2,133,849	429,100	1,778,207	619,385
2033	6,827,379	5,595,011	1,259,476	4,288,052	2,051,778	453,856	1,709,815	595,563
2034	7,220,741	5,751,881	1,332,137	4,123,127	1,972,863	480,039	1,644,052	572,657
2035	7,637,878	5,751,881	1,408,992	3,964,545	1,896,984	507,734	1,580,820	550,631

Total	60,113,638	52,377,839	11,089,515	47,598,754	22,775,395	3,996,137	18,979,491	6,610,938
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Note: FPP is cost savings from faster permit processing, OMO is revenue for optimized maintenance operations, RMAE is savings from reduced manual administrative efforts, FS is fuel savings, IISR is improved infrastructure safety and reliability, RRHE is reduced risk of human errors in permit validation, ICRWR is savings in insurance costs from reduced worker risks, CO₂ is CO₂ reduced emissions.

Figure 17: Total benefits of UCIV over the lifetime

Table 27: Summary of benefits over ten years for UCIV

Category	Benefits	(€)
Economic benefits	Cost savings from faster permit processing	52,377,839
	Revenue for optimized maintenance operations	106,405,266
	Savings from reduced manual administrative efforts	9,662,362
	Fuel savings	42,405,832
Reliability benefits	Improved infrastructure safety and reliability	21,035,135
	Reduced risk of human errors in permit validation	3,481,858
	Savings in insurance costs from reduced worker risks	18,979,496
Environmental benefits	CO ₂ reduced emissions	8,343,937
Total benefits		262,691,725

Table 27 summarizes economic, reliability, and environmental benefits over 10 years. Revenue for optimized maintenance operations is the highest among economic benefits.

Step 5: Quantify costs

Capital expenditures (CAPEX)

Table 86 in Appendix A4 shows the CAPEX for drone-based infrastructural inspection ODP deployment in Sapin, Portugal and France. The total upfront cost is €10,635,000. These costs cover hardware, software development, and system integration required for initial deployment.

Recurring operational & maintenance costs (OPEX)

The detailed OPEX for each country in the first year is presented in Table 88 in Appendix A4. The labor cost required for the implementation of the ODP is also presented in Table 87. Figure 18 illustrates the breakdown of OPEX in 2026 across Spain, France, and Portugal, as well as incremental costs tied to drone sensing operations.

Figure 18: Total OPEX in the first year for UCIV

Step 6: Compare costs and benefits

Table 28 provides the cost benefit comparison of drone-based infrastructure inspection ODP in its ten-year lifetime. The total benefits are estimated at €262.7 million, reflecting the combined economic, reliability, and environmental gains resulting from the platform's deployment. The CAPEX and OPEX are estimated to be €10.64m €202m, respectively.

Table 28: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCIV

Category	Value (€)
Total benefits	262,691,725
CAPEX	10,635,000
OPEX	202,068,369

Net benefit (NPV)	49,988,356
BCR	1.24

The ODP results in a net benefit of €50 million and a BCR of 1.24. This confirms that the platform not only recovers its costs but also delivers substantial added value, supporting more efficient, transparent, and safer inspection processes through digitalization and automation in infrastructure management.

Figure 19: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCIV

Figure 19 illustrates a comparative overview of the costs and benefits related to the deployment of the ODP. The results demonstrate an opportunity to deliver long-term operational, regulatory, and environmental impact across the infrastructure inspection ecosystem.

Step 7: Sensitivity analysis and risk assessment

Uncertainty always attaches to estimates of returns on major energy and transportation projects. The results of cost-benefit analysis may change with some critical parameters, as the baseline results are calculated by taking a lot of assumptions. Changes in the assumptions may affect the reliability of the results. Hence, sensitivity analysis is crucial. Table 29 demonstrates the impact of increased benefits (+10% benefits), increased costs (+10%), and decreased benefits (-10%), and decreased costs (-10%).

Table 29: Results under different benefit and cost scenarios for UCIV

Scenario	Benefit change	Cost change	New NPV (€)	New BCR
Base Case	0%	0%	49,988,356	1.24
Increased benefits (+10%)	10%	0%	76,257,529	1.36
Decreased benefits (-10%)	-10%	0%	23,719,184	1.11
Increased costs (+10%)	0%	10%	28,718,019	1.12
Decreased costs (-10%)	0%	-10%	71,258,693	1.37

Figure 20 illustrates the sensitivity analysis of discount rates using NPV and BCR.

Figure 20: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCIV using various discount rates

Figure 21: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCIV using Monte Carlos simulation

We run Monte Carlo simulation executed over 10,000 iterations to evaluate the financial uncertainty in the cost-benefit analysis of the digital permits ODP. This probabilistic approach allows us to model a wide range of scenarios by simulating variations in key

input variables, thereby quantifying the risk and potential variability in investment outcomes.

In this analysis, four main sources of uncertainty were considered:

Drone operator growth: Modelled using a triangular distribution (range: 0.98 to 1.06, mode: 1.03), this captures variability in drone inspection adoption rates over time.

ODP adoption growth: Simulated with a normal distribution (mean = 1.04, standard deviation = 0.01), reflecting the anticipated annual growth in the uptake of the ODP system.

CAPEX variation: Represented by a uniform distribution ranging from 90% to 120% of the base CAPEX value (€10.6M), accounting for uncertainties in initial implementation and infrastructure investment.

OPEX uncertainty: Modelled using a normal distribution (mean = 1.03, standard deviation = 0.016), capturing fluctuations in ongoing costs such as cloud hosting, system maintenance, and support.

The results are presented in Figure 21. The left panel presents the distribution of NPV values (in € million), showing a wide but mostly positive spread. The 5th and 95th percentiles provide a sense of downside and upside risk. The right panel displays the BCR distribution, indicating how frequently the investment exceeds break-even and to what extent. These results offer a robust perspective on the likely financial performance under real-world uncertainties.

3.6. Cost benefit analysis: Smart ports operations

Step 1. Define the Use Case

Please refer to Section 2.5.

Step 2. Map technologies to functions

The main technologies to be considered in this Use Case and their mapping with functionalities are outlined in Table 30.

Table 30: Mapping of technologies onto functions for UCV

		Functions				
Technologies (Assets)		A. Data and information collection	B. Improve interoperability and automatic data processing	C. Predictive maintenance and operational optimization	D. Reporting and digital twin	E. Decision support system

	IoT sensors	•	•	•		•
	AI-driven cameras	•	•	•		•
	Drone fleet	•	•	•		•
	Communication protocol	•	•	•	•	•
	Edge computing frameworks		•			•
	Cloud infrastructure		•			•
	Data integration			•	•	•
	Data lake & databases	•	•	•	•	•
	Edge 5G network	•	•			•
	Message queues	•	•		•	•

Step 3. Map functions to benefits

Table 31 details the mapping of functions to economic, operational and environmental benefits.

Table 31: Mapping functionalities to benefits for UCV

Benefits		Functions				
		A. Data and information collection	B. Improve interoperability and automatic data processing	C. Predictive maintenance and operational optimization	D. Reporting and digital twin	E. Decision support system
Economic benefits	Reduction in operational downtime monitoring			•	•	
	Better planning and scheduling			•	•	•
	Inventory control improvements		•			•
	Reduction in penalties and fines		•			•
	Minimized energy waste	•		•		•
	Operational benefit	Centralized data integration	•	•		•

	Faster response times			•		•
	Reduction in human error			•		
Environmental benefits	Reduced CO ₂ emissions	•		•		•

Economic benefits include cost reductions, reduction in operational downtime, planning and scheduling for cargo movement efficiency, inventory control improvements, reduction in penalties and fines and minimized energy wastes.

Operational benefits enhance port efficiency, logistics reliability, and automated decision-making, ensuring a streamlined and cost-effective supply chain. Centralized data integration improves real-time coordination between AI-driven monitoring systems, digital twin, and port logistics platforms. Faster response times are achieved through AI-driven situational awareness and automated alerts, ensuring swift reactions to operational anomalies, vessel movements, and cargo handling. Reduction in human error is realized by automating port workflows, including cargo tracking, vessel scheduling, and regulatory reporting.

Environmental benefits stem from optimized logistics, reduced emissions, and sustainable resource utilization, leading to lower environmental impact. Reduced CO₂ emissions occur as AI-driven optimization of port operations reduces fuel consumption in logistics and port operations.

Step 4: Monetize benefits

Table 32 presents the detailed formulas and metrics to calculated benefits.

Table 32: Metrics and formulas for calculations of benefits for UCV

Benefits	Metrics and formula of calculations
Reduction in operational downtime monitoring	Continuous monitoring and predictive maintenance minimize unplanned equipment outages. By catching issues early, smart port systems reduce operational downtime, ensuring higher equipment availability and continuous productivity. The reduction in operational downtime monitoring is based on industry benchmarks that show that

	<p>the cost of crane downtime can be extremely high¹². We will focus on crane downtime reduction for the ODP.</p> $\Delta DT = C_{\text{cost}} \times M \times N_{\text{cranes}} \times DT_{\text{saved}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C_{cost} = crane cost [€/h] • M = total months analyzed • N_{cranes} = total number of cranes in the port • DT_{saved} = reduction in downtime, day saved per crane per month [hours/month] <p>We assume a 10%¹³ reduction in downtime (24h, 1 day saved per crane per month¹⁴) using the ODP.</p>
<p>Better planning and scheduling</p>	<p>Advanced planning and scheduling tools improve coordination of port operations (ship arrivals, cargo handling, departures). Better scheduling reduces delays and waiting times for ships and equipment, increasing throughput and avoiding costs associated with idle assets and schedule disruptions.</p> $\Delta PS = BR_{\text{cost}} \times \%BR \times N_{\text{vessels}} \times D$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BR_{cost} = berth rate cost in port of Seville¹⁵ [€/h] • $BR_{\text{reduction}}$ = reduction in berth rate hours per day [h/day] • N_{vessels} = total number of vessels in the port per year • D = total days analyzed <p>We assume 10%¹⁶ reduction (1.5 hours/day reduction in berth rate hours per day) using the ODP. Those benefits are considered with an 8% annual growth of the vessels. Therefore, the benefits will increase every year. Savings accrue each year by reducing delays; benefit is proportional to port traffic levels (if port throughput grows, absolute delay cost savings grow correspondingly).</p>
<p>Inventory control improvements</p>	<p>Digital inventory tracking and analytics reduce overstock and stockouts for port supplies and goods in storage. Optimized inventory levels lower holding costs (such as storage and capital costs) and minimize spoilage or obsolescence.</p> $\Delta CI = SA \times SA_{\text{cost}} \times \%IC \times M$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA = square meters of storage area [m²] • SA_{cost} = holding cost for inventory buffe [€/m²] • $\%IC$ = improvement in inventory control [%]

¹² Assuming 70€ per container move, 30 moves per hour, 24 hours operation and an utilization rate of 65%, multiply 70 by 30 by 24 by 65% and the outcome is 32,760€ a day, for every crane that's not in operation (gantrex.com)

¹³ Integrating real-time intelligence platforms has shown promising results in industrial settings. The implementation of Microsoft Fabric led to an 18% reduction in downtime within three months (<https://nortal.com/insights/real-time-intelligence-with-microsoft-fabric>).

¹⁴ <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/spain/port-congestion-port-stay-duration-by-port-and-vessel-type/port-congestion-port-stay-duration-sevilla-dry-bulk>

¹⁵ <https://www.andalucia.com/boating/mooring.htm>

¹⁶ Integrating an ODP can potentially reduce berth occupancy hours by 10–20% per day. This estimation is based on the cumulative benefits of improved scheduling, predictive maintenance, and optimized cargo handling facilitated by data analytics.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M = total months analyzed <p>Assuming improved inventory management yields a sustained reduction in annual inventory costs (linear benefit each year with a constant percentage reduction in cost). We assume a 10% improvement in inventory control¹⁷.</p>
Reduction in penalties and fines	<p>Enhanced compliance and automated monitoring help avoid regulatory violations, customs delays, and safety incidents that typically result in fines. By meeting environmental, safety, and operational regulations, the port significantly cuts costs from penalties and legal fines.</p> $\Delta PF = \sum \%V \times F_{cost}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • %V = Probability of having the penalty [%] • F_{cost} = cost of the penalty [€/penalty] <p>The potential fines are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality (F_{costW}, %V_W) • Air quality (F_{costA}, %V_A) • Waste management (F_{costE}, %V_E) <p>These compliance benefits are hard to predict. Benefit assumed to recur each year as avoided costs; with smart operations, penalties are eliminated (constant high percentage reduction, barring changes in regulations or enforcement).</p>
Minimized energy waste	<p>Smart energy management in the port reduces unnecessary energy consumption. Cutting energy waste lowers electricity usage and costs while maintaining operational performance.</p> $\Delta E = (\Delta E_{ODP} \times E_{cost}) + (\Delta F \times F_{cost})$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ΔE_{ODP} = energy savings [kWh] • E_{cost} = electricity price [€/kWh] • ΔF = fuel saved [L] • F_{cost} = fuel price [€/L] <p>These benefits are considered with an 8% growth of the litres saved per year, thanks to the annual growth of the port. Therefore, the benefits will increase every year.</p>
Centralized data	<p>Integrating data from disparate systems into a unified platform streamlines information flow and eliminates duplicate data entry. This integration reduces administrative labour and errors, yielding cost savings and faster decision-making due to real-time comprehensive data availability.</p> $\Delta CD = N_{IT} \times P$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{IT} = total number of IT workers

¹⁷ Companies that have employed inventory optimization strategies have reported reductions in inventory levels by up to 25% within a year, along with improvements in service levels and overall operational efficiency (William Brandel, "Inventory Optimization Saves Working Capital in Tough Times," Computerworld, August 24, 2009).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P = effective productivity [€/worker] <p>The effective productivity is calculated as:</p> $P = t_{IT_{saved}} \times D \times LC_{IT}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LC_{IT} = IT labour costs [€/day] • D = total days analysed • $t_{IT_{saved}}$ = time saved per day [h/day]
Faster response times		<p>Real-time alerts and situational awareness tools enable quicker incident response (e.g. to equipment failures or safety hazards). Faster response mitigates the impact of incidents, shortening downtime and reducing damage or loss, which translates into cost savings.</p> $\Delta CD = t_{saved} \times N_{incidents} \times D_{cost}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t_{saved} = time saved per incident [h] • $N_{incidents}$ = total number of incidents per year • D_{cost} = delayed response halted operation [€/h] $t_{saved} = t_{old} - t_{new}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t_{old} = old equipment failure response [h] • t_{new} = new equipment failure response with ODP [h] <p>Assumes a roughly constant number of incidents annually; each incident incurs less cost with quick response, yielding consistent yearly savings (scales linearly, or increases if incident frequency grows).</p>
Reduction in human error	in	<p>Automation and decision support systems reduce the frequency of human errors in operations (such as misrouting containers, data entry mistakes, or safety errors). Fewer errors mean less work, fewer delays, and avoidance of accident costs, directly saving money and improving safety.</p> $\Delta CD = M_I \times \%A_{HA} \times I_{cost}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M_I = Marine incidents per year • $\%A_{HA}$ = accidents events that involved human action errors [%] • I_{cost} = Incident cost [€/incident] <p>Expected to provide stable yearly cost saving by maintaining a lower error rate (constant error reduction percentage each year once systems are in place).</p>
Reduced emission	CO2	<p>Greener port operations cut greenhouse gas emissions through energy efficiency, electrification of equipment, and optimized logistics (reducing idling and travel distances). Lower CO₂ emissions contribute to sustainability targets and can be monetized via carbon credit revenues or avoided carbon taxes.</p> $\Delta CO_2 = pCO_2 \times \Delta EE_{ET,ODP}$ <p>where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pCO_2 = CO₂ emission price [€/tonne] • $\Delta EE_{ET,ODP}$ = CO₂ reduction from fossil fuel vehicles due to ODP [tonnes CO₂/year]

All the assumptions and data necessary to calculate the listed benefits are presented in Appendix A5.

Figure 22 provides the benefits of implementing ODP for smart port operation over a ten-year period. In Addition, Tables 33 and 34 summarize the benefits over the time horizon of the ODP. The total projected benefits are approximately €233.9 million. Economic benefits are €108.5 million, Operational benefits could reach a total of €117.7 million and environmental benefits are expected to be 7.6. Figure 22 plots each benefit where economic benefits are in blue, operational benefits are in light red and environmental in light green.

Table 33: Economic, reliability and environmental benefits for UCV

Year	Economic Benefits (€)					Administrative benefits (€)			Environmental benefits (€)
	RODM	BPS	ICI	RPF	MEW	CD	FRT	RHE	GHG
2026	6,609,600	609,696	1,200,000	3,371,002	719,000	25,550	3,249,288	6,615,000	634,975
2027	6,355,385	633,146	1,153,846	3,241,348	709,808	24,567	3,374,261	6,869,423	659,397
2028	6,110,947	657,498	1,109,467	3,116,681	701,679	23,622	3,504,040	7,133,632	684,759
2029	5,875,910	682,786	1,066,796	2,996,809	694,600	22,714	3,638,811	7,408,002	711,095
2030	5,649,914	709,047	1,025,765	2,881,547	688,560	21,840	3,778,765	7,692,925	738,445
2031	5,432,609	736,318	986,313	2,770,718	683,546	21,000	3,924,102	7,988,807	766,847
2032	5,223,663	764,638	948,377	2,664,152	679,552	20,193	4,075,029	8,296,069	796,341
2033	5,022,753	794,047	911,901	2,561,684	676,568	19,416	4,231,761	8,615,148	826,970
2034	4,829,570	824,587	876,828	2,463,158	674,590	18,669	4,394,521	8,946,500	858,776
2035	4,643,817	856,302	843,104	2,368,421	673,613	17,951	4,563,541	9,290,596	891,806
Total	55,754,168	7,268,065	10,122,398	28,435,520	6,901,516	215,523	38,734,118	78,856,103	7,569,411

Note: RODM is reduction in operational downtime monitoring, BPS is better planning and scheduling, ICI is inventory control improvements, RPF is reduction in penalties and fines, MEW is minimized energy waste, CD is centralized data, FRT is faster response times, RHE is reduction in human error, GHG is reduced CO₂ emissions.

Figure 22: Total benefits of UCV over the lifetime

Table 34: Summary of benefits over ten years for UCV

Category	Benefits	(€)
Economic Benefits	Reduction in operational downtime monitoring	55,754,168
	Better planning and scheduling	7,268,065
	Inventory control improvements	10,122,398
	Reduction in penalties and fines	28,435,520
	Minimize energy waste	6,901,516
Operational Benefits	Faster response times	215,523
	Faster response times	38,734,118
	Reduction in human error	75,856,103
Environmental benefits	Reduced CO2 emissions	7,569,411
Total benefits		233,856,821

Step 5: Quantify costs

Capital expenditures (CAPEX)

Table 93 in Appendix A5 presents CAPEX, which is expected to be over €13,475,000 during the ODP's lifetime.

Recurring operational & maintenance costs (OPEX)

Figure 23 presents the OPEX distribution across various cost categories for the first year. Cloud computing and data processing, network maintenance (5G/LPWAN), and cybersecurity & threat monitoring, each amounting to €2.0 million.

Figure 23: Total OPEX in the first year for UCV

Step 6: Compare Costs and Benefits

Table 35 provides a comparative analysis of the costs and benefits associated with the deployment of the ODP over a ten-year period. The total benefits are estimated at €233.9 million, while CAPEX and OPEX amount to €13.5 million and €92.8 million, respectively. This yields a net benefit of €127.5 million. The BCR of 2.2 indicates for every €1 invested, the ODP on average delivers €2.2.

Figure 24 provides a comparison of the costs and benefits associated with the ODP over their ten-year lifetime.

Table 35: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCV

Category	Value (€)
Total benefits	233,856,821
CAPEX	13,475,000
OPEX	92,843,056
Net Benefit (NPV)	127,538,766
BCR	2.20

Figure 24: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCV

Economic benefits amount to around €108.5 million, followed by operational benefits of €117.8 million, and environmental benefits of €7.6 million. These yield a net benefit of €127.5 million, represented in green, which emphasizes the positive return and societal value delivered by the ODP initiative. This analysis confirms that the ODP deliver a strong return on investment, with benefits significantly outweighing costs, making them a high-impact solution for smart port operations in port of Seville.

Step 7: Sensitivity analysis and risk assessment

Table 36 presents scenarios demonstrating how changes in benefits and costs influence BCR and NPV. If benefits increase by 10%, the BCR improves to 2.42, and the NPV reaches €150.9 million. On the other hand, if benefits decrease by 10%, the BCR drops to 1.98, while the NPV declines to €104.2 million. If the total cost increases by 10%, the NPV and BCR will reduce to 116.9 million and 2.00, respectively. Meanwhile, if the total cost decreases by 10%, the NPV and BCR increase to €138.2 million and 2.44, respectively.

Table 36: Results under different benefit and cost scenarios for UCV

Scenario	Benefit change	Cost change	New NPV (€)	New BCR
Base Case	0%	0%	127,538,766	2.20
Increased benefits (+10%)	10%	0%	150,924,447	2.42
Decreased benefits (-10%)	-10%	0%	104,153,083	1.98
Increased costs (+10%)	0%	10%	116,906,959	2.00

Decreased costs (-10%)	0%	-10%	138,170,571	2.44
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In addition, Figure 25 illustrates the sensitivity analysis of discount rates using NPV and BCR.

Figure 25: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCV using various discount rates

Figure 26: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCV using Monte Carlos simulation

To run the Monte Carlo simulation with 10,000 iterations, we introduce variability in benefit uptake (modeled using a normal distribution with a mean of 1.0 and a standard deviation of 0.05), OPEX uncertainty (normal distribution with a mean of 1.04 and a standard deviation of 0.01), CAPEX fluctuations (represented by a uniform distribution of $\pm 10\%$), and recurrent CAPEX changes (using a triangular distribution with a minimum of 0.95, a mode of 1.0, and a maximum of 1.05). The left panel of Figure 26 presents the distribution of NPV values (in € million), showing a wide but mostly positive spread. The 5th and 95th percentiles provide a sense of downside and upside risk. The right panel displays the BCR distribution, indicating how frequently the investment exceeds break-even and to what extent. These results offer a robust perspective on the likely financial performance under real-world uncertainties.

3.7. Cost benefit analysis: Carbon footprint of ports supply chain

Step 1. Define the Use Case

Please refer to Section 2.6.

Step 2. Map technologies to functions

Table 37 maps the technologies to their respective functionalities, which are important in the next steps.

Table 37: Mapping of technologies onto functions for UCVI

		Functions				
		A. Data and information collection	B. Improve interoperability and automatic data processing	C. Carbon footprint calculation	D. Reporting and visualization	E. Decision support system
Technologies (Assets)	IoT Sensors	•	•	•		•
	Communication protocol	•	•	•	•	•
	Edge computing frameworks		•			•
	Cloud infrastructure		•			•
	Blockchain Network		•			
	Data integration			•	•	•
	Data lake & databases	•	•	•	•	•
	Edge 5G network	•	•			•
	Message queues	•	•			•
	Port/Customs Integration				•	•
	Blockchain Integration		•			

Step 3. Map functions to benefits

Table 38 shows the mapping of functionalities to economic, administrative and environmental benefits. *Economic benefits* of the ODP for logistics operations at ports stem from efficiency improvements, cost reductions, and enhanced decision-making. Optimized cargo handling reduces operational costs, minimizes loading and unloading times, and increases overall logistics productivity by improving interoperability and data

processing. Optimized port waiting time directly translates to cost savings, improved resource utilization, and increased operational throughput through advanced data collection and decision support systems. Reduced fuel consumption leads to direct cost reductions and environmental benefits by integrating data collection, decision support, and potentially carbon footprint calculation. *Administrative benefits* stem from the automation, digitalization, and standardization of key logistics and compliance processes enabled by the ODP. Reduced administrative burden streamlines data collection, reporting, and documentation processes, reducing the reliance on manual data entry and paper-based workflows. Environmental benefits arise from optimized logistics operations, reduced fuel consumption, and lower emissions, leading to a more sustainable and efficient supply chain.

Table 38: Mapping functionalities to benefits for UCVI

Benefits		Functions				
		A. Data and information collection	B. Improve interoperability and automatic data processing	C. Carbon footprint calculation	D. Reporting and visualization	E. Decision support system
Economic benefits	Reduced fuel consumption	•				•
	Optimized cargo handling		•			•
	Optimized port waiting time		•			•
Administrative benefits	Reduced administrative burden		•		•	
	Reduced compliance fines				•	
Environmental benefits	Reduced CO2 emissions		•	•		•
	Reduced SOx, NOx and PM10 emissions		•	•		•

Step 4: Monetize benefits

Table 39 presents the formulas, and the calculation of each benefit identified in Step 3.

Table 39: Metrics and formulas for calculations of benefits for UCVI

Benefits	Metrics and formula of calculations
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<p>Reduced fuel consumption</p>	$\Delta F = \Delta BF_{\text{consumption}} \times P_{\text{ff}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\Delta BF_{\text{consumption}}$ = baseline fuel consumption [L consumed/year] • p_{ff} = fuel price per ton [€/ton of fuel] <p>Calculate baseline fuel consumption</p> $\Delta BF_{\text{consumption}} = T \times C_{\text{ff}} \times \text{km}_{\text{route}} \times \%R_{\text{ff}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T = Tonnage [ton] • C_{ff} = Fuel consumption factor [L/ton-km] • km_{route} = Trade route distance [km] • $\%R_{\text{ff}}$ = Fuel reduction [%]
<p>Optimized cargo handling</p>	$\Delta CH = \Delta t_{\text{cargo}} \times \text{op}_{\text{cost}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Δt_{cargo} = time saved [h] • op_{cost} = operational cost [€/h] <p>Calculate time saved:</p> $\Delta t_{\text{cargo}} = t_{\text{cargo}_{\text{annual}}} \times \%R_{\text{cargo}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $t_{\text{cargo}_{\text{annual}}}$ = total handling cargo hours [h] • $\%R_{\text{cargo}}$ = reduction from optimization [%] <p>Calculate total annual cargo handling hours (Before Optimization)</p> $t_{\text{cargo}_{\text{annual}}} = N_{\text{ship}_{\text{proc}}} \times t_{\text{handling}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{ship}_{\text{proc}}}$ = ships processed annually • t_{handling} = handling time per ship [h] <p>These benefits will be increased annually due to a 5% increase in the port traffic.</p>
<p>Optimized port waiting time</p>	$\Delta Wt = \Delta t_{\text{waiting}} \times \text{op}_{\text{cost}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\Delta t_{\text{waiting}}$ = time saved [h] • op_{cost} = operational cost [€/h] <p>Calculate time saved:</p> $\Delta t_{\text{waiting}} = t_{\text{waiting}_{\text{total}}} \times \%R_{\text{waiting}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $t_{\text{waiting}_{\text{total}}}$ = total waiting hours [h] • $\%R_{\text{waiting}}$ = reduction from optimization [%] <p>Calculate total annual cargo handling hours (before optimization)</p> $t_{\text{cargo}_{\text{annual}}} = N_{\text{ship}_{\text{proc}}} \times t_{\text{waiting}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $N_{\text{ship}_{\text{proc}}}$ = ships processed annually • t_{waiting} = waiting time per ship [h] <p>These benefits will be increased annually due to a 5% increase in the port traffic.</p>
<p>Reduced administrative burden</p>	$\Delta AB = \%R_{\text{admin}} \times \text{admin}_{\text{cost}_{\text{tot}}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\%R_{\text{admin}}$ = reduction from optimization [%] • $\text{admin}_{\text{cost}_{\text{tot}}}$ = total administrative cost [€/h] <p>Administrative cost calculated as (before optimization):</p> $\text{admin}_{\text{cost}_{\text{tot}}} = N_{\text{entities}} \times \text{admin}_{\text{cost}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{entities} = total number of affected entities in port • $\text{admin}_{\text{cost}}$ = administrative cost per entity [€] <p>We assume a 1% growth of these entities. Therefore, the benefits will be higher each year.</p>
<p>Reduced compliance fines</p>	$\Delta F = \%R_{\text{fines}} \times N_{\text{fines}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\%R_{\text{fines}}$ = reduction from optimization [%] • N_{fines} = total number of fines before optimization

	<p>Calculate total annual compliance fines (before optimization):</p> $N_{\text{fines}} = N_{\text{entities}_{\text{risk}}} \times \%R \times F_{\text{cost}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{entities} = total entities at risk • $\%R$ = risk percentage [%] • F_{cost} = fine per entity [€] <p>We assume a 1% growth of these entities. Therefore, the benefits will be higher each year.</p>
<p>Reduced carbon emissions</p>	$\Delta\text{CO}_2 = \text{CO}_{2\text{saving}} \times p\text{CO}_2$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\text{CO}_{2\text{saving}}$ = CO₂ savings [ton] • $p\text{CO}_2$ = carbon credit price [€/ton] <p>Calculate CO₂ savings (10% reduction):</p> $\text{CO}_{2\text{saving}} = N_{\text{CO}_2} \times \%R_{\text{CO}_2}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_{CO_2} = total CO₂ emissions [ton] • $\%R_{\text{CO}_2}$ = reduction from optimization [%] <p>Calculate CO₂ emissions before optimization:</p> $N_{\text{CO}_2} = T \times \%f_{\text{CO}_2} \times \text{km}_{\text{route}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T = Tonnage [ton] • km_{route} = Trade route distance [km] • $\%f_{\text{CO}_2}$ = CO₂ factor [%] <p>These benefits will be increased annually due to a 5% increase in the port traffic.</p>
<p>Reduced Sox, Nox and PM10 emissions</p>	$\Delta\text{PE} = \sum P_{\text{savings}} \times p_p$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P_{savings} = pollutant savings [ton] • p_p = pollutant price [€/ton] <p>Calculate pollutant savings (10% reduction):</p> $P_{\text{savings}} = N_p \times \%R_{\text{PE}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N_p = total pollutant emissions [ton] • $\%R_{\text{PE}}$ = reduction from optimization [%] <p>Calculate pollutant emissions before optimization:</p> $N_{\text{CO}_2} = T \times \%f_p \times \text{km}_{\text{route}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T = Tonnage [ton] • km_{route} = Trade route distance [km] • $\%f_p$ = pollutant factor [%] <p>We analyze 3 pollutants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SO_x ($\%f_{\text{SO}_x}, p_{\text{SO}_x}$) • NO_x ($\%f_{\text{NO}_x}, p_{\text{NO}_x}$) • PM10 ($\%f_{\text{PM10}}, p_{\text{PM10}}$) <p>These benefits will be increased annually due to a 5% increase in the port traffic. Therefore, the tonnage per year will increase accordingly, and the benefits will be higher for 10 years.</p>

All the assumptions and data used for the calculation of benefits are presented in Appendix A6.

Table 40: Economic, reliability and environmental benefits for UCVI

Year	Economic Benefits (€)			Administrative benefits (€)		Environmental benefits (€)	
	RFC	OCH	OPT	RAB	RCF	CO ₂	SOx
2026	7,423,993	7,790,400	7,790,400	1,675,000	5,025,000	3,299,552	6,255,951
2027	7,795,192	8,179,920	7,644,785	1,581,075	4,743,224	3,237,878	6,139,017
2028	8,184,952	8,588,916	7,501,892	1,492,416	4,477,249	3,177,357	6,024,269
2029	8,594,199	9,018,362	7,361,670	1,408,729	4,226,188	3,117,967	5,911,666
2030	9,023,909	9,469,280	7,224,068	1,329,735	3,989,206	3,059,688	5,801,168
2031	9,475,105	9,942,744	7,089,039	1,255,171	3,765,512	3,002,497	5,692,735
2032	9,948,860	10,439,881	6,956,534	1,184,787	3,554,362	2,946,376	5,586,329
2033	10,446,303	10,961,875	6,826,505	1,118,351	3,355,052	2,891,303	5,481,911
2034	10,968,618	11,509,969	6,698,907	1,055,639	3,166,918	2,837,260	5,379,446
2035	11,517,049	12,085,467	6,573,693	996,445	2,989,334	2,784,227	5,278,895
Total	93,378,181	97,986,814	71,667,492	13,097,349	39,989,334	30,354,107	57,551,387

Note: RFC is reduced fuel consumption, OCH is optimized cargo handling, OPT is optimized port waiting time, RAB is reduced administrative burden, RCF is reduced compliance fines, CO₂ is CO₂ emissions reduction and Sox is air pollutant reduction (SOx, NOx and PM10).

Figure 27: Total benefits of UCVI over the lifetime

Table 40 presents economic, administrative and environmental benefits over the ten-year lifetime of the ODP. Table 41 summarizes the projected benefits for carbon footprint of ports supply chain over a ten-year period and the total benefit is approximately €345.7 million. To demonstrate all the benefits, Figure 27 depicts all benefits where we can see that economic benefits are the dominant ones.

Table 41: Summary of benefits over ten years for UCVI

Category	Benefits	(€)
Economic Benefits	Reduced fuel consumption	93,378,181

	Optimized cargo handling	97,986,814
	Optimized port waiting time	71,667,492
Administrative Benefits	Reduced administrative burden	13,097,349
	Reduced compliance fines	39,292,046
Environmental benefits	Reduced CO2 emissions	30,354,107
	Reduced SOx, NOx, PM10	57, 551,387
Total benefits		345,775,989

Step 5: Quantify costs

Capital expenditures (CAPEX)

Tables 99 and 100 in Appendix A6 present the CAPEX of TEUs sensors and miscellaneous technologies required for the deployment of the ODP. These investments cover maritime sensors for ships on TEU volume such as road freight sensors for trucks, and mobile units, enabling real-time emissions tracking and logistics data collection. Port facilities sensors will be installed in two pilot ports, Vigo and Leixões, to monitor air quality, energy usage, and local pollution. Additionally, connectivity infrastructure such as 5G and LPWAN networks will be deployed in Spain and Portugal to support seamless communication across logistics nodes. Data integration middleware is included to enable system interoperability, and blockchain infrastructure will ensure secure, immutable carbon footprint records. These costs are considered once for platform implementation. Nevertheless, it's expected the number of TEUs will grow in the next few years. Considering that the number of TEUs is growing 5% each year,

Recurring operational & maintenance costs (OPEX)

Figure 28 outlines the annual recurring operational and maintenance costs for the ODP implementation. The results show that comprehensive analytics tools and software deployment & integration are the highest costs to implement the ODP in Spain and Portugal.

Figure 28: Total OPEX in the first year for UCVI

Step 6: Compare Costs and Benefits

Table 42 provides a comparative assessment of the economic performance of ODP over a ten-year horizon. The total benefits amount to €345.7 billion, while the CAPEX and OPEX sum up to €54.7 million and €87.6 million, respectively. The net benefit of €203.5 million demonstrates the ODP implementation's economic feasibility and long-term financial gains. The BCR of 2.43 indicates that for every €1 invested, the system generates €2.43 in benefits. Figure 29 provides a comparison of the costs and benefits associated with the carbon footprint ODP over their ten-year lifetime based on the benefits categories.

Table 42: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCVI

Category	Value (€)
Total benefits	345,775,989
CAPEX	54,663,660
OPEX	87,620,320
Net Benefit (NPV)	203,492,009
BCR	2.43

Figure 29: Comparison of costs and benefits for UCVI

Step 7: Sensitivity analysis

Table 43 presents scenarios demonstrating how changes in benefits and costs influence BCR and NPV. If benefits increase by 10%, the BCR improves to 2.67, and the NPV reaches €238.1 million. On the other hand, if benefits decrease by 10%, the BCR drops to 2.19, while the NPV declines to €168.9 million. If the total cost increases by 10%, the NPV and BCR will reduce to €189.3 million and 2.21, respectively. Meanwhile, if the total cost decreases by 10%, the NPV and BCR increase to €217.7 million and 2.70, respectively.

Additionally, Figure 30 illustrates the sensitivity analysis of discount rates using NPV and BCR. Sensitivity analysis using Monte Carlos simulation on NPV and BCR is presented in Figure 31.

Table 43: Results under different benefit and cost scenarios for UCVI

Scenario	Benefit change	Cost change	New NPV (€)	New BCR
Base Case	0%	0%	203,492,009	2.43
Increased benefits (+10%)	10%	0%	238,069,608	2.67
Decreased benefits (-10%)	-10%	0%	168,914,410	2.19
Increased costs (+10%)	0%	10%	189,263,611	2.21
Decreased costs (-10%)	0%	-10%	217,720,407	2.70

Figure 30: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCVI using various discount rates

Figure 31: Sensitivity analysis on NPV and BCR of UCV using Monte Carlos simulation

The simulation results demonstrate the financial viability of the ODP, showing that the NPV ranges from over €190 million to less than €230 million. The BCR further confirms this viability, indicating that a €1 investment could yield a return of up to €2.8.

3.8. Economic feasibility summary

In Table 44, we establish the criteria for conducting the economic feasibility assessment by leveraging the results of the cost-benefit analysis and ranking the six UCs. Each UC is evaluated using a multi-criterion weighted scoring approach, which ensures a comprehensive assessment by accounting for both financial returns and implementation challenges. Each criterion is assigned a weight based on its relative importance, and scores are determined using a reverse ranking system. This system awards higher scores to UCs that perform better relative to others, enabling clear and structured differentiation. Overall, this method supports informed decision-making aimed at maximizing value within constraints.

Table 44: The criteria for economic feasibility assessment

Criterion	Description	Scoring guide	Weight (%)
NPV	Measures the profitability of investment for each use case based on the NPV.	=5 if ranked no. 1; =4 if ranked no. 2; =3 if ranked no. 3; =2 if ranked no.4; =1 if ranked no. 5 or 6	40
BCR	Measures the overall value or efficiency of investment for each use case based on the BCR.	=5 if ranked no. 1; =4 if ranked no. 2; =3 if ranked no. 3; =2 if ranked no.4; =1 if ranked no. 5 or 6	25
CAPEX ratio	$CAPEX = \frac{CAPEX}{Total\ cost}$ Measures how much of a project's total cost is spent on long-term assets (capital investments). Lower CAPEX ratio improves feasibility.	=5 if ranked no. 1; =4 if ranked no. 2; =3 if ranked no. 3; =2 if ranked no.4; =1 if ranked no. 5 or 6	15
Cost-effectiveness for environmental outcomes	$\frac{cost\ effectiveness}{Total\ cost} = \frac{Environmental\ benefits}{Total\ cost}$ Assess the cost-effectiveness in terms of environmental outcomes. Higher values measure cost-effectiveness in terms of environmental benefits.	=5 if ranked no. 1; =4 if ranked no. 2; =3 if ranked no. 3; =2 if ranked no.4; =1 if ranked no. 5 or 6	10
Sensitivity and risk resilience	Considered as the range of NPV changes using Monte Carlos simulation. Higher value measures robustness of the financial outcomes under uncertainty and the presence of risk.	=5 if ranked no. 1; =4 if ranked no. 2; =3 if ranked no. 3; =2 if ranked no.4; =1 if ranked no. 5 or 6	10

Before applying the economic and financial scoring of the Use Cases, we summarize the main elements of the cost-benefit analysis for each Use Case in Table 45. Total cost and CAPEX are important for calculating the sub-criteria CAPEX ratio. This metric measures how much of the ODP's total cost is spent on long-term technologies. The insights is that the lower the ratio, the better the financial feasibility of the ODP. Additionally, total cost and environmental benefits are used to assess the cost-effectiveness of each Use Case in terms of its environmental impact. To evaluate sensitivity and risk resilience, we consider

the range of NPV based on Monte Carlo simulation results. A higher value for this metric indicates a more resilient Use Case.

Table 45: The values for sub-criterion of UCs based on economic feasibility

Sub-criterion	Values					
	UCI	UCII	UCIII	UCIV	UCV	UCVI
NPV (€million)	931	439	357	203	128	50
BCR	2.43	2.41	2.20	1.83	1.41	1.24
CAPEX ratio	0.54	0.64	0.13	0.05	0.15	0.38
Cost-effectiveness for environmental outcomes	0.59	0.16	0.42	0.04	0.08	0.40
Sensitivity and risk resilience (Monte Carlo results)	500	200	50	20	20	40

Table 46 presents the weighted scores of each UC by criterion, along with the total scores from the economic feasibility analysis. Based on the total scores, UCI ranks highest in performance, while UCV ranks lowest. Stakeholders cost sources did not consider in the cost-benefit analysis as each Use Case is unique in terms of CAPEX source and OPEX implementations. Some Use Cases have internal CAPEX sources to implement the full ODP while others should be implemented considering the existing systems. Our overall focus is, however, the comparisons of costs and benefits irrespective of the sources of financing to implement the ODP.

Table 46: Sub-criterion and total weighted scores of UCs based on economic feasibility

Sub-criterion	Weights (%)	Scores					
		UCI	UCII	UCIII	UCIV	UCV	UCVI
NPV	40	5	4	3	2	1	1
BCR	25	2	1	4	1	3	5
CAPEX ratio	15	1	1	4	5	3	2
Cost-effectiveness for environmental outcomes	10	5	2	4	1	1	3
Sensitivity and risk resilience	10	5	4	3	1	1	2
Total weighted score	100	3.65	2.6	3.50	2.00	1.80	2.45

4. Technical feasibility

4.1. Scoring criteria and guides for technical feasibility

Detailed technical feasibility for the six shortlisted UCs is issued as Deliverable D3.1. The technical feasibility summary in this Deliverable is intended to score the six UCs based on the sub-criteria presented in Table 47. Each sub-criterion has its scoring guide and weight assigned based on its importance and scores are given from 1 to 5.

Table 47: Technical feasibility criteria, scoring guides and weights assigned

Sub-criterion	Description	Scoring guide	Weight (%)
Technology readiness	Are the core technologies at TRL 7 or higher and tested in real conditions?	5 = TRL \geq 8, 3 = TRL 6–7, 1 = $<$ TRL 6	17.5
Integration complexity	Can the system be integrated with existing IT/grid/energy systems without extensive customization or rework?	5 = Plug-and-play, 3 = Medium integration effort, 1 = High complexity	17.5
Availability	Are required physical infrastructure (sensors, data layers, grid systems) and connectivity (e.g. 5G, cloud infra) available in pilot countries?	5 = Fully in place, 3 = Partial, 1 = Major gaps	22.5
Interoperability potential	Is the Use Case built on open standards (e.g. FIWARE, Gaia-X) and designed for platform interoperability?	5 = Fully aligned with EU data spaces/standards, 3 = Partial, 1 = Proprietary only	20
Scalability & modularity	Can the solution be scaled or deployed modularly across regions or contexts?	5 = Fully modular/scalable, 3 = Somewhat, 1 = Not scalable	22.5

4.2. Summary results and discussions

Table 48 presents the sub-criterion scores and weighted scores for each UC based on technical feasibility. Based on the technical feasibility results, UCV, UCII and UCI are the three highest scoring UCs.

Table 48: Sub-criterion and total weighted scores of UCs based on technical feasibility

Sub-criterion	Weights (%)	Scores					
		UCI	UCII	UCIII	UCIV	UCV	UCVI
Technology readiness	17.5	4	5	3	2	4	3
Integration complexity	17.5	2	3	4	2	5	2

Infrastructural availability	22.5	4	5	2	4	3	4
Interoperability potential	20.0	3	3	3	2	5	3
Scalability & modularity	22.5	3	5	3	2	5	3
Total weighted score	100	3.23	4.25	2.95	2.45	4.37	3.05

A detailed explanation and justification of each Use Case scores, based on the five criteria are provided in the following subsections.

Electricity customers-centric ODP

The technical feasibility of this UC is relatively high. It builds on mature technologies, such as smart meters and IoT devices that are already deployed across many EU countries, particularly in Germany, Sweden, and Denmark, where this UC will be piloted if selected. Additionally, the growing standardization of digital identity frameworks, such as eIDAS, supports secure and verifiable customer authentication. However, challenges remain in the harmonization of cross-border data exchange, synchronization of contracts across different actors, and ensuring compliance with national regulatory variations. These issues can be addressed through modular platform design and adherence to EU interoperability standards. An increasing number of energy communities are being established, enabling consumers to contribute to a more flexible grid through their smart devices. Moreover, companies are beginning to offer aggregated flexibility services that leverage these devices. However, large-scale and cross-border implementations have yet to be realized. Furthermore, automatic supplier switching must be implemented individually for each country, as EU member states offer different interfaces to support this process.

AI-driven ODP for integration of EVs, ETs, RES and Grid

Technically, this UC is well-supported by advances in AI algorithms for route optimization, energy demand forecasting, and real-time traffic analytics. Charging infrastructure across the EU has become increasingly digitalized, and many operators already expose APIs for external coordination. Moreover, IoT-enabled CPs and smart fleet management systems make data acquisition technically viable. However, challenges exist in unifying data standards across different CP operators and integrating with national grid operators to manage flexibility services in real-time, particularly in cross-border scenarios.

Digitalisation of data centres

The technical feasibility is supported by existing DC management systems (BMS, EMS), widely deployed monitoring infrastructure, and growing interest in energy optimization through digital twins. The use of predictive AI models for demand forecasting and planning services to evaluate new technology deployment is also a mature domain. Technically, many DCs already participate in energy flexibility initiatives at national level,

although cross-border computational load shifting and coordination with DSOs/TSOs is still evolving. There are two main challenges with this UC from a technological perspective: *integration with individual data centres* and *security*. DCs are run and operated by many different companies with little to no standardization. Many have also been constructed without considering heat reuse and grid flexibility, which can make it difficult to fully utilize the data centres potential. Finally, operational stability and privacy are critical to data centres, which can complicate some of the integration needed to realize this Use Case.

Digital permits for drone-based inspections

The proposed solution in this UC introduces a blockchain-based digital permitting system that integrates data from various regulatory authorities and streamlines validation and authorization procedures. While blockchain, digital signatures, and workflow management technologies are mature, their coordinated application across aviation, environmental, and security agencies presents challenges. Nevertheless, growing alignment with EASA drone regulations and increased interest from public authorities in automation indicate high feasibility. This UC involves integration with multiple regulatory bodies, which poses an additional challenge, as some of these agencies currently lack automated solutions. Moreover, the relevant authorities vary by country, requiring tailored implementations to address country-specific regulatory environments.

Smart port operations

The FIWARE architecture aligns well with port digitalization efforts supported by CEF and national initiatives. Modern ports typically have data sources such as camera feeds, drone telemetry, and port equipment sensors already in place. API-based integration with existing port management systems is technically feasible. UCV aims to unify these existing devices into a single management system for the entire port, combining current technologies with enhanced functionalities. While some new functionalities will be introduced, most of the underlying technologies have already been tested in various scenarios. Therefore, the primary complexity of this UC lies in adapting and tailoring the functionality to meet the specific operational and regulatory requirements of each port.

Carbon footprint of port supply chain

The technical foundation for this UC includes emissions calculators, APIs from transport operators, and tracking systems (e.g., AIS for ships, GPS for trucks). The use of blockchain and data spaces supports the secure and transparent sharing of data among actors. The main challenge is harmonizing CF calculation methods and ensuring data interoperability across jurisdictions. Tracking carbon emissions of an entire supply chain is challenging as many different companies as possible, devices, and systems need to be involved. However, some of these will already be tracking or estimating their emissions, which simplifies some of the development.

5. Regulatory, governance, and stakeholder readiness

5.1. Scoring criteria and guides for regulatory alignment and stakeholder readiness

The regulatory analysis reveals that most UCs align well with EU regulations, demonstrating high feasibility for implementation in compliant markets. However, challenges persist at national level implementation for example those national regulatory gaps limit market participation. For instance, drone operations and smart port initiatives face barriers due to variations in national aviation and maritime laws. The scorings reported here come from the detailed analysis conducted in deliverable D3.2. Stakeholders consulted during the development of the BEGONIA UCs have, in general, demonstrated a clear interest in the proposed activities and acknowledged their relevance. Their feedback, ranging from overall support to specific interest in individual UCs, has been collected through both bilateral discussions and a targeted survey. These inputs have also provided insights into their willingness to contribute to or lead implementation efforts. The survey, aside of the interest in the specific ones, has shown that stakeholders consider the UCs relevant for solving current challenges in the energy and transport sectors (4.33 out of 5) and a general interest in the implementation of one or more UCs (4.33 out of 5).

The stakeholders' engagement is addressed through two different sub-criteria:

- **Stakeholder Alignment:** Measures the level of interest expressed by stakeholders in a specific UC and their recognition of its relevance.
- **Stakeholders support for UC deployment:** Evaluates the extent to which stakeholders are prepared to pilot or actively contribute to the UC's implementation in the short term.

Stakeholder responses were weighted based on the mode and strength of expression, and then translated into a standardized 1-to-5 scoring scale as follows.

Scoring of stakeholder alignment:

- An official expression of interest and a positive reply via the stakeholder survey was assigned 1 point.
- Interest expressed during bilateral conversations was assigned 0.5 points.
- The total score for each UC was calculated by summing these values and dividing by the total number of respondents, resulting in a percentage that was mapped to the scoring scale: 0-5% = 1 point; 5-10% = 2 points; 10-20% = 3, 20-30% = 4, >30% = 5.

Scoring of stakeholder support for UC deployment:

In this case, the scoring follows the qualitative criteria outlined in Table 49, which reflect both the level of stakeholder engagement and their readiness to support implementation.

- 5 = One or more key stakeholders are fully capable and ready to implement the UC. Clear, confirmed commitment from stakeholders who possess the authority, technical capacity, and resources to support full-scale deployment.
- 4 = Stakeholders are engaged and interested in deployment, but some gaps remain. There is strong interest and partial readiness, though not all critical enablers are fully in place.
- 3 = Some stakeholders show availability for piloting, but important gaps exist. Willingness to participate in testing or preliminary activities is present, though broader implementation capacity or key actors may be lacking.
- 2 = Some interest expressed, but without concrete engagement. Preliminary signs of interest or general support, but no clear commitment or active involvement from stakeholders.
- 1 = No stakeholders are currently engaged or identified. Absence of expressed interest or participation from relevant stakeholders

Global scoring system:

Scoring:

- The regulatory aspects were given scores based on the UC level of compliance with the UC concept regulation and data regulation and with the barriers encountered at implementation level. The alignment with EU priorities has also been considered, based on the UC promotion of EU policies.
- The stakeholders' engagement aspects have been evaluated based on the replies given directly by stakeholders in polls shared by the BEGONIA consortium and based on the number of players already involved in piloting or fully engaged in each UC.

Weights:

- It has been decided to weight the different sub-criterion giving a total of 60% to regulatory aspects and 40% to stakeholder engagement ones.
- Regulatory aspects on general compliance of the concept, compliance of data-related regulations and alignment with EU strategic policies have been given the same weight of 20%.
- Stakeholder alignment has been given a higher weight (30%) with respect to Stakeholder support (10%) since more stakeholders will be motivated to actively engage for the actual implementation of the UCs once the last 3 are selected.

Table 49: Regulatory feasibility sub-criteria, scoring guides and weights

Sub-criterion	Description	Scoring guide	Weight (%)
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Regulatory alignment and compliance of the UC concept	Is the UC compliant with EU regulations with no barriers at its implementation (RED II, AFIR, eFTI...)	5 = Fully compliant, 3 = Minor issues or pending alignment, 1 = Major legal gaps	20
Regulatory alignment of the data management and sharing	Is the UC compliant with data EU regulation (ownership, access rights, and interoperability mechanisms) and does its present barriers at its implementation?	5 = Fully defined and aligned with EU Data Space standards, 3 = Some gaps, 1 = Unclear or lacking	20
Alignment with EU priorities	Does the use case align with and promote current EU digital and green transition policies (e.g. EU Green Deal, Digital Decade)?	5 = Fully aligned, 3 = Partially aligned, 1 = Misaligned or irrelevant	20
Stakeholder alignment	Have stakeholders (industry, public institutions, users) recognized the UC concept as relevant and shown interest in it?	5 = Broad interest and confirmed relevance of the concept, 3 = Partial interest or relevance, 1 = Little to no stakeholder interest	30
Stakeholder support for UC deployment	Does the UC already have some key stakeholders fully engaged to support its future implementation?	5 = One or more key stakeholders fully ready for deployment, 3 = Some gaps in stakeholders engaged and for piloting. 1 = No stakeholders present.	10

Table 49 presents the criteria, descriptions of each sub-criterion, and the scoring guide, for regulatory alignment and stakeholder readiness.

5.2. Summary results and discussions

Table 50 shows the final scores of the six Use Cases based on regulatory and stakeholder readiness. The total weighted scores indicate that UCII achieves the highest score (4.8), UCIII the second highest (4.70), and UCI and UCVI score equally (4.50).

Table 50: Sub-criterion and total weighted scores of UCs based on regulatory feasibility

Scores	
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Sub-criterion	Weights (%)	UCI	UCII	UCIII	UCIV	UCV	UCVI
Regulatory alignment and compliance of the UC concept	20	3	4	4	4	4	5
Regulatory alignment of the data management and sharing	20	5	5	5	5	4	4
Alignment with EU priorities	20	5	5	5	3	4	5
Stakeholder alignment	30	5	5	5	2	4	4
Stakeholder support for UC deployment	10	4	5	4	1	3	5
Total weighted score	100	4.50	4.80	4.70	3.10	3.90	4.50

The detailed explanations and justifications of each score abased on the five criteria are provided below.

Electricity customer-centric ODP

This platform empowers consumers to manage their energy consumption, switch suppliers, and participate in renewable energy markets. It aligns with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for secure and transparent data handling, the Electricity Market Directive (2019/944) for supplier switching and smart meter integration, and the Data Act (2023/2854) for fair access to energy-related data. The platform also complies with the Data Governance Act (2022/868), which ensures trustworthy data-sharing mechanisms.

Main challenges: Barriers exist in Member States, where independent aggregator frameworks are either underdeveloped or non-existent, limiting the platform's ability to facilitate flexibility services. Energy Communities' market participation has not been defined in all Member States and present various barriers in terms of cross-border implementation.

Stakeholder engagement considerations:

- *Alignment:* Significant interest expressed in the Use Case by contacted stakeholders.
- *Support for deployment:* Expressions of interest through survey replies to participate in tests and pilots.

AI-Driven ODP for EV, ET, RES and grid Integration

This platform optimizes EV/ET charging, grid flexibility, and RES integration using AI-driven technologies. It aligns with the Artificial Intelligence Act for high-risk AI systems, ensuring transparency, cybersecurity, and human oversight. The Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (2023/1804) supports widespread EV charging infrastructure deployment, while the Renewable Energy Directive (2018/2001) facilitates EV integration

into renewable energy systems. Additionally, the platform adheres to the Electricity Market Regulation (2019/943) for dynamic pricing and demand-side flexibility, and the NIS 2 Directive (2022/2555) for cybersecurity standards.

Main Challenge: A lack of harmonized flexibility markets across Member States, complicates implementation and cross-border scalability. The figure of the independent aggregator has not been established in all Member States.

Stakeholder engagement considerations:

- *Alignment:* Significant interest expressed in the Use Case by contacted stakeholders.
- *Support for deployment:* Key stakeholders already fully engaged and ready for deployment. Several expressions of interest through survey replies to participate in tests and pilots.

Digitalization of data centers

This UC aligns with the Data Governance Act (2022/868) for secure data-sharing, the Electricity Market Regulation (2019/943) for data center participation in balancing and capacity markets, and the Energy Efficiency Directive (2023/1791) for automated energy audits and demand-side efficiency. The Renewable Energy Directive (2018/2001) supports self-consumption and surplus trading for renewable energy.

Main Challenge: In some Member States, the absence of a regulatory framework for independent aggregators limits the ability of data centres to participate with this actor fully in energy markets.

Stakeholder engagement considerations:

- *Alignment:* Good interest expressed in the Use Case by contacted stakeholders.
- *Support for deployment:* Some key stakeholders engaged for deployment with a few gaps but expressions of interest through survey replies to participate in tests and pilots.

Digital permits for drone-based inspections

This UC streamlines the permitting process for drone-based inspections of infrastructure like pipelines and railways. It aligns with the Regulation (EU) 2019/947 on UAS Operations, which requires operational risk assessments and cross-border permit validation. The GDPR ensures privacy compliance for drone-collected data, while the Interoperable Europe Act (2024/903) supports interoperability between air traffic control systems. The eIDAS Regulation (2014/910) facilitates secure electronic identification for drone operators.

Main Challenge: National aviation laws, introduce operational constraints that complicate cross-border interoperability, despite alignment with overarching EU regulations. This UC

does not specifically promote some of the most relevant EU priorities, as an example of, the European Green Deal.

Stakeholder engagement considerations:

- *Alignment:* Little interest expressed in the Use Case by contacted stakeholders.
- *Support for deployment:* No significant interest expressed by stakeholders for UC implementation and piloting.

Smart port operations

This UC aligns with the European Maritime Single Window Environment Regulation (2019/1239), which ensures interoperability in maritime data reporting, the Data Act (2023/2854) for secure data-sharing, and the Artificial Intelligence Act for transparency and safety in high-risk AI systems. The platform also complies with the eFTI Regulation (2020/1056) for electronic freight transport information exchange.

Main challenges: Variations in national drone regulations and the need for technological interoperability among port stakeholders present hurdles to seamless implementation.

Stakeholder engagement considerations:

- *Alignment:* Some interest expressed in the UC by contacted stakeholders.
- *Support for deployment:* No key stakeholders fully engaged, only some availability for piloting has been expressed.

Carbon footprint of port supply chains

This UC aligns with the Digital Markets Act (2022/1925) to ensure fair competition and access to emissions data, the Data Governance Act (2022/868) for secure data-sharing frameworks, and the European Green Deal, which prioritizes reducing the environmental impact of logistics.

Main challenges: Ensuring seamless cross-border data sharing, particularly through blockchain-enabled transparency mechanisms, remains a challenge due to technical and legal barriers.

Stakeholder engagement considerations:

- *Alignment:* Good interest expressed in the Use Case by contacted stakeholders.
- *Support for deployment:* Some key stakeholders already fully engaged for piloting with a few gaps. Some expressions of interest for piloting from additional stakeholders through survey replies.

5.3. Governance model analysis

Deliverable D3.2 has performed an analysis for the six shortlisted UCs from a potential governance perspective. The goal of the analysis was to understand whether a viable governance model for an ODP exists to support each of the envisioned use cases.

A core part of the work has been a detailed stakeholder analysis, as a suitable governance model must ensure the stakeholders' various (potentially conflicting) needs and expectations are met and that promised services/resources are adequately provided and delivered. It also needs to ensure trust between participants and that the expected outcomes of the ODP are successfully met. The analysis considered each of the specific roles that the different stakeholder groups play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating. Starting from the proposed ODP services, Table 51 examines the relationship between the service and the identified stakeholder groups. Considering the stakeholder context, the analysis concluded with the proposal of a potentially suitable governance model for the ODP. Based on the analysis on governance feasibility, all UCs are feasible. Thus, no UC is disqualified based on governance feasibility.

Table 51: Summary of the proposed governance model for each UC

Use case	Governance model	ODP ownership	Feasibility	Governance model complexity and flexibility
UCI	Commercial model	Private for profit	Yes	Cross-border virtual energy communities face challenges due to national regulatory barriers Requires multiple national ODP platform instance per member state Complexities in market participation as not all member states allow independent aggregators
UCII	Commercial or non-for-profit	Private for profit entity or public special purpose vehicle	Yes	Both commercial; and non-for-profit models possible, although the latter is more likely as market opportunity is niche Strong regulatory environment requires ideally involvement of regulators in advisory boards
UCIII	Commercial or non-for profit	independent private sector entity	Yes	Both commercial; and non-for-profit models possible, although the latter is more likely as market opportunity is niche Strong regulatory environment requires ideally involvement of regulators in advisory boards
UCIV	Non-for-profit	Public neutral European entity	Yes	A nationally controlled or for-profit model would risk fragmentation, regulatory misalignment, and lack of trust, particularly in cross-border operations.

				Very high regulatory complexity particularly due to the sensitive nature of airspace management, flight approvals, and public infrastructure oversight
UCV	Non-for-profit	Publicly governed, Port Authority-managed to serve interest of all port stakeholders	Yes	For-profit structure controlled by a private entity would add an unnecessary additional layer to complex port operations and likely increase costs and the security of port operation Strong regulatory environment requires ideally involvement of regulators in advisory boards
UCVI	Commercial or non-for-profit	independent legal entity (e.g., association, cooperative, or foundation) or private sector	Yes	A for-profit structure, especially one controlled by a single stakeholder, would risk limiting the perceived neutrality and trust required for broad participation Strong regulatory environment requires a regulatory Advisory Board composed of representatives from EU regulatory bodies, national authorities in customs, transport, and data protection, as well as relevant standardisation organisations.

Table 51 also explains in detail the proposed governance model for each UC. As only one suitable governance model option has been examined for each UC, it is not possible to perform an in-depth comparative analysis across the UC. Nevertheless, some UCs have been found to be more complex regarding the overall governance arrangements, hence limiting the options for finding potentially viable governance model constellations. As such, two different dimensions can be considered for a comparative analysis of the governance model:

- *Complexity*: indicating how complex the governance of an ODP to support the UC is likely to be. Range: [(Very high (1), high (2), medium (3), low (4), very low (5)]

- *Flexibility*: indicates how flexible or limited ODP governance model options are likely to be for a particular UC. Range: [(Very low (1), low (2), medium (3), high (4), very high (5))].

5.4. Governance model assessment results

Table 52 presents the governance model dimensions from the perspectives of flexibility and complexity, along with each UC's assessment and overall scores. UCII and UCIII achieve the highest scores (4.0), while UCIV receives the lowest (2.0).

Table 52: Governance model assessment of UCs

Use case	Governance model dimensions	Assessment	Overall score
UCI	Flexibility	Medium (3)	2.50
	Complexity	High (2)	
UCII	Flexibility	Very high (5)	4.00
	Complexity	Medium (3)	
UCIII	Flexibility	Very high (5)	4.00
	Complexity	Medium (3)	
UCIV	Flexibility	Medium (3)	2.00
	Complexity	Very high (1)	
UCV	Flexibility	Medium (3)	3.00
	Complexity	Medium (3)	
UCVI	Flexibility	High (4)	3.50
	Complexity	Medium (3)	

6. Sectors integration

6.1. Scoring criteria and guides for sectors integration

In the ODP concept utilized in the BEGONIA project, different sectors manifest themselves as real-time or near real-time operations within the infrastructure for corresponding domains (energy, mobility, data). Therefore, the integration between sectors in specific UCs must be evaluated from the point of view of mutual interaction (coupling) of the domain operations that bring the change in the domain-specific system states. Such interaction must be considered when establishing the ODPs and often requires system innovation, e.g. (partial) conversion of legacy domain systems to hybrid or purely modern form. This analysis aims to evaluate the six UCs in terms of the diversity of involved sectors and the strength of the coupling among them. The three main sectors considered are: energy, mobility, and data. Data is selected as one of the involved sectors to highlight the importance of integrating a UC with data-related concepts and services, such as Data spaces.

Coupling can be investigated in three possibilities, i.e., Energy-data, Mobility-Data, and Energy-Mobility. The same importance and weight are assigned to each coupling possibility. Additionally, the scoring is done based on the strength of coupling as no-coupling or very weak (1), weak (2), medium (3), strong (4), and very strong (5).

Considering the analysis performed in Deliverable D3.1 and D3.2, a summary of the analysis performed on the six UCs is presented in Table 53. Since the same weight is assigned to each coupling, the final score is calculated as the average score over all coupling possibilities.

6.2. Results and discussions

Table 53 presents the evaluation of each Use Case based on energy data, mobility data and energy mobility. Then the results are discussed for each Use Case in relation to the coupling strength. Governance model assessment of UCs

Table 53: Cross-sector integration assessment of UCs

Use case	Sectors	Coupling strength	Overall score
UCI	Energy-Data	Very strong (5)	3.33
	Mobility-Data	Medium (3)	
	Energy-Mobility	Weak (2)	
UCII	Energy-Data	Strong (4)	4.33
	Mobility-Data	Very Strong (5)	
	Energy-Mobility	Strong (4)	
UCIII	Energy-Data	Very strong (5)	2.33
	Mobility-Data	No-coupling (1)	
	Energy-Mobility	No-coupling (1)	
UCIV	Energy-Data	No-coupling (1)	2.00
	Mobility-Data	Strong (4)	
	Energy-Mobility	No-coupling (1)	
UCV	Energy-Data	No-coupling (1)	2.00
	Mobility-Data	Strong (4)	
	Energy-Mobility	No-coupling (1)	
UCVI	Energy-Data	No-coupling (1)	1.66
	Mobility-Data	Medium (3)	
	Energy-Mobility	No-coupling (1)	

Electricity customers-centric ODP

The ODP for this Use Case focuses on real-time flexibility estimation and procurement operations within the mobility and energy sectors, and couples them in a potentially cross-border fashion through digital services aggregating the cross-sector flexibility:

1. Cloud infrastructure (*data sector*): the separation of the ownership of the federated and centralized (local and EU) services will be matched with both

- physical control of centralized (DSO level) and decentralized (consumers' CLs) assets.
2. Cloud infrastructure (*data sector*): the separation of the ownership of the federated and centralized (local and EU) services will be matched with both physical control of centralized (DSO level) and decentralized (consumers' CLs) assets.
 3. IIoT (*energy and mobility sectors*): gives user full control over their assets, irrespective of their location within the EU, giving them full responsibility over data transactions for their CLs. This data sharing is supported in the ODP by Data Spaces-backed services and federated control algorithms. EVs as a dominant energy consumer and a source of flexibility throughout the EU, become a primary CL enabling tight integration between the energy and mobility operations.
 4. DSO monitoring and decision support systems (*energy sector*) interacting with grid-related data services in the platform.
 5. 5G (*energy and mobility sector*): gives an opportunity for EV and other CL owners to monitor and control their devices (as well as use other services) from any point in the EU.
 6. Federated learning HPC (*energy and mobility sectors*): the hardware support for local management of virtual communities is a must for reliable operation of the energy-related infrastructure and allows tight coupling between the mobility and energy sectors.
 7. Data Spaces (*data sector*): The interaction between local operation services and global training models will be enabled both directly (using connectors for energy services and non-sensitive loads) and through Data Space deployments that manage third-party data, including CL and DSO data to comply with the EU and member state regulations, especially for cross-border data sharing.

For UCI, different virtual communities that themselves are constructed based on the described interaction between all three sectors are further coupled through potentially cross-border data (strong coupling at the EU level) and training services. These services preserve the structure of the physical ownership of the devices in how they handle data within the EU context. IIoT and 5G-based services enable strong coupling between energy and data and mobility and data.

AI-Driven ODP for EV, ET, RES and grid Integration

The ODP for this Use Case focuses on price estimation and modification of cross-border routing behavior while supporting renewable energy in the locations with large RES supply, which necessitates strong cooperation between the following services:

1. 5G and charge monitoring systems (*mobility*): since the SOC of the final charge, as well as other parameters, are controllable by a user and in turn modify their routing behavior, these technologies enable tight coupling with the energy sector as reflected in Table 53.
2. Federated learning HPC (*energy and mobility sectors*): The federated training enables region-specific charging prices. It uses local HPC infrastructure for energy management computations (and in some cases, control) that are location-specific and allows tight coupling between the mobility and energy sectors within and across member-states.
3. MLOps (*data sector*): The price estimation happens in a cross-border fashion (interacting through Data Spaces and federated HPC principle). Correspondingly, the local MLOps pipelines and infrastructure must be coupled to the global (EU-level) model that trains aggregated parameters.
4. Data Spaces (*data sector*): The routing information and geo-data must be accessible by the MLOps services based on EV data associated with the consumer's account credentials. It must comply with the EU and member state regulations, especially for cross-border data sharing.
5. Cloud infrastructure (*data sector*): the separation of the ownership of the federated and centralized (local and EU) services will be matched with both monitoring of centralized (energy and mobility, e.g. charging stations) and decentralized (mobility) assets.

UCII and its related services require a strong coupling between different sectors. While UCII provides a variety of energy services (e.g., load coordination, flexibility services, RES support) and mobility services (e.g., booking, charging station and routing), there are strong mutual impacts between energy and mobility services. In addition, both energy and mobility services rely significantly on data operations for providing data and AI-driven services.

Digitalization of data centers

The ODP for this Use Case brings together the following operational domains:

1. FinOps/GreenOps (*data sector*): Though the field has relatively high TRL, currently only hyperscale or US-owned data centers shift their computational loads between different TSO zones (data operations), in time (energy operations), and even within the same data center.
2. MLOps (*data sector*): The flexibility from data centers is operated and procured on two levels, local and cross-border (interacting through Data Spaces and federated HPC principle). Correspondingly, the local MLOps pipelines and infrastructure must be coupled to the global (EU-level) model that trains aggregated parameters.

3. Data Spaces (*data sector*): The interaction between local operational services and global training models will be enabled both directly (using connectors for MLOps services and non-sensitive loads) and through Data Space deployments that manage third-party data, including DC data, to comply with the EU and member state regulations.
4. DevOps infrastructure (*energy sector*): the actuation from FinOps will be implemented in the DCs, both local and cross-border.
5. District heating operations (*energy sector*): MLOps will be integrated with DCs decision support system, both local and cross-border.
6. Operations for fuel transport and utilization in flexible on-site generators: legacy and H2 generators will be operated directly from flexible services (MLOps, FinOps/GreenOps, GPU).
7. IoT (*energy and data sector*): The IoT is integrated with SCADA system (or replaces it in some data centers) to enable integration of energy/charging schedule optimizers.

The necessity for the strong coupling between energy and data operations in UCIII is related to the tendency for increasing DC density across the EU and the associated energy demand. This can only be achieved by using cross-sector flexibility for overcoming operational challenges imposed by recent EU regulations, which incentivize non-hyperscale data centers to operate sustainably within mid-voltage network constraints. Sector coupling through the ODP will allow EU-owned medium-sized, edge and modular DCs to increase their competitiveness and benefit DSOs/TSOs and RES businesses. The local services that drive energy operations for these stakeholders will be tightly coupled to FinOps/GreenOps operations through the proposed platform to produce new revenue streams. Current 0% DC flexibility utilization in the grid is a tradition that must be changed on a regulatory level, because it does not correspond to the reality of modern DCs.

Digital permits for drone-based inspections

ODP for this Use Case provides integration of data operation services with mobility operations through the following digitalization services:

1. Data Ingestion/Normalization (*data sector*): Processes data from drones, air traffic systems, and environmental agencies, ensuring consistency and compatibility.
2. API Gateway and Messaging Broker (*data sector*): Supports real-time data streaming, as well as secure communication between stakeholders.
3. Data Spaces (*data sector*): Gaia-X integration will enable EU-wide compliance with regulations for Data Sovereignty and Privacy Compliance within the mobility sector.

4. Permit management operations (*data sector*): the drones change the state of the permit management service (as well as DSS) and permit management service changes the state of the drones (disabling/disabling cross-border mobility) thereby creating strong coupling between the sectors.
5. Drone operations (*mobility sector*): used for inspection of the member states' infrastructure, e.g., roads, railways, power lines, and pipelines and changes the state based on the permit management decision from data sector.

Mobility influences data sector by drone mobility status changing the state of the permit management service thereby triggering the permit validation/issuing process. The data sector influences the mobility sector when permit management service, in its turn, changes the cross-border status of the drone by either issuing or retracting permits. The UC is mostly focused on the permits for drone operations at a cross-border level. In this regard, while the UC represents a strong coupling between the data and mobility sectors, we don't see data-energy and energy-mobility coupling.

Smart port operations

ODP for this Use Case enables coupling between the following services:

1. Data Spaces (*data sector*): FIWARE digital platform provides an opportunity for cross-border integration if the routing information belongs to different member states as ports are inherently cross-border representing the outermost regions.
2. Port notification system (*data sector*): Receives real-time updates on docking schedules, available resources, and any potential operational issues to facilitate inspections and compliance checks.
3. Drone fleet (*data sector*): They perform scheduled or on-demand missions to provide detailed insights into operational and environmental conditions, enabling moderate coupling to the mobility sector. Captured imagery is used to calculate stockpile volumes for resources such as coal, gravel, or containers stored in the port.
4. Port monitoring systems with IoT (*data sector*): the ODP complements the legacy monitoring systems on docks and transport with modern digital operations, thereby enabling moderate coupling with the transport sector. The advanced monitoring includes AI cameras, drones, and IoT. Additionally, the feedforward is implemented in a decision-support manner that includes, e.g., inspections, compliance checks, and failure prevention.
5. Geolocation systems (*data sector*): These systems include Global Positioning System (GPS) for vehicle tracking and actuators for controlling port equipment, such as cranes, gates, conveyors, enabling precise and automated operations. Due to the real-time actuation control of the in-house equipment, the ODP provides a strong coupling with the logistic mobility sector.
6. Logistic supply chain (**mobility sector**): operations of logistic components (cranes, gates, conveyors, etc.) are sensed, evaluated and optimized in real-time (data sector)

and the actuation signal is generated for each component to accelerate the logistics supply chain enabling strong coupling with the data sector.

7. Real-time control system (**data and mobility sector**): acts on logistics components (mobile sector) by applying the actuation signals and thereby changing their state to improve the mobility of goods.

In UCV, there is a strong coupling between the data and mobility sectors. The data collected from cameras, drones, and ships is evaluated in the platform using AI, and optimal decisions regarding the management and coordination of ships and resources are made. Due to the importance of mobility-related services, energy does not play a role in this use case. Hence, there is no data-energy and energy-mobility coupling in this UC.

Carbon footprint of port supply chains

ODP for this Use Case enables coupling between the following UCVI operational services:

1. Data Spaces (*data sector*): Data Space adaptors provide an opportunity for cross-border integration if the routing information belongs to different member states or different companies than the one that is being monitored by the ODP.
2. CF Calculation and Route Optimization Microservices (*data sector*): optimizes the transport routes for logistics operators, ensuring that the most carbon-efficient and cost-effective routes are selected for goods transport. This microservice utilizes real-time data such as traffic conditions, fuel prices, and weather information, along with the CF data generated by the CF Calculation Microservice, to provide actionable recommendations, thereby enabling moderate coupling with the mobility sector.
3. Blockchain technology (*data sector*) allows monitoring and verification of the full supply chain attached to the ports, enabling moderate coupling to the mobility sector.
4. Transport- and CO₂-monitoring systems (*mobility sector*): The monitored systems include ships, trucks, and port equipment. The components of the port supply chain (mobility sector) are monitored and analyzed by the ODP through CO₂-estimation services, maintaining reliable CF label (security and reliability data) and optimizing CO₂, thereby changing the state of the data components. Based on the collected information (CO₂-related services, data sector), the ship operator has an opportunity to influence the routing of the ships. There is, however, no direct influence of the data services on the states within the mobility sector.

UCVI is only focused on the collection and analysis of data for tracking and managing carbon emissions in logistics. The use case has no coupling with the energy sector. While there are impacts from the mobility sector on the data sector by collecting and analyzing the carbon emission data, this data collection does not have a short-term impact on the mobility sector. So, the strength of coupling is scored as medium.

7. Comparative analysis of Use Cases

7.1. Methodology

We adopt a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) approach to systematically evaluate the six UCs. MCDA provides a structured framework for comparing heterogeneous options against multiple objectives in parallel [5]. In our context, the approach simplifies and rationalizes decision-making by incorporating technical, governance and policy, economic and strategic considerations in a transparent manner. A set of evaluation criteria was defined and agreed ex ante, ensuring that the assessment criteria cover all relevant dimensions of feasibility [6]. The MCDA methodology thereby enables an evidence-based ranking of UCs, supporting a justification for subsequent policy recommendations. In this feasibility study, five key criteria were used to appraise each UC: (1) Economic feasibility, which evaluates the profitability and cost-effectiveness of investment, the level of financial difficulty, and risk/sensitivity resilience; (2) Technical feasibility, which examines the technological maturity, interoperability and scalability of the solution; (3) Regulatory and stakeholders readiness, which assesses UCs alignment with existing EU regulatory frameworks, and legal compliance across borders; (4) Governance model assessment, which analyzes the governance model dimension from flexibility and complexity perspectives; and (5) Relevance and cross-sector integration, which measures the degree to which the UC enables synergies between the energy and transport sectors and adds value through sector integration. These criteria reflect widely accepted dimensions for evaluating innovative urban energy and transport infrastructure investment projects [7]. Technical, economic and regulatory viability are frequently identified as fundamental pillars of feasibility in the energy and transport domain, while cross-sector integration is included to capture strategic relevance in achieving EU policy goals (e.g. energy and mobility sector coupling for decarbonization). Indeed, cross-sectoral linkages are increasingly recognized as a cost-effective strategy to enhance system flexibility and impact [8], so this relevance criterion ensures that UCs supporting integrated energy-transport solutions are scored favorably. Each criterion was clearly defined with objective sub-indicators before scoring, following best practices to ensure a coherent and non-overlapping set of metrics. For each UC, a quantitative scoring of weighted sub-criteria is applied for each type of feasibility. This approach aligns with evaluation practices used in EU programs [8] and provides sufficient granularity to differentiate degrees of feasibility. However, each feasibility analysis has its own specific characteristics, with tailored scoring and ranking approaches described in their respective sections. Most importantly, the total scores, ranging from 1 to 5, are essential for the final ranking of the six UCs.

7.2. Evaluation of the cross-border aspect

The cross-border aspect of a Use Case increases the relevance of ODPs for EU-wide implementation. However, the economic and financial feasibility assessments of the UCs are based on country-specific assumptions regarding prices, costs, and market characteristics, even for UCs with a cross-border scope. For example, UCI, UCII, and UCIII operate within the broader framework of the EU electricity market, incorporating mechanisms such as zonal pricing and virtual energy communities. These elements inherently involve cross-border dynamics, although they are not explicitly modelled.

Table 54 summarizes the geographic scope of each UC, showing that all except UCV involve multiple countries. These multi-country UCs rely on shared infrastructure, regulatory harmonization, or integrated mobility and energy strategies, which can be enhanced through ODP implementation. By applying national-level inputs to each participating country, the CBA captures variations in cost-efficiency, environmental valuation, and feasibility across borders.

While some UCs reflect country-wide implementations, particularly in the electricity and mobility sectors, others are localized, such as those focused on smart port operations and logistics. Cross-border relevance was not used as a scoring criterion in the evaluation. However, the highest-scoring UCs tend to benefit from inherent cross-country integration, suggesting that the value of cross-border coordination is embedded in the cost-benefit analysis.

Table 54: Cross-border nature of Use Cases

Use Case	Countries involved	Cross-border nature
UCI	DE, SE, DK	YES
UCII	AT, HU, SI	YES
UCIII	DE, SE, DK	YES
UCIV	FR, ES, PT	YES
UCV	ES	NO
UCVI	ES, PT	YES

7.3. Results and discussions

Table 55 presents the summary results of each UC from all the feasibility analyses and the *Base Scenario* weights (%) assigned to each feasibility analysis.

Table 55: Summary scores of each UC based on the feasibility analyses along the weights

Feasibility	Use Cases						
	Weights (%)	UCI	UCII	UCIII	UCIV	UCV	UCVI
Economic feasibility	35.00	3.65	2.60	3.50	2.00	1.80	2.45
Technical feasibility	20.00	3.23	4.25	2.95	2.45	4.37	3.05
Regulatory & stakeholder readiness	12.50	4.50	4.80	4.70	3.10	3.90	4.50
Governance model assessment	12.50	2.50	4.40	4.40	2.00	3.00	3.50
Relevance & cross-sector integration	20.00	3.33	4.33	2.33	2.00	2.00	1.66

A weighted aggregation was then performed to compute the final score for each UC, as shown in Table 56. We consider this as the *Base Scenario*. The table shows the performance of the UCs across the five feasibility dimensions. The radar chart in Figure 32 visually represents the strengths and weaknesses of each UC, making it easier to compare their overall feasibility profiles. The analysis reveals that the first three UCs (UCI, UCII and UCIII) demonstrates the strongest overall performance. Conversely, UCIV shows the lowest overall feasibility scores, particularly in technical, regulatory and governance model, suggesting significant challenges in implementation or cross-sector applicability. UUV and UCVI also show relatively modest scores, with notable gaps in areas such as economic, technical and cross-sector relevance. We also consider a scenario (*Equal-Weight Scenario*) where the five feasibility dimensions are considered to have equal strategic importance and are therefore weighted equally, each contributing 20% to the total score.

Table 56 presents the final weighted scores of each UC based on each feasibility analysis of the *Base Scenario*, where we assigned greater weight to economic feasibility (35%). The result shows that the first three UCs (*UCI, UCII, and UCIII*) are the top three UCs from piloting based on the employed MCDA framework. However, it should be noted even in the *Equal-Weight Scenario*, the final ranking of the Use Cases does not change, only the scores are changed.

Table 56: Weighted final scores of each UC based on each feasibility analysis

Feasibility analysis	UCI	UCII	UCIII	UCIV	UCV	UCVI
Economic feasibility	1.28	0.91	1.23	0.70	0.63	0.88
Technical feasibility	0.65	0.85	0.59	0.49	0.87	0.61

Regulatory & stakeholder readiness	0.56	0.60	0.59	0.39	0.49	0.56
Governance model assessment	0.31	0.55	0.55	0.25	0.38	0.44
Relevance & cross-sector integration	0.67	0.87	0.47	0.40	0.40	0.33
Final weighted scores	3.46	3.78	3.42	2.23	2.77	2.80
Final rank of the UC	2	1	3	6	5	4

Figure 32: Use Case feasibility performance radar charts (scores: 1–5)

7.4. Recommendations of the final three UCs for pilot deployment

The applied MCDA framework is grounded in established evaluation literature and EU methodology guidelines. Similar multi-criteria frameworks have been applied in prior

studies to ensure that technological readiness, regulatory context, market viability and cross-sector benefits are collectively considered when comparing innovation options. By scoring each criterion on a standardized scale and combining them through weighted aggregation, the methodology yields a performance profile for each UC that is both quantitative and easy to interpret. Then the final scores for each UC calculated based on the weights assigned to each feasibility analysis and validated them with a Base Scenario, giving equal weights for each feasibility analysis. The outcome is a rigorous comparative evaluation of the UC' feasibility and relevance, grounded in a consistent decision-analytic approach. Accordingly, we recommend the following three UCs based on their ranks:

- 1) UCII: AI-driven ODP for the integration of EVs, ET, RES, and the grid
- 2) UCI: Electricity customers centric ODP
- 3) UCIII: Digitalization of data centers

8. Conclusions

Deliverable 3.3 has enabled the project team to conduct an in-depth cost-benefit analysis and assess the relevance and cross-sectoral importance of the six UCs within the Begonia project. Additionally, it provided an opportunity to revisit and build upon the technical, regulatory and stakeholder, and governance feasibility assessments previously addressed in Deliverables 3.1 and 3.2, leading to a comprehensive ranking of the six UCs. The results presented in this Deliverable are robust and rigorous, grounded in multiple feasibility studies that draw on data and materials from earlier deliverables, supplemented by fresh analysis. This comprehensive approach allows us to confidently recommend the most feasible UCs (the first three UCs) for piloting and implementation, along with a recommendation to conduct a detailed evaluation of their potential within their respective piloting countries.

9. References

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10. Appendices

Table 57 presents general assumptions used to calculate cost and benefits for all Use Cases. All ODPs are calculated for ten years lifetime in their respective countries and all future monetary values are discounted with 4% discount rate.

Table 57: General assumptions for all Use Cases

Parameter	Unit	Value	Remarks
Project duration	Years	10	From 2026 to 2035
Discount rate	%	4	Used for net present value (NPV) calculations ¹⁸
Calculation year (price basis)	Year	2025	All monetary values are in 2025 euros
ODP deployment start year	Year	2026	Full implementation begins
ODP deployment end year	Year	2035	Benefits calculated over this period

Appendix A1: Supplementary materials for cost-benefits analysis of UCI

Below are the proposed assumptions, categorized into general assumptions, economic and market assumptions, and technology-specific assumptions.

Assumptions for costs and benefits calculations

Tables 58 and 59 present the main assumptions considered in our quantitative analysis of costs and benefits for UCI.

Table 58: Country specific assumptions for UCI

Parameter	Unit	DE	SE	DK	Remarks
Total number of households (H_{tot})	Millions	84.2	10.6	5.9	2025 population data
Average annual electricity consumption per household (EE_{TOT})	kWh	6,500	6,500	6,500	Based on historical data and projected trends. ¹⁹

¹⁸ Project duration and discount rate: The discount rate of 4% is based on widely accepted economic and policy recommendations for energy investments in Europe. It accounts for time value of money in net present value (NPV) calculations. The NPV is calculated as $NPV = \sum_t^T \frac{FV_t}{(1+r)^t} - C_o$, where FV_t is the cash flow in the current year t and C_o is the upfront cost.

¹⁹ Data is derived from historical records and national statistics of Germany, Sweden, and Denmark, considering projected efficiency improvements from smart metering and energy management systems. However, for the sake of calculation we consider the average 6500kWh/year per household for all countries. A household is considered a family of five persons. Then we took the current (2025) population data of each country and construct a household table of all countries. We do not consider population growth for the 10-year life horizon of the project.

Average annual kilometers driven per vehicle (km_{year})	km	13,000	12,000	11,000	Considering urban and rural differences.
Average CO ₂ emissions per km for fossil-fueled vehicles (tonne_{CO2/km,ff})	g/km	120	110	115	Based on national vehicle emission standards.
Average CO ₂ emissions per km for electric vehicles (tonne_{CO2/km,EV})	g/km	60	50	55	Considering the electricity generation mix of each country.
Average CO ₂ emissions per km for electric trucks (tonne_{CO2/km,ET})	g/km	80	70	75	Considering the electricity generation mix of each country.
Equivalent full-load hours for RES (h_{eq})	hours/year	1,800	2,000	1,900	Average annual full-load hours for renewable energy sources.
Current RES capacity	GW	63,500	50,000	8,000	As of 2024 for Germany; estimates for Sweden and Denmark.
Projected annual growth rate of RES capacity	%	5	4	6	Based on national energy plans and historical trends. ²⁰
Current number of EVs	Millions	1.38	0.5	0.3	As of 2021 for Germany estimates for Sweden and Denmark ²¹
Projected annual growth rate of EVs	%	6.75	8.83	1.65	STATISTA
Projected annual growth rate of ETs	%	6.75	8.83	1.65	Assumed they have the same rate as EVs
Average electricity tariff (t_e)	€/kWh	0.12	0.13	0.14	Country-specific average tariffs

²⁰ Growth rates for RES capacity are derived from national energy transition plans (e.g., Germany's Energiewende, Sweden's Fossil-Free 2040, and Denmark's Climate Plan 2030).

²¹ The projected growth of ETs is based on policy targets, market trends, and European automotive industry forecasts.

CO ₂ emission price (PCO_2)	€/tonne	50	60	55	Based on national carbon pricing mechanisms
Air pollutant emission value (P_{AP})	€/tonne	10,000	9,000	9,500	Calculated based on this source
Number of EV charging stations installed in the ODP scenario (CS)	Count	10,000	5,000	3,000	Existing and planned installations during the project period
Proportion of EV demand shifted to off-peak hours (EV_{shift})	%	2.50	2.80	2.60	Expected ODP impact
Proportion of ET demand shifted to off-peak hours (ET_{shift})	%	2.50	2.80	2.60	Due to ODP-enabled smart scheduling
Share of RES self-consuming within the household (RES_{self})	%	4.00	4.50	4.20	Enhanced by ODPs and virtual energy communities
Households actively participating in virtual energy trading ($VEC_{engaged}$)	%	2.00	2.50	2.20	Enabled by ODP platforms.
Cost per MW of peak demand avoided (C_{MW})	€/MW	125.57	109.93	125.62	Taken from EPEX spot prices ²²
Total time energy saved per charging & transaction event (S_T)	%	5	5	5	Due to ODP-enabled optimizations
Energy efficiency Improvement from ODPs ($\%EE_{ODP}$)	%	3	4	3.5	Based on smart metering, demand optimization
Transaction cost reduction from ODPs ($\%TC_{reduction}$)	%	10	10	10	Includes smart metering & billing automation
Load reduction in Peak Load from ODPs ($\%LR$)	%	15	14	13	ODP-driven grid balancing
Curtailment Reduction Enabled by ODPs ($\%CR$)	%	5	6	4.5	ODP-driven RES flexibility
CO ₂ displacement per MWh of RES Generation (ERS_{factor})	tonne CO ₂ /MWh	0.4	0.38	0.42	Country-specific energy mix

²² Cost per MW of peak demand is taken from EPEX Sport price of March 14, 2025, for all countries and calculated as 10% this as costs could be avoided using ODP enhanced demand response program.

CO ₂ emissions per km for fossil-fuel vehicles (ERS_{factor,ff})	tonne CO ₂ /km	0.12	0.11	0.115	
CO ₂ emissions per km for EVs (ERS_{factor,EV})	tonne CO ₂ /km	0.06	0.05	0.055	
CO ₂ emissions per km for ETs (ERS_{factor,ET})	tonne CO ₂ /km	0.08	0.07	0.075	
Air pollutant reduction per MWh of RES generation (tonne_{AP/MWh})	tonne CO ₂ /km	0.0025	0.0022	0.0024	Based on grid intensity
Air Pollutant Reduction from EV & ET Adoption (tonne_{AP/km})	tonne CO ₂ /km	0.0015	0.0012	0.0013	

Table 59: Key technology-specific assumptions for UCI

Technology	Metric	With ODP	justification	Source
EV sensors	Battery life improvement	12%	AI-optimized charging extends battery longevity	Journal paper
	Grid peak load savings	€365/EV/year	Smart charging reduces peak grid load	https://www.neso.energy/
ET sensors	Battery life improvement	12%	AI optimizes charge-discharge cycles	Journal paper
	Fleet fuel savings	+€500/ET/year	AI-enhanced route and charge optimization	Fleet Report
RES sensors	Curtailed avoidance	5%	AI improves renewable energy forecasting	https://www.irena.org/
	Fossil fuel savings	10%	Increased RES integration reduces fuel dependency	https://www.irena.org/
	RES capacity installed from 2026-2035	Projected	Austria to reach 100% & Hungary to 90%	Country plans
Adaptive environmental sensors	Grid forecasting accuracy	+10%	Integrated sensing improves energy demand prediction	
Weather forecasting sensors	Renewable generation prediction accuracy	+8%	Improves energy scheduling & demand-supply matching	
	Peak load reduction	15%	Smart algorithms reduce grid strain	https://www.neso.energy/

AI Grid load optimization ²³				
Route optimization for EVs	Distance reduction	-10%/ trip	AI improves trip efficiency	https://www.here.com/
	Fleet fuel savings	€500/vehicle/year	Less energy wasted per trip	Fleet Report
Route optimization for ETs	Distance reduction	-8%/trip	AI optimizes heavy transport routes	-
Charging navigation & mobile Apps	Charging cost savings	-5%/ kWh	Smart charging optimizes cost-efficiency	
Smart meters & automated billing	Transaction cost reduction	-10%	Reduces manual processing, fraud, and errors	
Virtual energy community (VEC) management	Household participation increase	+25%	AI encourages active market participation	
AI-based demand response	Load shifting efficiency	+20%	Dynamic pricing adjusts consumption	
Smart home integrations	Energy self-sufficiency improvement	+15%	Reduces dependency on grid supply	
Financial settlement tools	Billing automation efficiency	+30%	Smart contracts and AI reduce transaction errors	
Data integration & ETL tools	Energy trading efficiency increase	+20%	AI optimizes virtual market trades	

Presentation of CAPEX and OPEX tables

Tables 60 and 61 present the miscellaneous and incremental CAPEX, respectively. Tables 63 and 64 present the total labor cost and miscellaneous OPEX for the first year,

²³ Imbalance reduction with ODP (3%), Market price forecasting accuracy improvement (5%), Market participation increases due to ODP (5%), Price optimization from ODP (2%), Increase in DR participation (5%), Time reduction per charge (15%), Market accuracy improvement (5%).

respectively. Meanwhile, Tables 62 and 65 present the total CAPEX and total OPEX, respectively.

Table 60: Miscellaneous CAPEX for UCI

Component	Unit Cost (€)	Quantity	Total Cost (€)	Remarks
Grid forecasting sensors	5,000	Per deployment (10)	50,000	AI-based dynamic grid optimization
Weather forecasting Sensors	10,000	Per deployment (10)	100,000	For renewable forecasting
VEC management software	50,000	Per country	150,000	AI model for trading
AI grid optimization software	500,000	Per country	1,500,000	AI model for demand response
Data integration & ETL tools	200,000	Per country	600,000	Optimizing trade, bills, and transaction costs
Charging navigation & mobile apps	100,000	Per country	300,000	Helps EV owners find optimized charging routes
Financial settlement & smart contracts	250,000	Per country	750,000	Automates energy trading & billing verification
Battery storage participation infrastructure	1,000,000	Per country	3,000,000	Smart battery storage for flexibility markets
Comprehensive analytics tools	1,000,000	Per country	3,000,000	Central visualization suite
Admin dashboard	1,000,000	Per country	3,000,000	Control platform
Total upfront cost			39,450,000	

Table 61: Sensors CAPEX for UCI

Year	Smart meters and billing systems (€)	RES sensors (€)	EV sensors (€)	ET sensors (€)
2026	10,082,755	1,270,335	1,778,125	5,210
2027	20,165,510	1,329,561	1,906,472	5,593
2028	30,248,265	1,391,590	2,044,444	6,006
2029	40,331,020	1,456,559	2,192,779	6,451
2030	50,413,775	1,524,608	2,352,273	6,930

2031	60,496,530	1,595,887	2,523,785	7,445
2032	70,579,285	1,670,550	2,708,240	8,001
2033	80,662,040	1,748,762	2,906,637	8,599
2034	90,744,795	1,830,693	3,120,053	9,243
2035	100,827,550	1,916,523	3,349,648	9,938
Sub total	554,551,520	15,735,067	24,882,455	73,416
Total Discounted				572,348,517

Note: smart meters and billing systems are based on the integrated household with unit cost of (€200 but we consider only 5% of it as the cost due to ODP integration), EV sensor unit price €50, RES sensor €50 and ET sensor €75 as the existing system has no these sensors.

Table 62: CAPEX for UCI

CAPEX category	Values (€)
Total upfront cost	39,450,000
Discounted CAPEX over the ten years	572,348,517
Total CAPEX	611,798,517

Table 63: Labor costs for UCI

Category	DE	SE	DK	Total	Ave. salary (€)	Total (€)
Data analytics and maintenance	22	14	10	46	50,000	2,300,000
EV/ET deployment and traffic monitoring	10	7	5	22	48,000	1,056,000
AI models energy and grid optimization	15	10	8	33	55,000	1,815,000
ODP software development and cybersecurity	12	8	6	26	60,000	1,560,000
Labor cost in the first year	59	39	29	127		6,731,000

Table 64: OPEX for each country in the first year for UCI

Category	Cost components	GR (€)	SE (€)	DK(€)	Source
Cloud computing & data processing	AI model retraining, real-time data analytics	3,500,000	2,500,000	1,800,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Software maintenance & updates	Patches, security updates, AI bug fixes	1,500,000	1,200,000	900,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report

Grid & sensor maintenance	Firmware updates, performance monitoring	2,800,000	2,000,000	1,500,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Cybersecurity & threat monitoring	Penetration testing, intrusion detection	2,200,000	1,800,000	1,400,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report
Customer support & data analytics	AI-driven reports, operator support	1,500,000	1,000,000	900,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
TSO/DSO & energy market integration	Regulatory compliance, market fees	2,500,000	2,000,000	1,800,000	ACER Market Integration Report
Grid expansion & new EV/ET integrations	New EV charging stations, grid enhancements	3,000,000	2,500,000	2,200,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report
Network maintenance (5G/LPWAN)	Upkeep of connectivity infrastructure	2,800,000	2,200,000	1,900,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Virtual energy community (VEC) integration	Participation in wholesale trading	1,500,000	1,300,000	1,000,000	ACER Market Integration Report
Miscellaneous costs	Hardware replacements, training, compliance	1,800,000	1,400,000	1,100,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)		23,100,000	17,900,000	13,500,000	-

Table 65: OPEX for UCI

OPEX category	Values (€)
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)	54,500,000
Labor cost in in the first year	6,731,000
Total discounted OPEX over ten years	516,503,789

Appendix A2: Supplementary materials for cost-benefits analysis of UCII

Assumptions for costs and benefits calculations

Tables 66, 67 and 68 present the main assumptions considered in our quantitative analysis of costs and benefits for UCII.

Table 66: Economic and market assumptions for EVs in UCII

Parameter	AT	HU	SI	Source
Annual EV growth rate (CAGR 2026-2035)	16.01%	17.96%	15.5%	Austria (STATISTA) Hungary (STATISTA) Slovenia (STATISTA)
RES capacity growth (2026-2035)	664 MW/year	2,750 MW/year	150 MW/year	International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA)
Initial EV fleet (2026)	343, 803	100,820	50,000	STATISTA
Annual charging sessions per EV	250	250	250	National EV reports
Electricity price for EV charging (€ / kWh)	€0.18	€0.17	€0.16	Eurostat
Battery lifespan extension (%)	12%	12%	12%	MDPI Journal
Electricity price (RES Generation) (€ / kWh)	€0.15	€0.14	15%	Eurostat

Table 67: Economic and market assumptions for ETs in UCII

Parameter	AT	HU	SI	Source
Annual ET growth rate (2026-2035)	12.97%	12.97%	10.5%	IEA Transport Outlook
Initial ET fleet (2026)	4,400	400	300	National vehicle registries
Annual charging sessions per ET	400	400	400	Industry reports
Electricity price for ET charging (€/kWh)	€0.20	€0.20	€19	Eurostat
Fleet fuel savings/ ET (€/year)	€500	€500	€500	

Data on the initial number of EVs, ETs and their growth rate are sourced from STATISTA, which indicates a significant increase in recent years in both countries. This trend is expected to continue with substantial investments in EV and ET adoptions. All countries have set ambitious targets for greening their energy consumption by 2030. However, considering the current growth rates of RES, EVs, ETs, we assume that this trend will continue at the same rate until 2035, allowing us to base our calculations on observed data trends.

Table 68: Key technology-specific assumptions for UCII

Technology	Metric	With ODP	justification	Source
EV sensors	Battery life improvement	12%	AI-optimized charging extends battery longevity	MDPI Journal

	Grid peak load savings	€365/EV/year	Smart charging reduces peak grid load	https://www.neso.energy/
ET sensors	Battery life improvement	12%	AI optimizes charge-discharge cycles	MDPI Journal
	Fleet fuel savings	+€500/ET/year	AI-enhanced route and charge optimization	Fleet Report
RES sensors	Curtailement avoidance	5%	AI improves renewable energy forecasting	https://www.irena.org/
	Fossil fuel savings	10%	Increased RES integration reduces fuel dependency	https://www.irena.org/
	RES capacity installed from 2026-2035	-	Austria to reach 100% & Hungary to 90%	Country plans
Adaptive environmental sensors	Grid forecasting accuracy	+10%	Integrated sensing improves energy demand prediction	
AI Grid load optimization ²⁴	Peak load reduction	15%	Smart algorithms reduce grid strain	https://www.neso.energy/
Route optimization for EVs	Distance reduction	10%/ trip	AI improves trip efficiency	https://www.here.com/
	Fleet fuel savings	€500/vehicle/year	Less energy wasted per trip	Fleet Report
Route optimization for ETs	Distance reduction	10%/trip	AI optimizes heavy transport routes	-
Charging Navigation & Mobile Apps	Charging cost savings	5%/ kWh	Smart charging optimizes cost-efficiency	

Presentation of CAPEX and OPEX tables

Tables 69 and 70 present the incremental CAPEX for sensors, and onetime CAPEX for different technologies, respectively. Tables 72 and 73 present labor costs and other

²⁴ Imbalance reduction with ODP (3%), Market price forecasting accuracy improvement (5%), Market participation increase due to ODP (5%), Price optimization from ODP (2%), Increase in DR participation (5%), Time reduction per charge (15%), Market accuracy improvement (5%).

miscellaneous OPEX for the first year, respectively. Meanwhile, Tables 71 and 74 present the total CAPEX and total OPEX, respectively for completeness.

Table 69: Incremental CAPEX for sensor for UCII

Year	RES (MW)	EVs	ETs	EV Sensors	ET Sensors	RES Sensors
2026	39,943	557,541	5,861	53,609,673	2,817,788	192,035,173
2027	2,084	70,948	875	6,821,956	420,476	10,018,426
2028	2,195	80,007	1,005	7,692,986	483,240	10,551,105
2029	2,311	90,226	1,155	8,675,541	555,377	11,112,954
2030	2,435	101,753	1,328	9,783,936	638,284	11,704,475
2031	2,564	114,757	1,526	11,034,322	733,572	12,328,417
2032	2,701	129,427	1,754	12,444,932	843,909	12,986,183
2033	2,845	145,978	2,015	14,036,342	968,962	13,679,635
2034	2,997	164,650	2,316	15,831,773	1,113,633	14,410,737
2035	3,158	185,717	2,662	17,857,439	1,279,910	15,181,563
Sub total	63,234	1,641,005	20,497	157,788,900	9,854,332	304,008,309
Total						471, 651, 541

The initial year (2026) incurs the highest costs²⁵, as all existing EVs, ETs, and RES units require sensor installations to enable seamless connectivity and data exchange with the ODPs. From 2027 onward, the CAPEX requirements decrease, as only newly added EVs, ETs, and RES units need sensor installations, leading to a gradual reduction in yearly expenditures.

Table 70: One-time CAPEX for different technologies

Component	Unit cost (€)	Quantity	(€)
Adaptive environmental sensors	10,000/site	200 key locations	20,000,000

²⁵ EVs and ETs are equipped with a variety of sensors that monitor and control different aspects of the vehicle's performance and safety. These sensors include current sensors, temperature sensors, position sensors, pressure sensors, speed sensors, LiDAR sensors, radar sensors, and image sensors. Each sensor serves a unique function, such as measuring battery health, regulating motor torque, or assisting with navigation and obstacle detection (https://prostech.vn/types-of-ev-sensors-and-its-features/?utm_source=chatgpt.com). Most of the sensors are included in EVs and ETs. A single EV could have up to 100 sensors. The cost of these sensors varies, with temperature sensors priced around €18 and LiDAR Sensors up to €200 on Amazon and there is a plan to reduce them (https://www.reuters.com/technology/chinas-hesai-halve-lidar-prices-next-year-sees-wide-adoption-electric-cars-2024-11-27/?utm_source=chatgpt.com). Most importantly, most sensors are available in existing EVs and ETs. For our analysis, we assume the operational platform requires additional cost of sensors with average price of €100 for EVs and €500 for ETs.

Weather forecasting sensors	20,000/unit ²⁶	60 meteorological sites	1,200,000
Connectivity infrastructure (5G/LPWAN)	100,000/ region	30 deployment zones	3,000,000
Communication protocols & message queues	1 million	3 integrated system	3,000,000
Databases & data lakes	1 million	3 (one per country)	3,000,000
Data integration middleware	1.5 million	3 integration system	4,500,000
API management	1.5 million	3 platform-wide	4,500,000
Market integration middleware	1.5 million	3 market-trading integration	4,500,000
AI models for grid optimization	5 million	3 comprehensive model	15,000,000
Demand response tools	2 million	3 system	6,000,000
Route optimization engines	3 million	3 system	9,000,000
Weather forecasting algorithms	1 million	3 AI-enhanced model	3,000,000
End-user mobile application	0.3 million	3 mobile app	900,000
Charging navigation systems	1 million	3 navigation system	3,000,000
Comprehensive analytics tools	1 million	3 central visualization suite	3,000,000
Admin dashboard	1 million	3 control platform	3,000,000
Software deployment & integration	1million	3 end-to-end integration	3,000,000
Miscellaneous CAPEX			89,000,000

The miscellaneous costs encompass key areas such as platform development and AI training, which include software development and cloud infrastructure setup to enable core AI functionalities.

Table 71: CAPEX for UCII

CAPEX category	Values (€)
Discounted CAPEX over ten years	471, 651, 541
Miscellaneous fixed CAPEX	89,000,000
Total CAPEX	561,251,541

²⁶ Considering Coda Sensors Automatic Weather Station, Radar Weather Stations, we assume €20,000 per metrological location to have complete sensors in a single metrological location that uses to apply the planned ODPs. For specialized weather station sensor prices check this website (https://www.codasensor.com/automatic-weather-station-cost.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com).

Table 72: Labor cost for UCII

Category	AT	HU	SI	Total	Average Salary (€)	Total (€)
Data analytics and maintenance	14	13	10	37	47,500	1,757,500
EV/ET deployment and traffic monitoring	5	3	3	11	44,000	484,000
AI-based energy and grid optimization	10	5	4	19	55,000	1,045,000
ODP software development and cybersecurity	5	3	3	11	60,000	660,000
Labor cost in the first year	34	24	20	78		3,946,500

Table 73: OPEX for the first year of UCII

Category	Cost Components	AT (€)	HU(€)	SI (€)	Source
Cloud computing & data processing	Cloud hosting (AWS, Azure, Google Cloud), API calls, AI model retraining, and real-time data processing	2,000,000	1,500,000	1,300,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Software maintenance & updates	Regular software patches, AI model retraining, security updates, bug fixes	1,000,000	1,000,000	700,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report
Grid & sensor maintenance	Firmware updates, sensor replacements, performance monitoring of RES, EVs, ETs, and adaptive environmental sensors	1,800,000	1,000,000	600,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Cybersecurity & threat monitoring	Annual penetration testing, firewalls, intrusion detection, identity access management	2,000,000	1,200,000	1,200,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report
Customer support & data analytics	Running analytics dashboards, AI-driven reports, customer and grid operator support	1,000,000	800,000	500,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
TSO/DSO & energy market integration	Compliance monitoring, integration with energy markets (EPEX SPOT, Nord Pool), regulatory updates	1,300,000	1,200,000	1,000,000	ACER Market Integration Report

Grid expansion & new EV/ET integrations	Adaptation of ODP to new EV charging stations, grid expansions, and additional RES installations	2,000,000	1,000,000	800,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report
Network maintenance (5G/LPWAN)	Upkeep of connectivity infrastructure (LoRaWAN, 5G towers, secure grid connectivity)	2,000,000	1,000,000	700,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Market trading fees (energy)	Participation fees in wholesale energy trading platforms, transaction fees	1,200,000	1,000,000	800,000	ACER Market Integration Report
Miscellaneous costs	Hardware replacements, staff training, regulatory compliance fees, unexpected expenses	1,500,000	1,000,000	900,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)		15,800,000	10,700,000	8,500,000	

Table 74: OPEX for UCII

OPEX category	Values (€)
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)	35,000,000
Labor cost in the first year	3,946,500
Total discounted OPEX over ten years	315,891,002

Appendix A3: Supplementary materials for cost-benefits analysis of UCIII

Assumptions for costs and benefits calculations

Tables 75 and 76 present the assumptions of UCIII categorized into general assumptions, economic and market assumptions, and technology-specific assumptions.

Table 75: Country specific assumptions for cost-benefit analysis of UCIII

Parameter	Unit	DE	SE	DK	Remarks
Number of data centers considered (N_{DC})	Number	529	95	50	Statista
Annual growth rate	%	8.87	11.06	11.06	Taken from arizon report , Germany report , and here

Average annual electricity consumption per DC (EE_{TOT})	GWh/year	28.37	24.21	45	Converted by consumption/ N_{DC}^{27}
Average electricity tariff (t_e)	€/kWh	0.12	0.13	0.14	Country-specific
CO ₂ emission price (p_{CO_2})	€/tonne	50	60	55	Based on national carbon pricing mechanisms
Air pollutant emission value (P_{AP})	€/tonne	10,000	9,000	9,500	Calculated based on this source
Equivalent full-load hours for RES (h_{eq})	hours/year	1,800	2,000	1,900	For RES generation potential
Current RES capacity	GW	63.5	50.0	8.0	As of 2024 for Germany; estimates for Sweden and Denmark. ²⁸
Projected annual growth rate of RES capacity	%	5	4	6	Based on national energy plans and historical trends. ²⁹
Transaction cost reduction from ODPs ($\%TC_{reduction}$)	%	10	12	9	Includes smart metering & billing automation
CO ₂ displacement per MWh of RES (ERS_{factor})	tCO ₂ /MWh	0.4	0.38	0.42	Based on electricity mix
Energy efficiency improvement with ODPs ($\%EE_{ODP}$)	%	3	4	3.5	From smart metering, AI, and optimization

²⁷ Germany: The Borderstep Institute estimated that data centers in Germany consumed 14 TWh in 2018, 16.3 TWh in 2020, 17 TWh in 2021, and 17.9 TWh in 2022. Based on current trends, they project data center energy consumption could reach 27 TWh in 2030. We use 23 TWh for 2025. Denmark: The Danish Energy Agency commissioned a study in 2021 which estimated that data centers consumed 0.88 TWh in 2020, and have since published data center energy consumption estimates in their annual Energy and Climate Outlook, with an estimate of 1.1 TWh in 2021 and we use 1.5 in 2025. Sweden: The Swedish Energy Agency and the Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE) estimate that data centers in the country used 2.8–3.2 TWh in 2022. Then we use 4.2 TWh for 2025 (source: <https://publications.irc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC135926>). Finally, we assume only 70% the energy consumption from each country comes from RES and with the assumption full-load hour of 1200 hours per year for RES generators. Then the RES_{int} is a result of all this calculations.

²⁸ RES_{int} data is based on the assumption that 20% of the existing renewable energy capacity is integrated into the data center system each year from 2026 onward. In parallel, data center integration into virtual energy communities is assumed to grow by 10% annually, reaching near full participation by 2035. Regarding AI model requirements (AI_{int}), while the number of models typically depends on data center size, for the purposes of this calculation, we assume a minimum of four AI models per data center. These cover energy optimization, workload orchestration, predictive maintenance, and demand-side flexibility and trading.

²⁹ Growth rates for RES capacity are derived from national energy transition plans (e.g., Germany's Energiewende, Sweden's Fossil-Free 2040, and Denmark's Climate Plan 2030).

Load reduction from ODP in peak hours (%LR)	%		15	14	13	Due to grid balancing
Curtailment reduction (%CR)	%		5	6	4.5	From better RES scheduling
Peak load cost savings (C_{MW})	€/MW		125.57	109.93	125.62	Based on EPEX spot market ³⁰
Data center participation in VEC (% $VEC_{engaged}$)	%		10	15	12	ODP-enabled trading & flexibility markets
Self-consumption of RES by DCs (RES_{self})	%		12	15	14	From on-site RES and energy storage
DCs shifting loads to off-peak hours (% DC_{shift})	%		10	12	11	Via orchestration tools
Avoided energy curtailment (ΔE_{curt})	MWh/year		200,000	120,000	70,000	DC flexibility used to absorb RES surplus
Air pollutant reduction per MWh of RES generation ($tonne_{AP/MWh}$)	tonne CO_2/km		0.0025	0.0022	0.0024	Based on grid intensity
P_{peak}	€/kWh		1.50	1.80	2.30	Peak electricity price; Germany's value from, Sweden's from, Denmark's from
P_{off}	€/kWh		0.12	0.0942	0.11	Off-peak electricity price; Germany's value from, Sweden's from, Denmark's from
HPC_{shift}	% of workload	0.1		0.12	0.11	HPC workloads shifted to off-peak hours
AI_{shift}	% of workload	0.1		0.12	0.11	AI workloads shifted to off-peak hours

Table 76: Key technology-specific assumptions for UCIII

Technology	Metric	With ODP	Justification	Source
Smart meters	Energy visibility & optimization	+15% accuracy	Enables real-time monitoring & load control	EU Pilot DC Reports

³⁰ Cost per MW of peak demand is taken from EPEX Sport price of March 14, 2025, for all countries and calculated as 10% this as costs could be avoided using ODP enhanced demand response program.

AI-based load forecasting	Peak demand reduction	-15%	Optimized AI/HPC scheduling	NESO Energy
Workload orchestration tools	Load flexibility	+20%	Enables shifting loads across locations/time	Projected from pilot use cases
Digital twin simulations	Investment optimization	+12% capex ROI	Improved planning & predictive maintenance	IBM DT Exchange
Federated learning	Model accuracy & privacy	+10%	DCs collaborate securely for forecasting	Industry trials
IoT + thermal sensors	Cooling efficiency	+8-10%	Smarter environmental control & waste heat reuse	MDPI + IEA
RES forecasting via weather sensors	Curtailed avoidance	+6%	Matches on-site solar/wind to workload needs	IRENA
5G + Edge integration	Latency reduction	-20%	Real-time data needed for dynamic load balancing	European 5G Observatory
Smart billing & automated settlement	Transaction cost reduction	-10%	Fewer manual errors, faster settlements	AI for Energy Markets
Visualization + DSS dashboards	Operator decision accuracy	+30%	Faster response, fault detection & DR activation	European Data Centre Assoc.

Presentation of CAPEX and OPEX tables

Table 77 presents the CAPEX based on data center sensors, assuming the number of data centers increases by seven each year until 2035, along with the miscellaneous CAPEX incurred in the first year. Tables 79 and 80 present the labor costs and other miscellaneous OPEX for the first year, respectively. Meanwhile, Tables 78 and 81 present the total CAPEX and total OPEX, respectively, for completeness.

Table 77: Miscellaneous deployment CAPEX for UCIII

Component	Unit Cost (€)	Quantity	Total Cost (€)	Remarks
All data center sensors	41,968.564 /data center	681 data centers in 2026	28,580,592	We assume from 2027 to 2035 every year 7 additional DCs and we included the discounted cost for them

Grid forecasting sensors	5,000	Per deployment (10)	50,000	AI-based dynamic grid optimization
Weather forecasting Sensors	10,000	Per deployment (10)	100,000	For renewable forecasting
Virtual energy community (VEC) management software	50,000	Per country	150,000	AI-powered trading software for community participation
AI grid optimization software	500,000	Per country	1,500,000	AI-based demand response & load shifting
Data integration & ETL tools	200,000	Per country	600,000	Market trading, smart billing, and transaction cost optimization
Financial settlement & smart contracts	250,000	Per country	750,000	Automates energy trading & billing verification
Battery storage participation infrastructure	1,000,000	Per country	3,000,000	Smart battery storage for flexibility markets
Comprehensive analytics tools	1,000,000	Per country	3,000,000	Central visualization suite
Admin dashboard	1,000,000	Per country	3,000,000	Control platform
Total upfront cost			40,730,592	

Table 78: CAPEX for UCIII

CAPEX category	Values (€)
CAPEX for data center sensors	28,580,592
Miscellaneous CAPEX	12,150,000
Discounted total CAPEX over ten years	40,730,592

Table 79: Labor costs for UCIII

Category	DE	SE	DK	Total jobs	Average salary (€)	Total cost (€)
Data analytics and maintenance	20	10	7	37	50,000	3,850,000
AI-models in DCs and grid optimization	15	8	6	29	55,000	1,595,000
ODP software interconnections and cybersecurity	10	6	4	20	60,000	1,200,000
Labor cost in the first year	45	24	17	86		6,645,000

Table 80: OPEX for each country in the first year for UCIII

Category	Remark	DE (€)	SE(€)	DK (€)	Source
Cloud computing & data processing	Core AI/data layer for DCs	3,500,000	2,500,000	1,800,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Software maintenance & updates	Applies fully to DC platforms	1,500,000	1,200,000	900,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report
Grid & sensor maintenance	Only DC-specific sensor systems	2,400,000	1,000,000	750,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Cybersecurity & threat monitoring	Crucial for DC data protection	2,200,000	1,800,000	1,400,000	IEA Electricity Grids Report
Customer support & data analytics	Applies fully (user portals, dashboards)	1,500,000	1,000,000	900,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Market integration	Only applies for VEC-participating DCs	1,000,000	800,000	720,000	ACER Market Integration Report

Network maintenance (5G/LPWAN)	Connectivity for DC IoT platforms	2,400,000	1,760,000	1,520,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
VEC integration	Direct ODP benefit to DCs	1,500,000	1,300,000	1,000,000	ACER Market Integration Report
Miscellaneous costs	Partially applies (training, compliance)	1,080,000	840,000	660,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)		17,080,000	12,200,000	9,650,000	-

Table 81: OPEX for UCIII

OPEX category	Values (€)
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)	38,930,000
Labor cost in the first year	6,645,000
Total discounted OPEX over ten years	269,888,435

Appendix A4: Supplementary materials for cost-benefits analysis of UCIV

Assumptions for costs and benefits calculations

Tables 82 and 83 present the main assumptions to calculate the monetary benefits of the drone-based infrastructure inspection ODP. In addition, Tables 84 and 85 present drone operators used in surveillance of infrastructure growth over ten years and drone operators' growth over ten years of the ODP's lifetime, respectively.

Table 82: Key country-specific assumptions for UCIV

Parameter	Unit	ES	PT	FR	Remarks
Total number of drone operators (DOs) (N_{DOs})	Unit	119,700	110,000	25,700	Spain (Spanish aerial security agency ³¹)

³¹The source for the Spanish number is the Spanish aerial security agency (<https://www.seguridadaerea.gob.es/en/noticias/espana-supera-los-119000-operadores-de-drones-registrados-en-la-agencia-estatal-de>).

					France (Statista ³²) Portugal (inferred, no available data)
Economic costs per operator per month (op_{cost})	€/month	150	250	100	General assumption
Critical infrastructures subject of inspections ($N_{infrastructures}$)	Unit	500	500	500	Assumption ³³
Average administrative labour cost per hour (t_{admin})	€/h	30	40	20	Hours saved per permit (10 hours) ³⁴ Hourly labour costs ³⁵ Annual permits ³⁶

Table 83: Economic and market assumptions for UCIV

Parameter	Metric	Justification	Source
Average time for permit for flying drones	1 year	Time spent since you requested the permit for flying a drone and effectively getting it.	Regulation in EU ³⁷ .
Time reduction getting permits for flying drones	80%	All the actors involved in the same platform	General assumption
Cost reduction from improved inspection frequency and accuracy	20%	Predictive maintenance expects to save costs in critical ³⁸ infrastructures.	20% ³⁹ reduction
Annual maintenance cost of an infrastructure	€100,000	Cost of maintaining an average transport infrastructure per year	Annual maintenance cost (€100,000)

³² Regarding France, Statista states that 338k drones are now registered. Assuming that each DO has a 3 drone fleet, we found a similar number of Spanish DOs.

³³ 5300 km of railways in Spain (<https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/lang/en/gobierno/news/paginas/2024/20240528-trans-european-transport-network.aspx>). We assume 10% of this figure as critical infrastructure for each country and year. Equal number of infrastructures (500) per country ensures consistency and clarity in comparing monetary benefits.

³⁴ Justified by the significant automation and digitalization expected from blockchain and smart-contract-based validations.

³⁵ Reflect varying salaries and overhead costs across the three countries, ensuring realistic and region-specific calculations.

³⁶ Conservatively based on one permit per drone operator per year, aligned with previous assumptions.

³⁷ Also, experience in several projects has been gathered within the project by several interviews. The owner of UC counts this delay as 1 year and a half to flight a drone. Therefore, we take the conservative option of 1 year. <https://megadron.pl/en/blog/drone-regulations-2024-everything-you-need-to-know-1701959301.html>

³⁸ <https://worktrek.com/blog/predictive-maintenance-statistics/>

³⁹ 20% (<https://www.logicline.de/en/predictive-maintenance-a-comparison-of-costs-and-benefits>) is a modest estimation, assuming improved inspection frequency (due to accelerated permit processes) significantly reduces the extent and severity of infrastructure damage through early preventive maintenance.

				per infrastructure ⁴⁰
Average administrative hours spent per permit in the current manual process	Estimated time before the ODP	12 hours/permit	Desk work to comply with every regulation related with flying drones in Europe.	General assumption
	Estimated time after the ODP	2 hours/permit		
Average cost per inspection	€3,000		Manual or semi-digital, without ODP ⁴¹ .	General assumption
Probability of critical infrastructure failures	2%		Annual probability of critical infrastructure failures without regular drone inspections	Reflecting low, yet realistic, baseline scenario.
Reduction in infrastructure failure	30%		Reduction in infrastructure failure probability due to improved inspections	Due to more frequent and accurate inspections
Average cost per infrastructure failure incident	€300,000		This covers emergency repairs, lost productivity, safety incidents, and legal cost	Assume conservatively
Reduction in infrastructure failure	30%		Due to improved inspections, more frequent and accurate inspections ⁴²	ASCE Library
Average cost per infrastructure failure incident	€300,000		Cover for emergency repairs, lost productivity, safety incidents, and legal cost	Assumption
Current annual rate of significant human errors in permit processing	3%		Administrative error rates in complex permit validation processes involving multiple regulatory entities of permits / year	Assumption
Percentage reduction in human errors due to blockchain-based automation	80%		Implementation of blockchain-based smart contracts, ensuring automated ⁴³ , transparent, and secure validations ⁴⁴ .	IBM, CIS Consultant
Average economic cost per compliance error	€5,000		Covering administrative reprocessing, penalties, and operational delays	Fines, corrective actions, administrative

⁴⁰ Conservative, covering routine and emergency repairs.

⁴¹ Including drone operator costs, logistics, planning, and manual validation.

⁴² <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/10.1061/9780784484548.074>

⁴³ <https://www.cisin.com/coffee-break/automate-manual-processes-to-reduce-human-errors-and-costs.html>

⁴⁴ <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/benefits-of-blockchain>

			re-processing, and delays
Average annual insurance cost per worker	€2,500 per worker/year	Insurance cost per worker is considered typical worker accident/liability insurance premiums in the construction/infrastructure sector ⁴⁵	Tech Insurance
Average number of workers required per traditional (manual) inspection	3		General assumptions
Percentage of manual inspections replaced by drone inspections	50%		General assumptions
Estimated reduction in insurance premiums due to lowered risk exposure	40% reduction	Significantly lower accident risks ⁴⁶	NSC
Average vehicle kilometres travelled per inspection (round trip)	200 km per inspection	200 km average per inspection ⁴⁷	General assumptions
Average fuel consumption per vehicle	8 litres per 100 km	8 litres/100 km ⁴⁸	General assumptions
Percentage of inspections replaced by drones	50% of inspections	50% drone replacement rate ⁴⁹	General assumptions
Fuel price per litre (average)	€1.80 per litre	Fuel cost (€1.80/L) and CO ₂ externality savings (€0.25/L) ⁵⁰	General assumptions
Cost savings from avoided CO ₂ emissions per litre of fuel	€0.25 per litre		General assumptions
Average duration of traffic disruption per traditional inspection	4 hours per inspection	4-hour average disruption duration ⁵¹	General assumptions

⁴⁵ <https://www.techinsurance.com/construction-insurance/cost>

⁴⁶ <https://www.nsc.org/workplace/safety-topics/work-to-zero/safety-technologies/drones>

⁴⁷ Typical round-trip distances covered by inspectors.

⁴⁸ Realistic fuel efficiency for inspection vehicles used in infrastructure checks.

⁴⁹ Realistic adoption potential of drone technology for inspections.

⁵⁰ Conservative assumptions on fuel costs and carbon valuation.

⁵¹ Realistic considering typical road inspections, lane closures, or slowdowns.

Average traffic volume affected by each disruption	500 vehicles per hour	500 vehicles/hour affected ⁵²	General assumptions
Average incremental fuel consumption per vehicle due to idling or slow-moving traffic during disruptions	1 litre of fuel per hour of disruption	1 litre/hour incremental fuel consumption ⁵³	General assumptions

Table 84: Drone operators' growth over ten years of the ODP

Year	Drone Operators Spain	Drone Operators France	Drone Operators Portugal	Total DO
2026	119,700	110,000	25,700	255,400
2027	120,897	111,100	25,957	257,954
2028	122,106	112,211	26,217	260,534
2029	123,327	113,333	26,479	263,139
2030	124,560	114,466	26,744	265,770
2031	125,806	115,611	27,011	268,428
2032	127,064	116,767	27,281	271,112
2033	128,335	117,935	27,554	273,823
2034	129,618	119,114	27,829	276,562
2035	130,914	120,305	28,108	279,327

Table 85: Drone operators used in surveillance of infrastructure growth over ten years

Year	Drone Operators Spain	Drone Operators France	Drone Operators Portugal	Total DO
2026	1,197	1,100	257	2,554
2027	1,317	1,210	283	2,809
2028	1,448	1,331	311	3,090

⁵² Moderate to high traffic volumes around typical infrastructure inspection points.

⁵³ Conservatively estimates idling and slow traffic impact.

2029	1,593	1,464	342	3,399
2030	1,753	1,611	376	3,739
2031	1,928	1,772	414	4,113
2032	2,121	1,949	455	4,525
2033	2,333	2,144	501	4,977
2034	2,566	2,358	551	5,475
2035	2,822	2,594	606	6,022

Presentation of CAPEX and OPEX tables

Table 86 presents CAPEX for different technologies of UCIV. Tables 87 and 88 present labor costs and other miscellaneous OPEX for the first year, respectively. Meanwhile, Table 89 presents the total OPEX for completeness.

Table 86: CAPEX for different of technologies of UCIV

Component	Unit cost (€)	Quantity	(€)
LiDAR Sensor, Imaging Camera, Thermal Camera	<u>2,000</u>	2,554	5,108,000
Environmental monitoring sensors	<u>185</u>	200 units	37,000
GPS modules	100	1,500 units	150,000
Cloud storage setup	50,000	3 countries	150,000
Database management systems	<u>20,000</u>	3 countries	60,000
Data lakes / warehouses	200,000	3 countries	600,000
Real-time data processing frameworks	<u>100,000</u>	1 integrated system	100,000
Blockchain platform (Hyperledger/Ethereum)	<u>130,000</u>	1 platform setup	130,000
Smart contracts development	<u>50,000</u>	1 comprehensive system	50,000
Cybersecurity & encryption tools	<u>50,000</u>	1 comprehensive setup	50,000
API connectors development	30,000	3 countries	90,000
Middleware integration with flight systems	100,000	3 integration systems	300,000
Compliance (EU drone regulations & GDPR)	<u>50,000</u>	1 comprehensive setup	50,000
Analytics and compliance dashboards	20,000	3 dashboards (one per country)	60,000

Decision-support tools (inspection scheduling)	50,000	3 countries	150,000
Platform software development	300,000	1 comprehensive software	300,000
Workforce hiring (developers, analysts, specialists)	150,000 per person/year	~ 20 initial staff	3,000,000 per year
Training & onboarding staff	5,000 per person	~ 20 staff trained	100,000
Software deployment & integration	<u>50,000</u>	3 countries	150,000
Total CAPEX			10,635,000

Table 87: Labor costs for each country in the first year of UCIV

Category	ES	FR	PT	Total	Ave. Salary (€)	Total (€)
Drone operation & inspection planning	5	5	5	15	45,000	675,000
Blockchain & smart contract development	3	3	3	9	60,000	540,000
GIS & environmental data analysis	4	4	3	11	50,000	550,000
Cybersecurity & compliance monitoring	3	3	2	8	55,000	440,000
Platform software development & integration	4	4	3	11	58,000	638,000
Training, support & administrative operations	4	4	3	11	42,000	462,000
Labor cost in the first year	29	30	18	65		3,305,000

Table 88: OPEX for each country in the first year for UCIV

Category	Cost Components	France (€)	Spain (€)	Portugal (€)	Source
Cloud computing & data processing	Cloud hosting (AWS, Azure), storage, API usage, real-time video/image data processing	1,000,000	800,000	500,000	European Commission Report on Digital Infrastructure ⁵⁴
Software maintenance & updates	Security patches, blockchain maintenance, smart contract updates, bug fixes	650,000	450,000	300,000	IEA Digitalization & Energy 2017
Cybersecurity & threat monitoring	Annual penetration testing, access controls, encryption, firewalls, GDPR monitoring	1,000,000	1,000,000	600,000	ENISA – EU Cybersecurity Agency ⁵⁵
Inspection support & data analytics	Analytics dashboard hosting, drone permit data	900,000	800,000	450,000	EC – AI for Smart Infrastructure

⁵⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en>

⁵⁵ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/>

	processing, operator and authority support				
Flight system & airspace integration	Integration with ENAIRE/U-Space, blockchain permit validation, compliance with flight regulation	1,000,000	900,000	500,000	EASA/U-Space Regulatory Framework
Infrastructure expansion & scaling	Adaptation to new corridors, airspace changes, additional inspection routes	1,000,000	900,000	500,000	IEA Urban Mobility Report
Network connectivity maintenance	Connectivity (5G modules, satellite uplinks), signal repeaters for remote inspection areas	1,000,000	1,000,000	700,000	EC – 5G Observatory & EU Connectivity Index ⁵⁶
Regulatory compliance & licenses	Airspace licenses, audit costs, cross-border regulation harmonization	1,000,000	900,000	500,000	EASA/Eurocontrol ⁵⁷
Miscellaneous operational costs	Staff upskilling, unforeseen tech support, system redundancies, data storage scaling	1,000,000	800,000	500,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs ⁵⁸
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)		8,550,000	7,550,000	4,550,000	

Table 89: OPEX for UCIV

OPEX category	Values (€)
OPEX the first year (excluding labor cost)	20,650,000
Labor cost in the first year	3,305,000
Total discounted OPEX over ten years	202,068,369

Appendix A5: Supplementary materials for cost-benefits analysis of UCV

Assumptions for costs and benefits calculations

Tables 90, 91 and 92 present the assumptions used to calculate the costs and benefits for UCV.

⁵⁶ <https://5gobservatory.eu/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en>

⁵⁸ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/final_report_network_costs_0.pdf

Table 90: Country specific assumption for UCV

Parameter	Unit	Spain	Remarks
Crane cost (C_{cost})	€/h	1,350	ShipUniverse, based on historical data and projected trends ⁵⁹ .
Total number of cranes (N_{cranes})	Unit	17	2025 port data ⁶⁰ .
Berth rate cost (BR_{cost})	€/h	1.16	2025 regional data ⁶¹ .
Total number of vessels ($N_{vessels}$)	Unit/year	960	2025 port data ⁶² .
Storage area (SA)	m ²	250,000	Sevitrade, storing regional data ⁶³ .
Holding cost (SA_{cost})	€/m ²	4	Sevitrade, storing regional data.
Cost of the penalty for water quality (F_{costW})	€/incident	39,180	WWF ⁶⁴
Probability of having the penalty for water quality ($\%V_W$)	%	30	Historical industry data and typical operational risks in port environments.
Cost of the penalty for air quality (F_{costA})	€/incident	1,600,000	EU FORUM OF JUDGES ⁶⁵
Probability of having the penalty for air quality ($\%V_A$)	%	0.000000001	Historical industry data and typical operational risks in port environments.
Cost of the penalty for waste management (F_{costE})	€/incident	33,592,480	Spanish government ⁶⁶
Probability of having the penalty for waste management ($\%V_E$)	%	10	Historical industry data and typical operational risks in port environments.
Energy savings (ΔE_{ODP})	kWh	500,000	Similar implementation (Otago Port ⁶⁷).

⁵⁹<https://www.shipuniverse.com/12-proven-ways-to-cut-port-fees-fast/#:~:text=,software%20to%20ensure%20optimal%20scheduling>

⁶⁰ <https://www.inlandports.eu/media/Port%20of%20Sevilla%20Brochure.pdf>

⁶¹ <https://www.andalucia.com/boating/mooring.htm>

⁶² www.puertodesevilla.com/images/estadisticas/2024/12_Diciembre2024.pdf

⁶³ <https://sevitrade.com/en/storage/>

⁶⁴ https://wwfeu.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/illegal_water_use_in_spain_may06.pdf

⁶⁵ https://www.eufje.org/images/docConf/visio2020/REPORT_SPAIN.pdf

⁶⁶ Spanish ports operate under a compulsory "no-special-fee" system, where vessels pay a fixed fee for waste reception services regardless of the amount of waste delivered. This fee is calculated based on the vessel's gross tonnage (GT) and includes incentives for compliance, such as discounts for reduced waste generation or regular short-distance traffic. Waste management fine €80 x 419,906 GT. (https://mio-ecsde.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/Agenda-item-6_MARTINEZ-GIL-PARDO-DE-VERA_No-special-fee-system-Spain.pdf)

⁶⁷ The Port Otago Energy Management Programme saved 530 MWh annually through coordinated energy management efforts, illustrating the potential of targeted initiatives (<https://www.deta.global/port-otago-energy-management-programme>)

Electricity price (E_{cost})	€/kWh	0.0958	Market rate for electricity in industrial zones. Eurostat, Energy Market Reports
Fuel saved (ΔF)	L	200,000	AllRead68.
Fuel price (F_{cost})	€/L	1.2	Market price69
Total number of IT workers (N_{IT})	Person	1	Assumptions from 2025 port data70.
IT labor costs (LC_{IT})	€/h	35	INE (National Statistica Institute)
IT Time saved per day ($t_{IT_{saved}}$)	h/day	2	DA desk71 .
Total number of incidents ($N_{incidents}$)	Unit/year	2,646	European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)72
Delayed response halted operation cost (D_{cost})	€/h	614	PORTS EUROPE73.
Old equipment failure response (t_{old})	h	3	UNCTAD (UN Trade and Development)
New equipment failure response with ODP (t_{new})	h	1	Assumptions from impact detection improvement74.
Marine incidents per year (M_I)	Unit	2,646	European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) average reported marine casualties and incidents from 2014 to 2022.
Accidents events that involved human action errors ($\%A_{HA}$)	%	25	European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)
Incident cost (I_{cost})	€/incident	10,000	SHIPUNIVERSE75 (in labor and delay penalties).
CO2 emission price (pCO_2)	€/tonne	55	Based on national carbon pricing mechanisms

⁶⁸ More precisely, an idling truck consumes 3,5 litres of fuel per hour [...] to be multiplied by the daily transits, every day, in every Port access. (<https://www.allread.ai/en/how-access-automation-contributes-to-sustainability-in-port-logistics/>)

⁶⁹ <https://www.dieselogasolina.com/>

⁷⁰ 23,000 employees, port data, expected 5 people in charge of this (www.puertodesevilla.com/images/estadisticas/2024/12_Diciembre2024.pdf).

⁷¹ Users of Marcura's DA-Desk platform reported a reduction in time spent on key tasks from 2-3 hours to just 9-11 minutes per port call—a time savings of approximately 90% per task (<https://www.da-desk.com/delivering-digital-efficiency-and-port-cost-savings/>).

⁷² <https://safety4sea.com/emsas-annual-overview-of-marine-casualties-and-incidents-2023/>

⁷³ <https://www.portseurope.com/seville-zal-presents-improved-financial-results/>

⁷⁴ Planned Maintenance Systems streamline workflows, cutting response time by 30-50% and trained teams resolve issues 2-3x faster (<https://voyagex.ai/predictive-maintenance-fleet-downtime-costs/>).

⁷⁵ <https://www.shipuniverse.com/the-true-cost-of-ship-downtime-data-driven-insights-for-shipowners/>

CO ₂ reduction from fossil-fuel vehicles due to ODP ($\Delta EE_{ET,ODP}$)	tonne CO ₂ /year	11,545	AllRead76
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Table 91: Economic and market assumptions for Port of Seville operation

Parameter	Value	Justification	Source
Annual goods vessel growth rate	8% per year	Estimated based on historical trends in port.	Statista, Port Industry Reports
Annual port traffic growth rate	8% per year	Estimated based on historical trends in port.	Statista, Port Industry Reports

Table 92: Key technology-specific assumptions for UCV

Technology	Metric	With ODP	Justification	Source
AI-Powered predictive maintenance	Reduction in Unplanned Downtime	15%	Historical implementation results from predictive maintenance in industrial operations.	McKinsey & Company, Industry Reports
Automated scheduling and dispatch	Reduction in Average Ship Wait Time	10%	Improved logistics coordination using AI and real-time data feeds.	Port Logistics Reports, AI in Transport Studies
Real-time cargo tracking with IoT	Reduction in Lost/Misrouted Cargo	20%	Studies on IoT tracking efficiency in reducing cargo mishandling and theft.	IoT Market Studies, Logistics Efficiency Papers
Shore power for socked ships	Reduction in Ship Emissions at Port	90%	Case studies of ports using shore power to cut emissions from docked ships.	Port Energy Reports, Environnemental Agenciers
RES integration	Increase in Renewable Energy Usage	40%	Projections based on current port investments in green energy sources.	Renewable Energy Port Initiatives
AI-driven decision support for non-compliance	Reduction in Regulatory Non-Compliance	50%	Regulatory compliance reports indicating effectiveness of AI in tracking adherence.	Compliance and Governance Reports

Presentation of CAPEX and OPEX tables

Table 93 presents CAPEX of considering different technologies. Meanwhile, Tables 94 and 95 present labor costs and other miscellaneous OPEX for the first year, respectively. Finally, Table 96 presents the total OPEX for completeness.

⁷⁶ If we extrapolate a deployment on the scale of Spain (based on the current volumes of TEUs), with for instance 5 minutes of shorter waiting time per container, this will allow a reduction of 11,545 tons of CO₂ per year (<https://www.allread.ai/en/how-access-automation-contributes-to-sustainability-in-port-logistics/>).

Table 93: CAPEX for UCV

Component	Unit cost (€)	Quantity	Total cost (€)	Remarks
AI camera	700-1,500/camera ⁷⁷	Depending on the number of cameras	165,000	To monitor port operations
Drone fleet	2,000-3000/drone ⁷⁸	Depending on the number of drones	60,000	To monitor port operations
IoT environmental sensors	2,000/site ⁷⁹	Per key locations (10)	400,000	To monitor port environmental conditions
Connectivity infrastructure (5G/LPWAN)	100,000/region	Per deployment zone (1)	100,000	
Communication protocols & message queues	1 million	Per country	1,000,000	
Databases & data lakes	1 million	Per country	1,000,000	
Data integration middleware	1.5 million	Per ODP	1,500,000	
API management	1.5 million	Per ODP	1,500,000	
Digital twin	1.5 million	Per country	1,500,000	For simulations
Comprehensive analytics tools	1 million	Per country	1,000,000	Provide improvement to operations
Admin dashboard	1 million	Per country	1,000,000	
Predictive maintenance tools	1.5 million	Per country	1,500,000	
Automatic compliance middleware	1.5 million	Per country	1,500,000	
Software deployment & integration	1 million	Per country	1,000,000	For integrate data from different sources
Total upfront cost			13,475,000	

Table 94: Labor cost in the first year of UCV

Category	Job	Ave. Salary (€)	Total (€)
Data analytics & maintenance	5	47,500	237,500
Deployment & traffic monitoring	3	44,000	132,000

⁷⁷ ([⁷⁸ \(\[⁷⁹ <https://www.fiware.org/2021/11/25/revolutionary-ai-air-pollution-system-powered-by-fiware/#:~:text=To%20achieve%20this%2C%20Breeze%20Technologies,and%20accuracy%20of%20sensor%20data>\]\(https://www.dronepilotgroundschool.com/how-much-does-a-drone-cost/#:~:text=Drones\), expected 20 drones.</p>
</div>
<div data-bbox=\)](https://mammothsecurity.com/blog/commercial-security-camera-installation-cost/#:~:text=Depending%20on%20the%20quality%20and,1%2C500%E2%80%94including%20the%20expense%20of), expected 110 cameras.</p>
</div>
<div data-bbox=)

Operational optimization	5	55,000	275,000
ODP Software development & cybersecurity	7	60,000	420,000
Labor cost in the first year	20		1,064,500

Table 95: OPEX for the first year of UCV

Category	Cost components	Spain (€)	Source
Cloud computing & data processing	Cloud hosting (AWS, Azure, Google Cloud), API calls, AI model retraining, and real-time data processing	1,000,000	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Software maintenance & updates	Regular software patches, AI model retraining, security updates, bug fixes	1,000,000	Maddevs.io ⁸⁰
Sensor maintenance	Firmware updates, sensor replacements, performance monitoring of adaptive environmental sensor	309,180	European Commission Report on Network Costs ⁸¹
AI driven cameras	Maintenance and support	740,027	Mammoth security ⁸²
Cybersecurity & threat Monitoring	Annual penetration testing, firewalls, intrusion detection, identity access management	1,500,020	Safety4sea ⁸³
Customer support & data analytics	Running analytics dashboards, AI-driven reports, customer and grid operator support	1,500,000.00	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Network maintenance (5G/LPWAN)	Upkeep of connectivity infrastructure (LoRa WAN, 5G towers, secure grid connectivity)	1,500,000.00	European Commission Report on Network Costs
Miscellaneous costs	Staff training, regulatory compliance fees, unexpected expenses	2,000,000.00	European Commission Report on Network Costs
OPEX in the first year (excluding labor cost)			9,549,227

Table 96: OPEX for UCV

OPEX category	Values (€)
OPEX in the first year	9,549,227

⁸⁰ <https://maddevs.io/customer-university/software-maintenance-costs/>

⁸¹ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/final_report_network_costs_0.pdf

⁸² <https://mammothsecurity.com/blog/commercial-security-camera-installation-cost#:~:text=Depending%20on%20the%20quality%20and,1%2C500%E2%80%94including%20the%20expense%20of>

⁸³ <https://safety4sea.com/maritime-cyber-security-piecing-the-puzzle-together/>

Labor cost in the first year	1,064,500
Total discounted OPEX over ten years	92,843,056

Appendix A6: Supplementary materials for cost-benefits analysis of UCVI

Assumptions for costs and benefits calculations

Tables 97 and 98 present the assumptions necessary to calculate the costs and benefits of UCVI.

Table 97: Country specific assumption for calculations

Parameter	Unit	ES	PT	Remarks
Total ships per year ($N_{\text{ship,proc}}$)	Unit	4,101	2,391	Stats from ports ⁸⁴
Tonnage (T)	Tons	7,653,993	5,544,216	Stats from ports ⁸⁵

Table 98: Key technologic, economic and market assumptions for UCVI

Parameter	Value	Justification	Source
Fuel consumption/Ton-Km	0.000003 litres/ton-km	Average fuel consumption estimation	Industry reports ⁸⁶ & academic studies ⁸⁷
Typical trade route distance	10,000 km	Common transatlantic maritime shipping distance	Maritime route data
Fuel price/ton	€750/ton	Based on current fuel market prices for maritime transport	Industry fuel pricing sources ⁸⁸
Estimated reduction in fuel consumption	5%	Studies on route optimization and smart port operations indicate a 10% reduction	Transport decarbonization studies ⁸⁹
Cargo handling time/ship	12h/ship	The time for a ship to load/unload	Based on port efficiency reports ⁹⁰

⁸⁴ <https://leixoes.apdl.pt/en/statistics/stats-report/>

⁸⁵ https://www.apvigo.es/es/paginas/estadisticas_generales

⁸⁶ <https://transportgeography.org/contents/chapter4/transportation-and-energy/fuel-consumption-containerships/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.ieabioenergy.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/Marine-biofuel-report-final-Oct-2017.pdf>

⁸⁸ <https://shipandbunker.com/news/world/571509-analysis-bunker-price-outlook-for-2025>

⁸⁹ <https://www.shipuniverse.com/data-driven-route-optimization-the-secret-to-faster-cheaper-voyages/>

⁹⁰ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1101596/port-turnaround-times-by-country/>

Reduction in cargo handling time	10%	Better digital coordination and real-time tracking (AI + IoT)	Several studies suggestions ⁹¹
Average waiting time	6h/ship	The time for a ship to enter the port	Industry Benchmarks ⁹²
Reduction waiting time	10%		Assumption
Operational costs ship/h	€2.000/h	Fuel & crew costs for ships at birth or anchorage	Fuel usage and crew expenses during waiting time. Industry benchmarks ⁹³
Affected stakeholders in a port	Logistic & Freight Companies: 1,500 Shipping and transport Operators: 800 Manufacturers and exporters: 1,000 Custom and Trade authorities: 50 agencies Total: 3,350	All the stakeholders related to both ports.	The total affected entities were estimated based on port activity, logistics sector data, and industry benchmarks
Carbon footprint tracking & compliance reporting	€10,000 per entity/year	Estimated labour, audit, and documentation costs	Industry benchmark ⁹⁴
Reduction in administrative workload	5%		Based on digitalization case studies in logistics & compliance
Average fine per non-compliant entity/year	€20,000	Data from ports	Industry benchmark ⁹⁵
Estimated number of entities at risk/year	15% of 3,300 = 495	Data from ports	Assumptions
Reduction of compliance risk	50%		Based on automation & transparency improvements
CO2 emissions factor	10g CO2/ton-km	CO2 emissions to save	Industry benchmarks ⁹⁶
CO2 reduction percentage	5%	Savings based on optimization of the routes AI-Driven	Industry benchmarks ⁴

⁹¹ <https://www.msc.com/en/lp/blog/technology/ai-shipping-development>

⁹² <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-023-38080-2>

⁹³ <https://www.shippingaustralia.com.au/ship-operating-costs-up-773-demand-up-supply-up-congestion-up-shipper-propaganda-up/>

⁹⁴ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7662751/>

⁹⁵ <https://shipandbunker.com/news/world/676099-imo2020-survey-highlights-huge-variance-in-noncompliance-penalties>

⁹⁶ <https://www.ecta.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/ECTA-CEFIC-GUIDELINE-FOR-MEASURING-AND-MANAGING-CO2-ISSUE-1.pdf>

CO2 credit price	€50/ton	Cost of tons for CO2	Europe stats ⁹⁷
Emission factors for maritime transport	SOx: 0.2 g/ton-km NOx: 0.4 g/ton-km PM10: 0.05 g/ton-km	Emissions for maritime transport	Based on EU air pollution damage cost estimates ⁹⁸
Health cost savings/ton of pollutant avoided	SOx: €30,000 per ton NOx: €12,000 per ton PM10: €100,000 per-ton	Price per ton of SOX savings	Based on EU air pollution damage cost estimates ⁹⁹
Percentage of the pollutant avoided	1%	% of the pollution that can be assigned to the implementation of the ODP	Assumptions

Presentation of CAPEX and OPEX tables

Tables 99, and 100, present CAPEX of TEUs sensors for each year¹⁰⁰, miscellaneous CAPEX for different technologies, respectively. Tables 102 and 103 present labor costs and other miscellaneous OPEX for the first year, respectively. Finally, Tables 101 and 104 present the total CAPEX and OPEX, respectively.

Table 99: CAPEX of TEUs sensors for each year

Year	TEUs	Incremental TEUs	Price (€)	Costs (€)
2026	45870	0	381	
2027	48164	2294	381	840,215
2028	50572	4702	381	1,722,441
2029	53100	7230	381	2,648,777
2030	55755	9885	381	3,621,431
2031	58543	12673	381	4,642,718
2032	61470	15600	381	5,715,069
2033	64544	18674	381	6,841,037
2034	67771	21901	381	8,023,304
2035	71159	25289	381	9,264,684

⁹⁷ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1322214/carbon-prices-european-union-emission-trading-scheme/>

⁹⁸ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1322214/carbon-prices-european-union-emission-trading-scheme/>

⁹⁹ <https://www.ecta.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/ECTA-CEPIC-GUIDELINE-FOR-MEASURING-AND-MANAGING-CO2-ISSUE-1.pdf>

¹⁰⁰ Fuel flow sensors¹⁰⁰ (105€), CO2¹⁰⁰ (13€)/NOx¹⁰⁰ (10€)/SOx¹⁰⁰ (8€) sensors, GPS tracking devices¹⁰⁰ (245€). The data for the TEUs are directly from the ports of Vigo and Leixoes.

Total CAPEX of TEUs sensors	43,319,675
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Table 100: Miscellaneous CAPEX for technologies in UCVI

Component	Price/unit (€)	(€)	Justification
Road freight sensors	464/Truck	4,507,340	On board diagnostic systems
Port facilities sensors	1,200/ port	2,400	Air quality sensors (CO ₂ (13€)/+ PM/NOx sensors (120€) + SOx (8€)), energy meters ¹⁰¹ (1,067€)
Connectivity infrastructure (5G/LPWAN)	250,000/port	500,000	5G network ¹⁰²
Data integration middleware	14,000/port	2,800	Middleware ¹⁰³
Blockchain Network	25,000/port	50,000	Medium complexity Blockchain-based app ¹⁰⁴
AI models for optimization routes	14,230/port	28,460	Azure calculator (Azure ML, GPU NDm A100 v4-series)
AI camera	700/camera	70,000	To monitor port operations
Drone fleet	2,000/drone	60,000	To monitor port operations
IoT environmental sensors	2,000/port	4,000	To monitor port environmental conditions
Connectivity infrastructure (5G/LPWAN)	200,000/port	400,000	Connectivity setups (for different ports/sites) ensuring stable operation
Communication protocols & message queues	500,000/port	1,000,000	Secure, real-time communication protocols and messaging infrastructure
Databases & data lakes	250,000/port	500,000	Cloud-native, scalable storage for structured (databases) and unstructured (data lakes)
Data integration middleware	500,000/port	1,000,000	Large-scale integration beyond pilot phase
API management	500,000/port	1,000,000	Gateway services, security, analytics, and lifecycle management
Digital twin	500,000/port	1,000,000	Virtual models of physical port operations
Comprehensive analytics tools	150,000/port	300,000	BI dashboards to visualize environmental, logistics, and operational KPIs

¹⁰¹ [energy meters](#)

¹⁰² [5G network](#)

¹⁰³ [Middleware](#)

¹⁰⁴ [Medium Complexity Blockchain-Based App](#)

Software deployment & integration	100,000/port	200,000	Integration across all subsystems
Software deployment & integration	500,000/port	718,985	Adjusted deployment/integration based on scope
Total		11,343,985	Fixed and onetime costs

Table 101: CAPEX for UCVI

CAPEX category	Values (€)
Total fixe CAPEX for technologies	11,343,985
Discounted CAPEX of TEUs sensors	43,319,675
Total CAPEX over ten years	54,663,660

Table 102: Labor cost for the first year of UCVI

Category	ES	PT	Total	Ave. Salary (€)	Total (€)
Maritime & logistics data management	8	6	14	47,000	658,000
Emissions monitoring & reporting	5	4	9	45,000	405,000
Route optimization & AI modelling	6	5	11	52,000	572,000
ODP software development & integration	4	2	6	58,000	348,000
Regulatory compliance & admin support	5	3	8	42,000	336,000
Labor cost in the first year	28	20	48		2,319,000

Table 103: OPEX for the first year of UCVI

Component	Annual cost (€)	Justification
Software & security updates	242,800	More frequent updates and cybersecurity ¹⁰⁵ needs (Azure Calculator, Application Gateway)
Blockchain maintenance	1,250,000	15-25% of blockchain cost ¹⁰⁶
Databases & data lakes	508,200	Azure calculator ¹⁰⁷ (Azure SQL database, 1TB)
Communication protocols & message queues	65,900	MQTT ¹⁰⁸

¹⁰⁵ [Cybersecurity](#)

¹⁰⁶ [Blockchain cost](#)

¹⁰⁷ [Azure calculator](#)

¹⁰⁸ [MQTT](#) costs

API management	54,800	Azure calculator ¹⁰⁹ (API management)
Comprehensive analytics tools	3,355,300	Azure calculator (Power BI Embedded, 4 cores, RAM 10 GB)
Admin dashboard	91,300	Azure calculator (Azure Managed Grafana, 30 users)
Software deployment & integration	2,500,000	<u>50 engineers full time to maintain</u>
OPEX in the first year (excluding labor cost)		8,068,300

Table 104: OPEX for UCVI

OPEX category	Values (€)
OPEX in the first year	8,068,300
Labor cost in the first year	2,319,000
Total discounted OPEX over ten years	87,620,320

¹⁰⁹ [Azure calculator](#)